

**IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION
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POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL

**ENHANCED DIAGNOSTIC AND INTERPRETABLE MODEL FOR FEBRILE
DISEASES USING EXPLAINABLE AI AND LARGE LANGUAGE MODEL**

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AUGUST 2025

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**THESIS SUBMITTED TO POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL IN PARTIAL
FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY(PhD) COMPUTER SCIENCE**

AUGUST 2025

DECLARATION

I, Attai, Kingsley Friday with Matriculation Number: **IAUE/2022/COM/PhD/0003** declare that this thesis on **“Enhanced Diagnostic and Interpretable Model for Febrile Diseases Using Explainable AI and Large Language Model”** was carried out by me; that this is my original work and it has not been submitted wholly or in part for the award of a degree in any institution.

CERTIFICATION

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POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL**

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BY

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The board of Examiners certifies that this Thesis is accepted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Computer Science.

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to GOD ALMIGHTY for the strength to complete this work.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABDPN: Abdominal Pains
AHP: Analytic Hierarchy Process
AIDS: Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
API: Application Programming Interface
BERT: Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BITAIM: Bitter taste in Mouth
BLDYURN: Bloody Urine
CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CGHDRY: Cough (initial dry)
CHLNRIG: Chills and Rigors
CHSIND: Chest Indraw
CHSPN: Chest Pain
CNST: Constipation
CTRH: Catarrh
CHW: Community Health Worker
DDM: Disease Diagnostic Model
DIFBRT: Difficulty Breathing
DL: Deep Learning
DRYCGH: Dry Cough
ENFVR: Enteric Fever (Typhoid Fever)
FTG: Fatigue
FOLBRT: Foul Breath
FVR: Fever
GENBDYPN: Generalized Body Pain
GENRSH: Generalized Rashes
Google Colab: Google Colaboratory
GPT: Generative Pre-trained Transformer
HDACH: Headache
HGGDFVR: High-grade Fever
HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

HVAD: HIV and AIDS
IDE: Integrated Development Environment
LIME: Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
LLaMA: Large Language Model Meta AI
LLM: Large Language Model
LMIC: Low to Middle-income Country
LMPNDSWL: Lymph Node Swelling
LRM: Language Representation Models
LTG: Lethargy
LWGDFVR: Low-grade Fever
MAL: Malaria
MCDA: Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
MFA: Multi-factor Authentication
MIF: Model Interpretability Framework
MLP: Multi-layered Perceptron
MSCBDYPN: Muscle and Body Pain
NFRF: New Frontiers in Research Fund
NLP: Natural Language Processing
MUTUCR: Mouth Ulcer
NGTSWT: Night Sweats
NUS: Nausea
RBAC: Role-based Access Control
RF: Random Forest
RTI: Respiratory Tract Infection
SHAP: SHapley Additive exPlanations
SO: Standing Order
SRTRT: Sore Throat
SPPBPN: Suprapubic Pains
SWRFVR: Stepwise Rise Fever
PaLM: Pathways Language Model
PNFLURNTN: Painful Urination
TB: Tuberculosis

UML: Unified Modeling Language

URNFQC: Urinary Frequency

UTI: Urinary Tract Infection

VMT: Vomiting

VS Code: Visual Studio Code

WHZ: Wheezing

WHO: World Health Organization

XGBoost: Extreme Gradient Boost

XAI: eXplainable Artificial Intelligence

XLNet: eXtreme Language Understanding

ABSTRACT

Tropical febrile diseases pose significant public health challenges in tropical regions, particularly in resource-limited settings, where timely and accurate diagnoses are critical for effective disease management. However, existing diagnostic systems are black-box and often lack interpretability, making it difficult for healthcare practitioners to understand and trust machine learning (ML) predictions. Additionally, the existing system excludes younger patients, limiting its applicability. This study aimed to develop an integrated diagnostic system that enhances interpretability by leveraging machine learning (ML), Explainable AI (XAI), and a large language model (LLM). A dataset comprising 3,914 patient records with 32 symptoms was obtained from a New Frontiers in Research Fund-sponsored project and preprocessed for analysis. Random Forest (RF) was trained with hyperparameter tuning using GridSearchCV and evaluated with 5-fold cross-validation to optimize its performance. The tuned model achieved high diagnostic performance, demonstrating its effectiveness in diagnosing six febrile diseases. To enhance interpretability, a Model Interpretability Framework (MIF) was incorporated, integrating Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) for visual insights and ChatGPT for textual explanations. This combination provided users with a clear understanding of the diagnostic process, addressing the limitations of black-box ML models. The system was implemented using Python in a development environment that included Google Colaboratory, Visual Studio Code, Flet, and MySQL for database management. Agile development methodology and Unified Modeling Language tools were employed to create a user-friendly design for clinicians and patients. The diagnostic system was evaluated using precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC metrics. The RF model achieved outstanding precision for most diseases, high recall (≥ 0.97), and an AUC-ROC of 0.99, indicating nearly flawless training performance with few misclassifications. On the test dataset, the model performed better in diagnosing malaria (F1-score = 88%, precision = 85%), urinary tract infection (F1-score = 72%, precision = 80%), and respiratory tract infection (F1-score = 72%, precision = 77%). The evaluated system demonstrated strong predictive performance, correctly identifying 72 out of 99 tested patient cases, with 26 cases misclassified and one case completely missed. It achieved the highest detection rates for Malaria and HIV/AIDS, accurately identifying all cases without false positives. This work enhances diagnostic solutions for tropical healthcare settings by improving explainability and ensuring inclusivity for younger patients, addressing key limitations in existing systems. The integration of ML, XAI, and LLM enhances diagnostic performance and lays the groundwork for future AI-driven healthcare innovations, ultimately improving health outcomes in resource-scarce regions. Healthcare providers should adopt this system to enhance the efficiency of disease diagnosis and extend the system to diagnose additional medical conditions.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Diagnosing tropical febrile diseases in patients can be a huge challenge for healthcare providers due to the confusing symptoms presented by these diseases. Accurate diagnosis of these diseases requires a combination of laboratory testing, clinical evaluation, and, in specific situations, sophisticated diagnostic instruments that may not be easily accessible in some hospitals and health centres in countries with low- to middle-income economies (LMICs). In medical contexts, “febrile” is frequently used to describe conditions characterized by an elevation in body temperature. Diseases with fever as an accompanying symptom are known as febrile diseases, and they are the leading cause of high mortality rates throughout the world's tropical and subtropical regions (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023a; Centres for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2021; Guo et al., 2017). Fever or pyrexia is a surge in the body temperature above the normal diurnal variations of 36.5⁰C to 37.5⁰C and it is often seen as a symptom of an infectious disease. Febrile diseases are prevalent in tropical and subtropical regions due to the high temperature, heavy rainfall, and high humidity, which create favourable conditions for infectious agents. Several factors contribute to the prevalence and thriving of these diseases in tropical and subtropical regions. Environmental factors, biological factors such as the high biodiversity, and social factors such as poor sanitation and vector control, drug resistance, and self-diagnosis contribute to increasing the burden of tropical diseases in these regions.

Tropical diseases are infectious and non-infectious diseases, as well as diseases caused by environmental conditions or nutritional deficiencies (Rupali, 2019). Infectious diseases are caused by pathogens, which are harmful agents to a susceptible host (human body), and these pathogens can be viruses, bacteria, fungi, or parasites. Infectious diseases are classified into viral, bacterial, parasitic, and fungal diseases (Goeijenbier et al., 2014). Humans can become infected with these pathogenic or infectious agents through an infected person, animal, vehicle, airborne

particle, or vector. A vehicle is anything that is contaminated and can be found in our environment, such as a table, clothing, water, food, tools, etc., while a vector is an animal or insect that spreads an infectious agent from one infected person or animal to another (Ekpenyong et al., 2020). Infectious illnesses are the most common cause of fever, and fever is the patient's defensive reaction to an infection (Kluger et al., 1998). According to Paul (2024), these infectious diseases are typically categorized into three groups: those that result in high rates of death, those that heavily burden the population with disabilities, and those that, because of their sudden and rapid spread, may have catastrophic repercussions on a worldwide scale. It is projected that between 2030 and 2050, the effects of climate change will result in approximately 250,000 deaths annually due to tropical diseases, diarrhoea, heat stress, and undernutrition (WHO, 2023b). According to Albareedy and Ramadan (2023), Africa has been found to have a high prevalence of both emerging and reemerging tropical diseases, which is one of the main causes of death on the continent.

The demographic group for the study is patients above four (4) years old because the data collection instrument employed was not designed to capture relevant symptoms in younger children. Therefore, records of patients under the age of 5 years will be removed from the dataset because of the potential impact of including this age group without proper symptom documentation and the potential consequences of inaccurate data on the machine learning model's performance. The tropical diseases considered in this study include typhoid fever (Marchello et al., 2022), malaria (WHO, 2023), HIV and AIDS (Uwishema et al., 2022a), respiratory tract infection (Woodall et al., 2022), urinary tract infection (Li et al., 2022), and Tuberculosis (Uwishema et al., 2022b). Several factors, such as climate and environmental conditions, poor sanitation and hygiene, overcrowding, urbanization, limited access to healthcare, poverty, and malnutrition, as well as political and economic factors, are responsible for the prevalence of these diseases in tropical regions, particularly Nigeria. Therefore, early diagnosis and treatment of these diseases can prevent several complications, such as reducing the risk of transmission to others, the risk of intestinal perforation in typhoid fever, and ultimately death. According to the WHO (2023a), the initial symptoms of malaria may be mild, similar to many other febrile

diseases, and if *P. falciparum* malaria is not diagnosed and treated early, it can cause severe illness and death in as little as 24 hours.

Since tropical diseases present confusable symptoms, it is important to consider the presence of two or more additional conditions that may complicate diagnoses. The presence of comorbidities can complicate the management and treatment of tropical febrile diseases, necessitating a comprehensive strategy to address all of the health issues patients may be facing. Comorbidities should be a cause of concern for healthcare professionals since they can complicate the diagnosis and treatment of tropical febrile diseases. The word "comorbidity" in medicine refers to the coexistence of one or more additional chronic health conditions with a primary disease. The prefix "co" means together, and the word "morbidity" is the presence of an illness or a disease. Diagnosing tropical febrile diseases can be challenging because of overlapping symptoms, a range of clinical presentations, and limited access to qualified medical professionals in low- to middle-income areas. According to Meyer et al. (2013), diagnostics accuracy declines when healthcare providers encounter difficult cases. Therefore, timely differential diagnoses of these diseases by harnessing the power of technology are important to avoid several complications and possible misdiagnoses (Uzoka et al., 2017).

The application of technology in healthcare can reduce missed, delayed, or inaccurate diagnoses (El-Kareh et al., 2013). The application of large language models (LLMs) and artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare could lead to better patient outcomes and revolutionize the solutions to healthcare-related challenges such as handling the high level of imprecision, especially in the diagnosis of illnesses (Alowais et al., 2023; Thirunavukarasu et al., 2023; Briganti, 2023; Yang et al., 2023; Agrawal et al., 2022). AI provides valuable decision support by synthesizing and interpreting complex medical information (Kaul et al., 2023) while LLMs can help with the interpretation of unstructured data, like clinical notes, contributing to evidence-based decision-making in patient care (Yang et al., 2022). ML algorithms are seen as "black boxes," casting doubt on their methods of operation and judgmental processes. Because of this uncertainty, machine learning systems have found it challenging to be accepted in sensitive but crucial domains such as healthcare, where they have enormous

potential benefits (Linardatos et al., 2020). To address this challenge of interpretability and transparency, eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) has been developed to enable human users to comprehend and accept the output generated by machine learning algorithms. Consequently, the use of XAI in healthcare can result in better collaboration between AI and medical professionals and increased user confidence in AI systems.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Febrile diseases remain a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, with the heaviest burden concentrated in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). In the WHO African Region alone, malaria accounted for an estimated 246 million cases (94% of global cases) and 569,000 deaths (95% of global malaria deaths) in 2023 (WHO, 2023a). Alongside malaria, typhoid fever continues to impose a considerable health burden, with reports of culture-confirmed cases from 42 out of 57 African countries between 1900 and 2018, and with outbreaks increasing in frequency and scale over time (Kim et al., 2019). HIV/AIDS remains highly prevalent in sub-Saharan Africa, where 25.6 million people were living with the virus at the end of 2022, of whom 20.8 million were receiving antiretroviral therapy (WHO, 2023d). Tuberculosis (TB), often co-occurring with HIV, is also widespread, with the continent accounting for one-quarter of all new TB cases globally in 2022 (2.5 million people) and 424,000 TB-related deaths, over one-third of the global total (WHO, 2023e). Respiratory tract infections (RTIs) add further to the burden: a systematic review across Africa between 2013 and 2023 found pooled prevalence rates of 19.9% for rhinovirus, 12.0% for adenovirus, 8.9% for RSV, 5.2% for influenza, and 5.0% for *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Nyahoda et al., 2024). Similarly, urinary tract infections (UTIs) affect about 3.7% of the African population, more than double the global average of 1.6% (Mengistu et al., 2023).

These statistics reveal that malaria is not an isolated health problem but is closely linked with other febrile and infectious diseases, many of which share overlapping symptoms and risk factors. The combined burden of malaria, typhoid, TB, HIV/AIDS, RTIs, and UTIs is amplified by weak health systems, limited diagnostic

infrastructure, and inadequate access to skilled physicians in LMICs. This challenge is further compounded by the migration of experienced healthcare workers to developed countries, leaving community health workers (CHWs) to provide frontline services. While CHWs play an essential role, they depend on simplified protocols such as Standing Orders (SOs) that cannot adequately address differential diagnoses when patients present with overlapping or confusable symptoms.

To address these challenges, the Febra Diagnostica (Febra) app was developed as an Android-based mobile health (mHealth) application. Built on an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) model, the app provides a structured way to distinguish among febrile diseases by incorporating multiple risk factors and symptoms. While this represents a pioneering effort, its limitations are notable. AHP is a knowledge-driven rather than data-driven approach, meaning it cannot adapt or improve with new data inputs. The system also excludes patients below 17 years of age, reducing its applicability, and its mathematical complexity makes it less transparent to non-technical stakeholders such as CHWs, potentially limiting acceptance and trust.

In contrast, machine learning (ML) methods such as Random Forest, Extreme Gradient Boosting, and Multi-layer Perceptron offer powerful alternatives for capturing complex, non-linear relationships in large patient datasets. These models can automatically learn patterns and improve diagnostic accuracy. However, their black-box nature poses a major challenge: predictions are often opaque and difficult to interpret, creating mistrust among healthcare providers and limiting adoption in clinical practice. To address this, the integration of Explainable AI (XAI) techniques such as Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) can provide transparency by showing the contribution of each feature to a diagnostic prediction. Furthermore, coupling XAI outputs with Large Language Models (LLMs) enables explanations to be translated into user-friendly narratives tailored to the knowledge level of different stakeholders, from CHWs to physicians.

Despite the growing application of ML in healthcare, there remains a clear knowledge gap in combining ML, XAI, and LLMs for febrile disease diagnosis in resource-poor settings. Existing systems have yet to fully address the dual challenge

of diagnostic performance and interpretability in a way that builds trust, supports decision-making, and aligns with global health goals. This study seeks to bridge this gap by developing a data-driven, interpretable, and communicative diagnostic framework that enhances transparency, fosters stakeholder confidence, and ultimately contributes to reducing the burden of febrile diseases in LMICs.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to enhance the interpretability of febrile disease diagnosis using Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) and Large Language Model (LLM). The objectives of the study were to:

- i. acquire a tropical febrile disease patient dataset from an NFRF-sponsored project, including cases of Enteric Fever, Malaria, HIV and AIDS, Respiratory Tract Infection, Urinary Tract Infection, and Tuberculosis.
- ii. develop a Disease Diagnostic Model (DDM) using the Random Forest (RF) algorithm, chosen for its robustness to noisy data, ability to handle high-dimensional features, and compatibility with interpretability frameworks
- iii. train and test the DDM using an 80/20 split of the febrile disease dataset.
- iv. integrate a model interpretability framework (MIF) to enhance the DDM's transparency.
- v. implement and evaluate the integrated febrile disease diagnostic model using Python and appropriate performance metrics.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study will provide significant benefits to primary, secondary, and tertiary stakeholders in the healthcare sector by improving the interpretability and accessibility of tropical febrile disease diagnosis.

1.4.1 Primary Stakeholders

Medical professionals: doctors, nurses, and community health workers (CHWs), will benefit from an AI-powered diagnostic tool that enhances early detection, reduces the risk of misdiagnosis, and provides interpretable insights into disease predictions. CHWs, especially in resource-limited settings, can leverage this system

to make more informed decisions, reducing the burden on referral hospitals, while doctors and nurses can use it as a decision-support tool to enhance treatment and patient outcomes.

Healthcare organizations: hospitals, clinics, and research institutions can adopt this diagnostic system to improve workflow efficiency, minimize diagnostic errors, and support disease pattern research. By utilizing XAI and LLMs, healthcare facilities can better manage patients, allocate resources efficiently, and advance medical research on febrile diseases.

1.4.2 Secondary Stakeholders

Healthcare Administrators: Hospital administrators and policymakers will gain access to a data-driven approach for improving diagnostic accuracy and optimizing resource allocation. This system can help reduce unnecessary tests, improve patient care quality, and inform policy decisions related to febrile disease management.

Medical Researchers: AI-assisted diagnostics will provide valuable insights into disease modeling, predictive analytics, and treatment responses. Researchers in epidemiology and infectious diseases can leverage the dataset and methodologies developed in this study to advance AI applications in healthcare.

Healthcare Technology Developers: AI developers and healthcare tech companies can build upon this study to refine AI-driven diagnostic tools, enhance their interpretability, and expand their application to other medical conditions. The system's framework can serve as a foundation for future AI innovations in healthcare.

Public Health Officials: Government agencies responsible for disease control and public health policy will benefit from real-time epidemiological data generated by the AI model. This can support disease surveillance, outbreak management, and informed decision-making for healthcare interventions.

Insurance Providers: Health insurance companies can use the system to enhance risk assessment and claims processing, ensuring accurate diagnosis verification. Improved diagnostics will contribute to preventive care, reducing long-term healthcare costs and improving coverage accuracy.

1.4.3 Tertiary Stakeholders

Healthcare Educators: Medical schools and training institutions can incorporate AI-powered diagnostic tools into their curriculum to train future healthcare professionals on AI-assisted medical decision-making.

Healthcare IT Professionals: IT specialists will play a crucial role in implementing and maintaining this AI-driven diagnostic system, ensuring its seamless integration into healthcare infrastructures.

Medical Device Manufacturers: Companies producing diagnostic devices can integrate this AI-powered system to improve the interpretability and reliability of their products, enhancing healthcare delivery in both urban and rural settings.

Pharmaceutical Companies: Drug manufacturers can utilize AI-driven diagnostic insights to develop targeted treatments for febrile diseases, improving drug efficacy and patient care.

This study significantly advances the application of Explainable AI in healthcare, promoting transparency in machine learning-based diagnostics. It provides a replicable framework for integrating XAI and LLMs in disease diagnosis, with potential adaptability to other medical conditions. The findings will inform policymakers, healthcare providers, and researchers, ultimately improving healthcare access, reducing misdiagnosis, lowering costs, and saving lives in tropical and subtropical regions where febrile diseases remain a major health challenge.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The research was conducted in the Niger-Delta region of Nigeria, an area characterized by a high prevalence of tropical febrile diseases due to environmental and socio-economic factors. The study acquired a relevant patient dataset from an NFRF-sponsored project for six tropical febrile diseases: Enteric Fever (ENFVR), Malaria (MAL), HIV and AIDS (HVAD), Respiratory Tract Infection (RTI), Urinary Tract Infection (UTI), and Tuberculosis (TB). A Disease Diagnostic Model (DDM) was designed using the Random Forest (RF) algorithm, and the DDM was trained and tested using an 80/20 data split to ensure robustness and generalizability. To

address the challenge of interpretability often associated with machine learning models, a Model Interpretability Framework (MIF) was integrated into the system. This allowed for transparent and explainable outputs, making the diagnostic recommendations more understandable to healthcare practitioners. The system was implemented and evaluated using the Python programming language and appropriate performance metrics to validate its effectiveness. The work was conducted between July 2023 and January 2025, following an Agile and data-driven development methodology that emphasized iterative design, continuous feedback, and adaptive refinement of the diagnostic system.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

This study adopted the Dual-Process, Pattern Recognition, Transparency and Trust theories.

Dual-Process Theory

In 2008, Jonathan Evans published a paper that examined a wide range of dual-processing theories (Evans, 2008). The study was supported by the Economic and Social Research Council of the United Kingdom. According to this theory, two different cognitive processes go into human thought and decision-making: System 1 and System 2. System 1 is intuitive and automatic, requiring little to no conscious effort. It is the emotional, instinctive, and intuitive side of thought. Examples of tasks involving System 1 include identifying well-known faces and comprehending simple language. System 2 is reflective and deliberative, demanding conscious effort and focus. It calls for more restrained and analytical thought. System 2 works on tasks that require intentional thought, focus, and concentration. It involves making decisions, applying critical thinking, and solving complicated problems. Tasks involving System 2 include solving a mathematical problem, assessing evidence in a logical argument, and consciously trying to override an initial intuitive judgment.

A more thorough and efficient method of illness diagnosis is possible when dual-process theory is combined with machine learning techniques. Machine learning models can be very good at recognizing patterns, which is similar to System 1 thinking. However, they can also facilitate analytical reasoning, which is more in line with System 2 thinking. This makes them an invaluable tool for healthcare professionals when making decisions.

Pattern Recognition Theory

Author Elstein, Shulman, and Sprafka, in the book "Medical Problem Solving: An Analysis of Clinical Reasoning," published in 1978, reported the findings of five-year research on medical problem-solving (Elstein et al., 1978). This study examined

a complex, multifaceted target using a wide range of methods and orientations, including naturalistic, descriptive, experimental, anecdotal, and psychometric. They sought to gain a deeper understanding of medical practice to enhance the training and performance of both current and future practitioners. The capacity to gather relevant case information and apply it wisely to make an appropriate diagnosis is one of the competencies required for the practice of clinical medicine (Elstein et al., 1978). Expert clinicians frequently identify familiar patterns rather than following a methodical analytical process to arrive at quick and accurate diagnoses. The Pattern Recognition Theory has had a significant impact on shaping the understanding of clinical expertise and decision-making in medicine.

When employing machine learning techniques to diagnose diseases, Pattern Recognition Theory is extremely pertinent and useful. Machine learning models have the potential to improve the efficiency, accuracy, and adaptability of pattern recognition in the context of disease diagnosis by utilizing large datasets and sophisticated algorithms.

Transparency and Trust Theory

Finale Doshi-Velez and Been Kim published a paper, “Towards A Rigorous Science of Interpretable Machine Learning,” in 2017. The premise of the theory is that for AI systems to be accepted and trusted, they must be transparent and able to explain their decisions in a way that is both understandable and interpreted. Interpretability and Explainability are important components of this theory. Designing AI systems in a way that makes it possible for people to comprehend how they function and the reasoning behind their decisions is important (Interpretability). For non-experts to understand the decision-making process, the system should give clear and simple explanations for its outputs (Explainability). Doshi-Velez and Kim (2017) emphasized the need for further research in the field of interpretable machine learning because it lacks a consensus on its definition and measurement.

In the context of machine learning and healthcare, Transparency and Trust Theory highlight how critical it is to make machine learning models interpretable, understandable, and trustworthy. Transparency and Trust Theory is crucial for

diagnosing diseases because it addresses important concerns with interpretability, trustworthiness, ethical considerations, collaboration, and regulatory compliance. These concerns are necessary for the successful integration of machine learning models into the delicate and complicated field of healthcare diagnostics.

2.2 Conceptual Review

The conceptual review of this study was reviewed under the following subheading:

- i. Introduction to Tropical Febrile Diseases
- ii. Diagnostic Challenges in Tropical Febrile Diseases
- iii. Importance of Accuracy in Diagnosis
- iv. Machine Learning and Explainable AI in Medical Diagnosis
- v. Large Language Models in Healthcare
- vi. Integration of XAI and LLMs in Medical Diagnosis
- vii. Interpretability and Transparency in AI Models and Medical Diagnosis
- viii. Ethical Considerations in AI-based Diagnosis
- ix. User Acceptance and Trust in AI Diagnosis
- x. Human-Machine Collaboration in Diagnosis

2.2.1 Introduction to Tropical Febrile Diseases

Tropical febrile diseases are a class of infectious diseases with feverish symptoms that are typically found in tropical and subtropical areas of the world. The word "febrile" denotes that fever is one of these diseases' main symptoms and is the hallmark of several medical conditions (Leone et al., 2023). The body's natural reaction to an inflammation, infection, or other underlying medical conditions is fever (Haddad et al., 2023), which indicates that the immune system is triggered and actively battling a disease. The normal range of the body temperature is approximately 37 degrees Celsius, or 98.6 degrees Fahrenheit, though it can vary slightly throughout the day (Fritsch et al., 2023). It is crucial to note that fever is a symptom of an underlying condition, not a specific disease. Febrile diseases can be caused by a variety of pathogens, such as bacteria, viruses, and parasites, and these pathogens are the leading cause of tropical febrile diseases in the tropical and subtropical regions. Vectors like flies, ticks, and mosquitoes are frequently

responsible for the spread of these diseases. These diseases are more prevalent in tropical and subtropical regions due to the favourable environmental conditions for the vectors that carry these diseases. The factors that contribute to the thriving of tropical diseases in tropical and subtropical regions include:

- a) **Environmental Factors:** The high temperature, heavy rainfall, and high humidity create a perfect environment that is both warm and humid for disease vector survival and reproduction. Disease-transmitting vectors also proliferate in these regions due to stagnant water and favourable conditions for vector breeding (Matthew, 2020).
- b) **Biodiversity and Ecosystem Factors:** The complexity of disease transmission cycles is increased by the diversity of hosts and disease vectors that are supported by diverse ecosystems. Also, urbanization and deforestation can alter ecosystems and put people in closer proximity to disease-carrying vectors (Pfäffle et al., 2015; Roche et al., 2012).
- c) **Socioeconomic Factors:** The continuation and spread of diseases are facilitated by inadequate resources, unsanitary conditions, and restricted access to potable water. Inadequate healthcare facilities and services in these regions hamper the monitoring, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases (Eichelberger et al., 2021).
- d) **Globalization Factors:** Diseases are more likely to spread to new areas when there is increased movement of people and goods. In new areas where local populations may not have much immunity, travellers from endemic areas may introduce pathogens (Baker et al., 2022).
- e) **Vector Control and Environmental Management:** Inadequate precautions, like the use of bed nets and insecticides, add to the persistence of diseases spread by vectors in these regions. Climate change and natural events can also impact the distribution, and prevalence of diseases and their vectors (Wilson et al., 2020).
- f) **Public Health Infrastructure:** Tropical diseases persist and spread in tropical and sub-tropical regions due to inadequate systems for disease surveillance, prevention, and control (Engels & Zhou, 2020; Wilson et al., 2020).

Tropical diseases include both non-infectious and infectious diseases. Non-infectious tropical diseases are caused by other factors, such as genetic predispositions, environmental exposures, and nutritional deficiencies while infectious tropical diseases are caused by infectious agents like bacteria, viruses, and parasites (Adly et al., 2019; Attai et al., 2022). Infectious tropical diseases frequently present a range of symptoms, ranging from moderate to severe and occasionally fatal conditions. The infectious tropical diseases that are considered in the study include:

- a) **Malaria:** Malaria is a severe and sometimes life-threatening disease caused by Plasmodium parasites (*P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, *P. falciparum*, *P. ovale*) and spread to humans by Anopheles mosquitoes (Abdulraheem et al., 2022). Symptoms of malaria can be mild or severe. Mild symptoms are fever, headache, chills and sweating. Severe symptoms include fatigue, muscle and joint pain; nausea and vomiting, and difficulty breathing (WHO, 2023). Early detection and treatment of malaria lowers illness, averts fatalities, and helps to lower transmission. Some of the conventional methods for diagnosing malaria include microscopy and Rapid Diagnostic Tests (RDTs). In Microscopy, blood samples are stained with specific dyes to visualize malaria parasites under a microscope (Mfuh et al., 2019; Wilson, 2013). This method is frequently used in medical environments, and useful for identifying species but the limitation is that it requires trained personnel. RDT uses immunochromatographic tests in detecting specific malaria antigens and the results are quick (15–20 minutes) (Mfuh et al., 2019; Mukkala et al., 2018), appropriate for field situations, and don't require specialized equipment. RDTs are less sensitive than microscopy and can occasionally produce false negatives or positives. The World Health Organization advises that parasite-based diagnostic testing, either by microscopy or a quick diagnostic test be used to confirm any suspected cases of malaria (WHO, 2023).

Some advancements in diagnostic technologies for malaria include Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification (LAMP), Nucleic Acid Sequence-Based Amplification (NASBA), Digital PCR, and Malaria Antigen Detection Assays. Using a molecular method of

amplifying and detecting parasite DNA, Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) is a highly sensitive and specific method for identifying and quantifying parasite species. Although PCR is relatively expensive, needs specialized equipment and trained personnel, and is highly sensitive in identifying species at low parasite densities (Mfuh et al., 2019).

LAMP amplifies DNA in an isothermal environment using a molecular technique (Mukkala et al., 2018). The outcomes are visible to the unaided eye, and it is quick and easy. LAMP has a high sensitivity, works quickly, requires less equipment, but needs trained personnel. Isothermal amplification of RNA sequences is used in NASBA. Although it needs specific tools and skilled workers, it has a high sensitivity, quantification potential, and species identification capabilities.

NASBA amplifies and detects RNA through the use of molecular techniques, specifically isothermal amplification of RNA sequences (Varo et al., 2021). It requires specialized equipment and trained personnel, but it has high sensitivity, quantification potential, and species identification capabilities.

Digital PCR partitions samples into thousands of individual reactions, allowing for absolute quantification using molecular techniques for precise quantification of nucleic acids (Pomari et al., 2019). It has high sensitivity, precise quantification, and potential for multiplexing but requires specialized equipment and expertise.

Malaria Antigen Detection Assays employ immunoassays, which use more recent technologies like multiplexed bead-based assays or enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) to detect particular malaria antigens (Plucinski et al., 2021). This technology may be multiplexed and has high sensitivity and specificity, but it may also need specialized personnel and a laboratory setup.

The diagnosis of malaria is now more accessible, accurate, and rapid thanks to technological advancements in diagnostics. The setting (lab or field), the resources at hand, and the particulars of the diagnostic task all play a role in

selecting the best approach. A timely and precise diagnosis is essential for managing and controlling malaria effectively.

- b) **Typhoid Fever:** A bacterial infection that can spread throughout the body and damage numerous organs. If left untreated, it can become fatal or lead to major complications. Typhoid fever is caused by a bacterium called "Salmonella enterica serotype Typhi" (Ashurst et al., 2023) and is spread by contaminated water and food. Symptoms of typhoid fever include fever, headache, abdominal pain, constipation or diarrhea, fatigue, anorexia, nausea, vomiting, and mobility disorder (Nelwan et al., 2023).

Some conventional methods for diagnosing typhoid fever include Blood Culture and widal tests (Bector and Kumar, 2023). Blood culture involves isolating Salmonella Typhi bacteria from a blood sample and culturing the blood in an appropriate medium. If bacteria are present, the culture will grow over time. Because of its high specificity, blood culture is regarded as the gold standard for diagnosis; however, because of its time-consuming nature and need for specialized facilities and equipment, results may take several days to obtain. The Widal test is a widely available, relatively simple method that uses a serological test to detect antibodies against Salmonella Typhi antigens (Sapkota et al., 2023). However, it lacks specificity, is prone to false positives and false negatives, and is not advised for routine use.

Some advancements in diagnostic technologies for typhoid fever include Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA), Typhoid Rapid Tests, Biosensors, and Lateral Flow Assays. PCR amplifies and detects particular Salmonella Typhi DNA sequences using molecular techniques (Mostafa-Mahmoud et al., 2023). Although PCR is very sensitive and, specific, enabling rapid detection, it requires specialized equipment, and trained personnel, which can be relatively expensive.

ELISA detects particular antigens or antibodies using immunoassay. The reaction is measured after the patient's blood or serum is added to wells coated with specific antigens or antibodies (Panzner et al., 2022). Quick results and

automation potential are provided, but the selection of antigens can affect sensitivity and specificity, which may necessitate laboratory equipment.

Typhoid Rapid Tests identify particular antigens or antibodies associated with *Salmonella Typhi* through immunochromatographic assays (Strobel et al., 2022). Variable sensitivity and specificity may be influenced by factors such as the infection stage, but it yields fast results and is appropriate for field settings without the need for specialized equipment.

Biosensors employ a variety of transducers to transform a biological response into an electrical signal that can be used by biosensor devices to identify particular biomolecules linked to *Salmonella Typhi* (Fathi et al., 2023). Although biosensor technologies are still being developed and validated, they have the potential to detect things quickly and sensitively.

Lateral Flow Assays use lateral flow technology to identify particular antigens or antibodies (Frempong et al., 2022). It generates fast results and is appropriate for point-of-care testing, but its sensitivity may be limited and its performance is inconsistent.

The best diagnostic approach to use will depend on several variables, including the resources available, the environment (field or laboratory), and the particulars of the diagnostic task. Integrating various techniques could improve the precision of the diagnosis. Typhoid fever management and treatment require prompt and precise diagnosis.

- c) **Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS):** The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) targets the body's defenses, particularly the white blood cells known as CD4 cells and these CD4 cells are destroyed by HIV, which reduces patient's resistance to opportunistic infections. HIV can spread through blood, perinatal transmission, and sexual contact. Some of the early HIV symptoms are fever, fatigue, swollen lymph nodes, joint and muscle pain, and headache (Yetman, 2023). The advanced stage of HIV infection known as acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) develops when the virus severely

compromises the immune system of the body. When a person's CD4 count drops below 200 cells per milliliter of blood (200 cells/mm³), or if they get one or more opportunistic infections, regardless of CD4 count, they are considered to have progressed to AIDS. AIDS-related symptoms include opportunistic Infections, unexplained and significant weight loss, chronic diarrhea or prolonged gastrointestinal issues, persistent cough, and shortness of breath (CDC, 2021). HIV can be diagnosed through rapid diagnostic tests which provide results the same day and make early diagnosis, treatment, and prevention much easier. HIV self-tests are also available in pharmacies and drug-stores which can also be used by individuals to test themselves (CDC, 2022). A qualified and trained health or community worker at a community centre or clinic must perform confirmatory testing since a single test cannot provide a complete HIV-positive diagnosis.

Some of the conventional methods for diagnosing HIV/AIDS include Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) and Western Blot. ELISA employs a serological test to identify HIV-antibody antibodies. When a patient's blood is added to wells coated in HIV antigens, the reaction is noted. A follow-up confirmatory test may be necessary because ELISA has a high sensitivity and is appropriate for large-scale screening, but it may also give false positive results in cases of early infection (Alfie., 2023).

The Western Blot is an additional test used to confirm the presence of HIV antibodies. It uses electrophoresis to separate and identify particular HIV proteins. It is used to validate positive ELISA results and has a high specificity, but the process is very complicated and may call for specialized equipment (Guiraud et al., 2023; Korkusuz et al., 2022).

Some advancements in diagnostic technologies for HIV/AIDS include Nucleic Acid Testing (NAT), Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), Fourth-Generation HIV Tests, Point-of-Care Tests (Rapid Tests), Antigen/Antibody Combination Tests, and Home Testing Kits. Nucleic Acid Testing (NAT) uses molecular techniques to detect HIV RNA or DNA. It has high sensitivity in

the early detection of infection but requires specialized equipment and is more expensive than antibody tests (Jani and Peter, 2022).

PCR amplifies and detects specific HIV DNA or RNA sequences using molecular techniques (White et al., 2022). Early HIV detection is beneficial for early-stage diagnosis; however, it needs specialized equipment, which can be costly.

Fourth-generation HIV tests identify early antibodies and viral protein in addition to p24 antigen and HIV antibodies. Confirmatory testing is still required even though this method has a shorter window period and better sensitivity during acute infection. It may also have a higher false-positive rate (Shallal et al., 2022).

Point-of-care tests (Rapid Tests) use immunoassays to detect HIV antibodies or antigens. It provides rapid results appropriate for field settings and doesn't require specialized equipment, but may need confirmatory testing due to its variable sensitivity and specificity (Luo et al., 2022; Hsieh et al., 2022).

Antigen/Antibody Combination Tests Detects both HIV antibodies and p24 antigen and it is similar to ELISA, with improved sensitivity. This method reduces the window period, used for routine screening but may have possible false positives and confirmatory testing may be needed (White et al., 2022; Whitney et al., 2022).

Home Testing Kits are meant for self-testing at home and are comparable to rapid tests (King et al., 2022). After gathering their sample and running the test, users can get the results in a matter of minutes. Although testing is now more accessible and confidential thanks to this method, counseling may not be available to all candidates, and accuracy depends on proper application.

The goal of developments in HIV/AIDS diagnostic technologies is to increase test accuracy, shorten the window of opportunity, and improve accessibility. The stage of infection, the resources at hand, and the environment in which testing is done all influence the selected diagnostic approach. Prompt and

precise diagnosis is essential for prompt treatment initiation and prevention of further transmission.

- d) **Respiratory Tract Infection (RTI):** Any infectious disease affecting the upper or lower respiratory tract is referred to as a respiratory tract infection. The common cold, laryngitis, pharyngitis/tonsillitis, acute rhinitis, acute rhinosinusitis, and acute otitis media are examples of upper respiratory tract infections (URTIs) (Gulmez, 2022; Arroll, 2011). Pneumonia, tracheitis, bronchiolitis, and acute bronchitis are examples of lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) (Centre for Clinical Practice [CCP], 2008). Bacteria (such as *Streptococcus pneumoniae*), viruses (such as influenza and respiratory syncytial virus), and fungi are the causative agents for respiratory tract infections (Calderaro et al., 2022). Common symptoms of RTI include fever, dry or productive cough, shortness of breath, chest pain, and fatigue (Honarmand et al., 2022).

Some of the conventional methods for diagnosing RTI include Clinical Assessment, Chest X-ray, Sputum Culture, and Throat Swab and Culture. Clinical assessment entails a physical examination as well as an assessment of clinical symptoms. Medical professionals evaluate symptoms like fever, coughing, and dyspnea and listen for unusual noises coming from the lungs. Although the patient's condition is quickly and initially assessed, the specific pathogen cannot be identified and the patient only exhibits non-specific symptoms.

An X-ray of the chest is used to diagnose anomalies like consolidation or infiltrates by visualizing the lungs and surrounding structures. This approach has limited ability to differentiate between bacterial and viral infections, but it helps identify structural abnormalities (Margret et al., 2022; Ait-Nasser and Akhloufi, 2023).

The purpose of sputum culture is to identify bacterial pathogens by collecting and cultivating sputum samples (Shen & Sergi, 2023). It takes time, might not

work for viral infections, and might be contaminated, but it detects bacterial pathogens and directs antibiotic treatment (Cleveland Clinic, 2023).

Throat Swab and Culture are used to identify bacterial pathogens, like streptococcal bacteria, that cause throat infections (Hirsch, 2023). This technique has limited sensitivity for viral infections, but it works well for bacterial infections like strep throat.

Some advancements in diagnostic technologies for RTI include Nucleic Acid Amplification Tests (NAATs), Immunofluorescence Assays, Point-of-Care Tests (Rapid Tests), Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), Biomarker Detection, and Digital PCR/Droplet Digital PCR.

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is one of the molecular techniques used by NAATs to amplify and detect the genetic material (DNA or RNA) of pathogens (Calderaro et al., 2022). These techniques allow for rapid and accurate detection and multiplexing of pathogens, but they also require specialized equipment and expertise.

Fluorescence signals are used in immunofluorescence assays to show which viral antigens are present (Calderaro et al., 2022). It is limited to certain pathogens and antibodies, but it yields fast results and is appropriate for a variety of respiratory viruses.

Point-of-care tests identify particular viral antigens or antibodies using straightforward lateral flow tests with visual readouts. Although point-of-care tests yield variable sensitivity and specificity and may need confirmatory testing, they are suitable for field settings, yield rapid results, and do not require specialized equipment (Gentilotti et al., 2022).

With Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), multiple pathogens can be identified at once by sequencing RNA or DNA using high-throughput sequencing of genetic material. Although NGS provides thorough and objective detection and is appropriate for identifying novel pathogens, its complex data analysis and high cost are a drawback (Shao et al., 2022).

Biomarker detection uses proteins or other infection-related markers to identify particular biomarkers linked to respiratory infections (Hogendoorn et al., 2022). This approach has variable specificity and might not be able to identify specific pathogens, but it might be able to provide information on treatment response and severity.

Digital PCR and Droplet Digital PCR uses precise quantification of nucleic acids for accurate detection of pathogens by partitioning samples into individual reactions, allowing absolute quantification. It yields high sensitivity and precise quantification but requires specialized equipment and expertise (Milosevic et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2020).

The goal of advancements in respiratory tract infection diagnostic technologies is to increase efficiency, precision, and the capacity to identify multiple pathogens at once. The pathogens that are suspected, the extent of the infection, and the resources at hand all influence the diagnostic approach that is selected. For respiratory tract infections to be appropriately managed and treated, a timely and accurate diagnosis is crucial.

- e) **Tuberculosis (TB):** Tuberculosis is a communicable infection that typically affects the lungs and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is the bacterium that causes TB. This infection can be transmitted through respiratory droplets or by air (Pöhlker et al., 2023). Although the TB bacteria typically affect the lungs, they can also affect the kidney, spine, and brain, among other parts of the body (Hammami et al., 2022). The common symptoms of TB include Persistent cough for more than three weeks, chest pain, unexplained and significant weight loss, fatigue, fever, and night Sweats (Sharma et al., 2023).

Some of the conventional methods for diagnosing TB include Tuberculin Skin Test (TST), Chest X-ray, Sputum Smear Microscopy, and Sputum Culture. TST or Mantoux Test measures the amount of induration (swelling) at the injection site 48–72 hours after administering an intradermal injection of purified protein derivative (PPD) to evaluate the delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction. Easy to use and extensively accessible, but it is

unable to distinguish between latent and active tuberculosis and is impacted by prior BCG vaccination.

A chest X-ray is a radiographic examination used to find cavities, lung lesions, or other indications of tuberculosis (Sajed et al., 2023). It helps detect pulmonary tuberculosis, but is unable to establish the existence of an active infection or distinguish TB from other lung conditions (Giannelli et al., 2022).

Sputum Smear Microscopy examines sputum under a microscope to detect *M. tuberculosis* in sputum samples using acid-fast bacilli (AFB) staining. It is easy to use and reasonably priced, but it cannot differentiate between different mycobacterial species, has a moderate sensitivity, and may miss low bacterial loads. Sputum Culture is used in the culturing of sputum samples to isolate and identify *M. tuberculosis*. It is extremely precise, and permits drug susceptibility testing, but necessitates specialized facilities and takes several weeks to produce results (Rimal et al., 2022).

Some advancements in diagnostic technologies for TB include Nucleic Acid Amplification Tests (NAATs), Xpert MTB/RIF Assay, Line Probe Assays (LPAs), Cytokine Release Assays (IGRAs), Biosensors and Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS).

NAATs amplify and detect *M. tuberculosis* DNA using molecular methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Although it needs specific tools and knowledge, it yields quick results when identifying drug-resistant strains (Wen et al., 2023). The Xpert MTB/RIF Assay targets rifampicin resistance and *M. tuberculosis* DNA using automated cartridge-based NAAT. In a matter of hours, it can simultaneously identify TB and resistance to rifampicin; however, its use is expensive and equipment-dependent (Horne et al., 2019).

LPAs employ genotypic assays, which identify particular genetic markers linked to drug-resistance mutations in *M. tuberculosis*. Although it provides quick drug resistance detection, it necessitates laboratory equipment and experience (Diriba et al., 2022).

IGRAs use blood tests to measure the release of interferon-gamma in response to *M. tuberculosis* antigens. Although it distinguishes between latent and active TB, it has drawbacks, including potential false-positive results in some populations and cost considerations (Banaei et al., 2016).

Biosensor devices are used to detect specific biomolecules associated with TB. This technique turns a biological response into an electrical signal that can be detected using a variety of transducers. Although biosensor technologies are still being developed and validated, they have the potential to detect things quickly and sensitively (Zhou et al., 2011).

WGS provides precise genetic data for strain typing and epidemiological research by employing a thorough sequencing of the whole genome of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Although it requires advanced sequencing technology and bioinformatics expertise, it has detailed genetic information with high resolution (Zhang et al., 2023).

Digital PCR partitions samples into individual reactions, allowing absolute quantification of nucleic acids for accurate detection of *M. tuberculosis*. It has a high sensitivity and accurate quantification, but it needs specific tools and knowledge (Yang et al., 2017).

The goal of improvements in tuberculosis diagnostic technologies is to increase efficiency, precision, and the capacity to identify drug resistance. The suspected clinical presentation, the existence of drug resistance, and the resources at hand all influence the diagnostic method selection. Efficient diagnosis is essential for successful tuberculosis management and control.

- f) **Urinary Tract Infection (UTI):** Urinary Tract Infections are common infections caused by bacteria that enter the urethra usually from the skin or the rectum and infect the urinary tract (Flores-Mireles et al., 2015). Although the infections can affect various parts of the urinary tract, bladder infections (cystitis) are the most common type and kidney infection (pyelonephritis) is another form of UTI. Some common symptoms include painful urination, the urge to urinate more often than usual (frequent urination), having an empty

bladder but still feeling the need to urinate(urgency), discomfort or pain in the lower abdomen, cloudy or bloody urine, and fever (CDC, 2021).

Some of the conventional methods for diagnosing UTI include urinalysis, urine culture, and gram staining. Urinalysis is the process of analyzing urine for physical, chemical, and microscopic features by looking for bacteria, red blood cells, white blood cells, and other abnormalities. The method is easy to use, economical, and gives preliminary information; however, it might not be able to differentiate between distinct pathogens. In urine culture, urine is cultured for the identification of specific bacteria. Although it takes time (24–48 hours for results) and may be tainted by outside factors (Karah et al., 2020), this method finds the causative organism and directs antibiotic therapy. Gram staining is a technique used to identify bacteria as Gram-positive or Gram-negative by staining their cells according to the properties of their cell walls. It can quickly identify bacteria in clinical specimens, but it is only effective in identifying specific types of bacteria and is not appropriate for all pathogens (Tripathi and Sapra, 2023).

Some advancements in diagnostic technologies for UTI include Molecular Testing (PCR), Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS), Flow Cytometry, Biosensors, Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) and Digital PCR. Polymerase chain reaction, or PCR, is a technique used in molecular testing to amplify and identify specific pathway DNA sequences. It needs specialized tools and knowledge, but it offers quick results, great accuracy, and pathogen detection for particular diseases.

MALDI-TOFMS determines microorganisms based on their mass spectra using bacterial isolates from culture. This technique is mostly employed in laboratory settings and is quick and accurate in identifying pathogens but needs specific equipment (Singhal et al., 2015).

Flow Cytometry quantitative analysis of cells in a fluid sample by measuring the size, granularity, and fluorescent properties of cells, including white blood

cells and bacteria. It provides a rapid and automated analysis but may require specialized equipment and expertise (McKinnon, 2018).

To detect specific biomolecules linked to urinary tract infections (UTIs), biosensor devices use a variety of transducers to transform a biological response into an electrical signal. Although the development and validation of biosensor technologies are still in progress, it has the potential to detect quickly and sensitively (Mehrotra, 2016).

High-throughput sequencing of genetic material is used by NGS to thoroughly identify pathogens. It uses DNA sequencing to simultaneously identify several pathogens. It offers thorough and objective pathogen detection and identification, but it is expensive and requires complex analysis (Martina et al., 2015).

Digital PCR allows for absolute quantification by dividing samples into separate reactions. It offers accurate nucleic acid quantification for highly sensitive pathogen detection, but it necessitates specialized tools and knowledge (Mao et al., 2019).

UTI diagnostic technology is always evolving to enhance speed, accuracy, and simultaneous detection of multiple pathogens. The pathogens that are suspected, the extent of the infection, and the resources available all play a role in the diagnostic method selection. Urinary tract infections must be managed and treated appropriately, which requires a prompt and accurate diagnosis.

2.2.2 Diagnostic Challenges in Tropical Febrile Diseases

Due to overlapping symptoms, a variety of clinical presentations, and restricted access to skilled medical professionals in low-to-middle-income areas, diagnosing tropical febrile diseases can be difficult. Some of the key diagnostic challenges include.

- a) **Diverse Clinical Presentations:** Numerous pathogens, such as bacteria, viruses, and parasites, are responsible for tropical febrile illnesses (Attai et al.,

2022). It can be difficult to determine the precise cause of a clinical presentation based only on symptoms because different pathogens can cause similar presentations. Different manifestations of the same pathogen may occur in different people or places, making it more difficult to establish precise diagnostic criteria because of this variability (Washington, 2011).

- b) **Overlapping Symptoms:** Fever, fatigue, headaches, and muscle pain are common symptoms of many tropical febrile illnesses. Based only on clinical presentation, it is challenging to differentiate between various diseases due to symptom overlap (Attai et al., 2022). In tropical regions, multiple pathogen coinfections are common and can complicate the diagnostic process even more, and a confluence of symptoms from various illnesses can be caused by coinfections (Middlebrook et al., 2022).
- c) **Limited Access to Expertise and Lack of Diagnostic Infrastructure:** There is a dearth of medical facilities, labs, and qualified medical personnel in many tropical regions and inadequate access to medical facilities makes it more difficult to diagnose febrile illnesses promptly and correctly (Ahmat et al., 2022; Makuku and Mosadeghrad, 2022). This challenge makes it difficult to identify and diagnose less common tropical diseases in some areas due to a lack of specialized training in tropical medicine among healthcare providers.
- d) **Seasonal Patterns and Outbreaks:** There are tropical febrile diseases that show seasonal patterns that make it difficult to differentiate between outbreaks and endemic cases (Fairhead et al., 2022). Clinical diagnosis accuracy may be impacted by seasonal variations. The unpredictability of new and re-emerging diseases makes it difficult for healthcare systems to adjust swiftly and create efficient diagnosis plans.
- e) **Vector-Borne Transmission:** Many tropical febrile illnesses, including those brought on by arboviruses, are spread by vectors such as biting midges, sandflies, ticks, and mosquitoes. (Artsob et al., 2023). Diagnosis is further complicated by the intricate interactions that exist between hosts, vectors, and pathogens.
- f) **Population Movements:** Tropical febrile diseases are spreading to new regions as a result of increased international travel and population movements

(Baker et al., 2022; Findlater and Bogoch, 2018). This may make it more difficult to identify and diagnose illnesses that were previously rare in some areas.

In an attempt to tackle these challenges, efforts should be made to fortify the healthcare infrastructure in tropical areas, improve diagnostic technologies, and improve professional training. Enhancing the diagnosis and treatment of tropical febrile diseases requires research and development of quick and precise diagnostic instruments as well as greater awareness and surveillance. To develop capacity and successfully address these intricate challenges, cooperation between governments, research institutions, and international health organizations is also essential.

2.2.3 Importance of Accuracy in Diagnosis

This section emphasized the critical role that timely and accurate diagnosis of tropical febrile diseases plays in improving patient outcomes and public health.

2.2.3.1. Patient Outcomes

- a) Initiation of Appropriate Treatment:** If left untreated, several tropical febrile illnesses, including malaria, dengue fever, and typhoid fever, can spread quickly and cause serious complications (Lu et al., 2017).
- b) Reduction of Morbidity and Mortality:** Morbidity and mortality rates can be considerably decreased by early detection and treatment (Yang et al., 2022). For instance, early antimalarial medication administration in malaria cases or supportive care for severe dengue cases can avert complications and enhance patient outcomes.
- c) Prevention of Disease Spread:** Prompt diagnosis is essential to stopping the spread of infectious illnesses. To control outbreaks and safeguard the larger community, patients suffering from infectious tropical febrile diseases, such as some viral hemorrhagic fevers, should be identified and isolated (Yang et al., 2022).
- d) Prevention of Complications:** Timely intervention to prevent complications is made possible by early detection. (Yang et al., 2022) With timely and

effective treatment, complications of tropical febrile diseases can be reduced. Examples of these include respiratory distress in certain respiratory tract infections and organ failure in severe cases of leptospirosis.

- e) **Avoidance of Unnecessary Treatments:** Accurate diagnosis aids in avoiding pointless medical interventions (Marwaha et al., 2022). A precise diagnosis guarantees that patients receive the precise treatment needed for their condition, lowering the risk of side effects from needless medications. Certain tropical febrile diseases have similar symptoms.

2.2.3.2 Public Health Impact

- a) **Disease Surveillance and Control:** For disease surveillance and control to be effective, accurate diagnosis is necessary (Marwaha et al., 2022). It makes it easier to implement focused control measures by enabling public health authorities to keep an eye on the prevalence, distribution, and trends of tropical febrile diseases.
- b) **Outbreak Response:** Accurate and timely diagnosis is essential for controlling outbreaks. Public health officials can control the spread of the disease by implementing containment measures, tracing contacts, and allocating resources when the disease is detected early (Hossain et al., 2022).
- c) **Resource Allocation:** Resource allocation strategies are informed by accurate diagnosis. To maximize the effectiveness of interventions, public health programs can distribute resources such as staff, medications, and vaccines, based on the particular diseases that are common in a given area.
- d) **Public Health Education:** Prompt diagnosis aids in public health education initiatives. Understanding the particular pathogens responsible for febrile illnesses allows for more focused education campaigns, enabling communities to take preventive action and seek medical attention as soon as possible (Wang et al., 2023).
- e) **Preventing Antimicrobial Resistance:** A precise diagnosis helps ensure that antibiotics are used responsibly (Bassetti et al., 2022). The overuse of antibiotics, which is frequently observed in undifferentiated fever cases, can lead to the development of antibiotic resistance (Akram et al., 2023). Correct

diagnosis aids in treatment customization and lowers the possibility of overusing antibiotics.

- f) International Collaboration:** Reliable diagnosis promotes cross-border cooperation. To coordinate responses to transboundary tropical febrile diseases, countries, and international organizations can benefit from sharing accurate diagnostic data, which enhances global health security.

Prompt and precise diagnosis of tropical febrile illnesses is essential for both the treatment of individual patients and the general public's health. It lowers the burden of disease, facilitates timely and appropriate treatment, and supports successful public health initiatives. To improve overall health outcomes and stop the spread of infectious diseases, healthcare systems must prioritize the development of accurate diagnostic capabilities.

2.2.4 Machine Learning and Explainable AI in Medical Diagnosis

Machine Learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that deals with creating models and algorithms that let computers recognize patterns in data and predict or decide without the need for explicit programming. The common types of machine learning algorithms are supervised learning, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning algorithms (Bloch, 2023).

- a) Supervised Learning:** Supervised learning algorithms are trained on labelled datasets, which can map input data to the appropriate output. In supervised learning, a model is trained using a labelled dataset that contains both the input data and the appropriate output. Learning an input-to-output mapping that can be applied to forecast the labels of fresh, unobserved data is the aim. In medical applications, supervised learning is essential, especially for prognostication and diagnosis (Kasula, 2024). This method, which has been applied extensively in medical image analysis, requires sizable labelled datasets for training. Deep learning models, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have demonstrated exceptional performance in tasks like medical image classification, detection, and segmentation (Aljuaid & Anwar, 2022). In medical image processing, methods like data augmentation,

dropout, and transfer learning have been used to get around the problem of limited labeled data (Ming & Yuan, 2022). Several medical domains have seen the successful application of supervised learning models, such as the classification of kidney biopsy images of patients with diabetic nephropathy and the prediction of acute kidney injury (AKI) from electronic health records (EHRs). By offering precise and effective solutions for challenging medical tasks, the integration of supervised learning algorithms, particularly deep learning, continues to improve clinical practice and medical research.

- b) Unsupervised learning:** Unsupervised learning algorithms are used to find hidden structures in data through clustering and pattern recognition without labeled data. Unsupervised learning works with data that is not labeled. Without explicit instructions on what to predict, the objective is to identify intrinsic structures or hidden patterns in the input data. In many medical applications, unsupervised learning is essential, especially for pathology detection and medical image reconstruction. It has the benefit of not requiring labeled data, which makes it useful for assignments where getting annotations is difficult (Lukauskas & Ruzgas, 2023). Unsupervised learning techniques, such as clustering algorithms, have been successfully used in the medical field to identify various diseases, demonstrating their adaptability and efficiency in analyzing large, complex datasets. Furthermore, deep unsupervised approaches have demonstrated potential in medical image segmentation and pathology detection, providing a more effective and general-purpose substitute for supervised methods, particularly in the detection of uncommon pathologies. These developments demonstrate the enormous potential of unsupervised learning to transform patient care and medical diagnostics via creative, data-driven methods.
- c) Reinforcement learning:** Reinforcement learning involves using trial-and-error training to teach models, with feedback given based on actions taken. Reinforcement learning teaches an agent how to make a series of decisions by using rewards for desired behaviors and penalties for undesirable ones (Whig et al., 2024). Through interaction with its surroundings, the agent gains knowledge about how to accomplish a task. Medical decision-making relies

heavily on reinforcement learning (RL), which creates treatment plans using patient data from electronic health records (EHR) (Smith et al., 2023). To optimize long-term rewards, reinforcement learning, a subset of machine learning, enables sequential interactions between an agent and its surroundings (Zhang, 2023). Artificial diagnosis, precision medicine, treatment recommendations, and drug dosage optimization in conditions like acute kidney injury (AKI) or chronic kidney disease (CKD) complications are just a few of the tasks that machine learning has been used for in the medical field (Khezeli et al., 2023; Nambiar et al., 2023). Nevertheless, there are difficulties in applying RL to practical medical applications, particularly when it comes to managing retrospective datasets that are biased and guaranteeing patient safety (Adiga et al., 2023). Notwithstanding these difficulties, reinforcement learning (RL) holds great promise for the healthcare industry. It can automate treatment choices, improve patient care, and improve clinical outcomes by creating dependable simulation environments and incorporating clinical insights.

Explainable AI (XAI) refers to a collection of approaches and strategies in machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) that seek to explain, reveal, and allow humans to engage with the decision-making processes of AI systems. Its main goal is to create AI systems that can clearly explain their choices and forecasts so that users can comprehend how the model arrived at a given result (Saeed & Omlin, 2023). The three important concepts in XAI are feature importance, local explanations, and model-agnostic techniques. Feature importance describes how much of an influence or contribution each input feature has on the predictions made by the model. The goal of local explanations is to provide context for a machine learning model's prediction for a particular instance or data point. It explains each prediction in detail so that users can comprehend the reasoning behind a particular choice. Model-agnostic techniques are methods that, regardless of the underlying algorithm, can be used to explain the predictions of different machine learning models (Parisineni & Pal, 2023). These methods are adaptable to different kinds of models and encourage interpretability and flexibility. Model-agnostic approaches

improve flexibility by releasing users from the constraints of a specific algorithm, enabling them to apply explanation techniques to a variety of model types. These XAI concepts collectively help machine learning models become more transparent and trustworthy by addressing issues with accountability and interpretability, particularly in critical applications. The popularly used XAI techniques are delineated below

- a) **Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME):** LIME is a framework created to offer understandable justifications for machine learning models' predictions, especially when it comes to specific cases. LIME produces locally accurate explanations for particular cases by varying the input data and tracking how the model's predictions alter. LIME is a community-recognized algorithm that can be used to explain the predictions of any black-box classifier and black-box regressors trained on tabular data (Vinogradova & Myers, 2023).
- b) **SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP):** SHAP is a framework for analysing machine learning model output, and it helps to comprehend how each feature affects the model's predictions (Al-Najjar et al., 2023) by giving the means to link a model's prediction to each of its features. SHAP values assign contributions to each feature for a given prediction based on cooperative game theory and offer a fair means of allocating "credit" for the model's output (Palar et al., 2023).

2.2.5 Large Language Models in Healthcare

Healthcare is one of the many industries where large language models (LLMs) like Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3 (GPT-3) have shown great promise (Peng et al., 2023; Bumgardner et al., 2023). There is both excitement and concern regarding the use of LLMs in healthcare settings because they can answer free-text queries without having received specialized training for the task (Thirunavukarasu et al., 2023). Recent advancements in AI and Deep Learning (DL) have led to the creation of LLMs, which use transformer-based architectures to provide cutting-edge results on a range of language tasks (Chacko & Chacko, 2023). Large volumes of medical text data can be processed and analyzed by these models, which have been trained

on enormous datasets and have natural language understanding capabilities. Some common types of large language models are:

- a) Language Representation Model:** Language representation models (LRM) are the foundation of many NLP applications; they are made to comprehend and produce human language. These models include RoBERTa, BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), and GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) models (Fajcik et al., 2020). These models can be optimized for particular tasks like text classification and language generation because they have already been pre-trained on large text corpora.
- b) Zero-Shot Model:** A zero-shot model can perform tasks without specific training data; it can generate text for tasks it has never seen before or generalize and make predictions (Meng et al., 2022). GPT-3 is an example of a zero-shot model; it can translate languages, answer questions, and perform a variety of tasks with little to no fine-tuning.
- c) Multimodal Model:** Although multimodal models, like OpenAI's CLIP, can understand and generate content across different modalities, LLMs were originally designed for text content (Carolan et al., 2024). On the other hand, multimodal models, like CLIP, can work with both text and image data. Their ability to associate text with images and vice versa makes them useful for tasks like image captioning and text-based image retrieval.
- d) Fine-Tuned Or Domain-Specific Models:** Even though pre-trained language representation models are flexible, certain tasks or domains may not always yield the best results from them. To boost performance in specific domains, fine-tuned models have undergone additional training on domain-specific data (Bai et al., 2020). For instance, a GPT-3 model could be improved using medical data to develop a medical chatbot tailored to the industry or help with diagnosis.

Some examples of predominant large language models are summarized below.

- a) Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT):** BERT is a pre-trained transformer-based model that can be used in natural language understanding tasks (Devlin et al., 2018). BERT is a deep

bidirectional transformer architecture that allows for the multilingual universal language representation of different languages, and contextual embeddings are obtained using pre-trained unlabelled Wikipedia and book corpus (Deepa, 2021). BERT is an advanced and more realistic technique because it recognizes that a document can belong to multiple classes at the same time and has demonstrated exceptional performance in eleven natural language understanding (NLU) tasks (Alaparthi & Mishra, 2020).

- b) Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) Series:** Models like GPT-2 and GPT-3 are part of OpenAI's GPT series. The purpose of these models is to generate natural language. Pre-training and fine-tuning are the two steps in the training process for GPT models. GPT models are trained on enormous volumes of text gathered from various sources, and these models are fine-tuned on smaller, task-specific datasets after pre-training to conform to particular domains. Fine-tuning preserves the general language understanding acquired during pre-training while enabling the model to specialize in the desired task and enhance its performance on domain-specific data (Kamnis, 2023). GPT-4 is a more sophisticated version of GPT-3 and GPT-3.5, its predecessors. It performs better than the earlier models in terms of creativity, context, and visual comprehension. Users can work together on screenplays, music, technical writing, and other projects with this LLM. In addition to text, images can be entered into GPT-4. Furthermore, GPT-4 is a multilingual model that can respond to thousands of queries in 26 languages, according to OpenAI (Akshay, 2024).
- c) Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer (T5):** Google's T5 is a flexible LLM that was trained with a text-to-text framework (Gupta, 2024). Thanks to its ability to convert input and output formats into a text-to-text format, it can handle various language tasks. In the areas of machine translation, text summarization, text classification, and document generation, T5 has produced cutting-edge outcomes. It is incredibly versatile and effective for a wide range of language-related applications because of its capacity to manage various tasks within a single framework (Akshay, 2024).

- d) eXtreme Language Understanding (XLNet):** Researchers from Google and Carnegie Mellon University created XLNet to address some of the drawbacks of autoregressive models like GPT-3. It makes use of a permutation-based training strategy, which enables the model to take into account every possible word order in pre-training. This makes it possible for XLNet to detect bidirectional dependencies during inference without the need for autoregressive generation (Khan et al., 2020). Impressive results have been shown by XLNet in tasks like sentiment analysis, question and answer, and natural language inference.
- e) Turing-NLG:** Microsoft's Turing-NLG is a potent LLM that specializes in producing conversational responses and to enhance its conversational skills, a vast dataset of exchanges has been utilized for training (Sahoo et al., 2024). Turing-NLG performs well in chatbot applications, offering conversational settings with interactive and contextually relevant responses.
- f) Pathways Language Model (PaLM):** Google AI created a sizable language model called PaLM. The LLM is becoming one of the most potent AI language models since it can train on Google's enormous dataset (Chowdhery et al., 2023). It is a significant advancement in responsible AI and machine learning. Even though PaLM is still in development, it already can comprehend language, answer questions in natural language, and perform machine translation, code generation, summarization, and other creative tasks. PaLM was created with data security and privacy in mind as well. Data can be encrypted and shielded from unwanted access with its help. Because of this, it's perfect for delicate projects like developing safe eCommerce websites and platforms that handle sensitive user data.
- g) Large Language Model Meta AI(LLaMA):** LLaMA is a brand-new, open-source large language model that is presently being worked on by Meta AI. It is intended to be a strong and adaptable LLM that can be applied to a range of tasks, such as reading comprehension, natural language understanding, and query resolution. LLaMA is the outcome of Meta's specific concentration on language learning models for use in teaching (Thirunavukarasu et al., 2023).

- h) CoHere:** CoHere is a large language model created by the same-named Canadian startup. The open-source LLM is proficient in handling a wide range of languages and accents because it was trained on a varied and inclusive dataset (Chen et al., 2023). Furthermore, Cohere's models are better suited for a variety of tasks because they were trained on a sizable and varied corpus of text.
- i) Gemini:** Google AI developed Gemini, an LLM chatbot that was formerly known as BARD. It is trained using a sizable text and code dataset. This enables it to create text, translate between several languages, write code, produce a variety of content, and respond to inquiries with insightful information (Metz & Grant, 2023). Google Search provides access to real-world data for Gemini, one of the top multimodal large language models. This enables it to interpret and respond to a wider range of cues and questions.
- j) Falcon:** The Technology Innovation Institute developed the open-source language model Falcon. It is now the best language model, surpassing Llama on the Hugging Face Open LLM Leaderboard. Trained on a higher-quality dataset that encompasses a vast array of text and code in various languages and dialects, Falcon is an autoregressive model (Kukreja et al., 2024). Additionally, it makes better predictions and processes data more effectively thanks to a more sophisticated architecture. Compared to the best NLP models, this new pre-trained model has learned with 40 billion fewer parameters.
- k) Claude v1:** A sizable language model called Claude v1 was created by the US AI startup Anthropic. It is a flexible AI assistant made especially to make managing, creating, and optimizing websites easier. Claude v1's sophisticated natural language capabilities make it simple for anyone to create, manage, and expand a website without the need for complex technical knowledge. Compared to other LLMs, Claude has a more sophisticated architecture that enables it to process data more quickly and produce more accurate predictions (Turpin et al., 2024).
- l) Grok:** The generative artificial intelligence chatbot Grok was created by xAI. Elon Musk created it as an initiative based on a large language model (LLM)

in direct response to ChatGPT's explosive growth, the development of which Musk co-founded with OpenAI (Ding et al., 2024). The chatbot is marketed as having direct access to Twitter (X) and "having a sense of humor". X Premium is required to access it, and beta testing is underway (OptimizeIAS, 2024).

m) Med-PaLM: Med-PaLM is intended to deliver superior responses to medical queries. MedLM, a family of foundation models optimized for the healthcare sector, is powered by research models, including our second version, Med-PaLM 2. MedLM is now accessible to Google Cloud users experimenting with various applications, ranging from simple jobs to intricate workflows. Med-PaLM leverages the power of Google's extensive language models, which have been assessed using consumer queries, medical research, and examinations in the medical field. The first version of Med-PaLM was preprinted in late 2022, and it was published in Nature in July 2023. This made it the first AI system to pass the U.S. Medical Licensing Examination (USMLE) style questions with a passing score of greater than 60%. According to panels of doctors and users, Med-PaLM also produces precise, beneficial long-form responses to consumer health queries. In March 2023, at Google Health's annual event, The Check Up, Med-PaLM 2 was unveiled. The first to answer questions similar to those on the USMLE at the level of a human expert was Med-PaLM 2. Doctors report significant improvements in the model's long-form responses to consumer medical queries. (Singhal et al., 2023)

LLMs are effective tools in a variety of domains, such as healthcare, education, customer service etc and some of its advantages are summarized below (Abdullahi, 2024).

a) Increased Efficiency: Due to their capacity for comprehending human language, LLMs are well-suited for handling tedious or repetitive tasks. LLMs are useful for tasks like content creation, writing code, and summarizing vast amounts of information because they can produce human-like text much faster than humans.

- b) Enhanced Question-Answering Capabilities:** An answer-generation machine is another way to characterize LLMs. Experts had to intervene to persuade users that generative AIs would not supplant Google as a search engine because LLMs are so adept at producing precise answers to user inquiries.
- c) Few-Shot or Zero-Shot Learning:** With minimal training examples or no training at all, LLMs are capable of performing tasks and generalizing from available data to infer patterns and predict in novel domains.
- d) Transfer Learning:** Professionals in a variety of industries benefit from LLMs because they can be customized for different tasks, allowing a model to be trained for one task and then used for another with little further training.

Large Language Models also present challenges, some of which are summarized below (Abdullahi, 2024). These challenges show how using LLMs requires careful thought and mitigating measures.

- a) Performance depends on training data:** The quality and representativeness of the training data are critical to the effectiveness and precision of LLMs. Since LLMs are only as good as the training data they use, models that are trained on skewed or poor-quality data will undoubtedly yield debatable results. This is a serious potential issue since it can have a negative impact, particularly in delicate fields like law, medicine, or finance where accuracy is crucial.
- b) Lack of common-sense reasoning:** Large language models are remarkably good at language, but they frequently have trouble with common-sense logic. Humans possess common sense by nature; it's one of our innate instincts. However, common sense is not common among LLMs, as they can generate responses that lack context or are factually incorrect, producing outputs that are misleading or nonsensical.
- c) Ethical concerns:** Concerns about potential abuse or malevolent applications arise when using LLMs. The possibility of producing offensive or dangerous content, deepfakes, or impersonations that could be utilized for manipulation or fraud exists.

2.2.6 Integration of XAI and LLMs in Medical Diagnosis

There are various ways in which the combination of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) and Large Language Models (LLMs) could improve the diagnostic precision of diseases. There are also numerous benefits to integrating AI and LLMs into clinical pharmacology, but there are also important safety and ethical issues to be aware of (Rubinic et al., 2023). Here are some advantages of this integration:

- a) **Improved Clinical Decision Support:** XAI methods can offer clear-cut and understandable insights into how LLMs make decisions. It is simpler for clinicians to trust and depend on the AI system for decision support when they can comprehend how the model arrived at a specific diagnosis (Antoniadi et al., 2021).
- b) **Enhanced Feature Interpretability:** XAI techniques can draw attention to the significance of particular traits or terms during the diagnosis process (Pawar et al., 2020). Clinicians can focus on important aspects during patient evaluation for diseases by knowing which clinical symptoms or historical data were important to the model.
- c) **Contextual Understanding:** Contextual explanations are given by XAI for the model's predictions (Pawar et al., 2020). XAI can help explain why the model leaned towards a specific diagnosis in the context of tropical febrile diseases, where symptoms may overlap, taking into account the larger clinical context.
- d) **Reduced Diagnostic Ambiguity:** Model prediction uncertainty can be estimated with the aid of XAI techniques (Thuy & Benoit, 2023). Clinicians can be informed when the model is unsure or presents with unclear symptoms. This information may lead to additional diagnostic testing or the search for more information.
- e) **Facilitating Clinician-Model Collaboration:** Healthcare professionals will be able to easily understand the explanations generated by XAI (Gentile et al., 2021). This makes it easier for doctors and the AI model to collaborate, which

improves the effectiveness of incorporating AI-driven insights into diagnosis procedures.

- f) Error Analysis and Model Improvement:** XAI can assist in localizing errors by pinpointing particular situations in which the model might have interpreted data incorrectly (Widyasari et al., 2022). For ongoing model improvement and refinement, this feedback is helpful.
- g) Transparent Treatment Recommendations:** The reasoning behind the model's suggested treatments can be explained by XAI (Pawar et al., 2020). In the case of tropical febrile diseases, this transparency can help physicians comprehend and have confidence in AI-generated treatment plans.
- h) Education and Training:** Healthcare workers may find XAI to be a useful teaching tool (Fiok et al., 2022). It can aid in educating medical professionals about the subtleties of tropical febrile illnesses and enhance their comprehension of the diagnostic reasoning behind the model.
- i) Compliance with Ethical Standards:** Ethical issues about accountability and transparency in AI systems are addressed by the integration of XAI (Arrieta et al., 2020). Clear models support responsible AI applications in healthcare and are consistent with moral principles.
- j) Patient-Clinician Communication:** Better communication between patients and clinicians can be fostered by sharing explanations generated by XAI with patients (Lötsch et al., 2021). When patients understand the rationale behind their diagnosis, their confidence in the medical system grows.

There is great potential to improve decision-making processes' interpretability and transparency by integrating XAI and LLMs in medical diagnosis (Zhou et al., 2023). Healthcare professionals can gain valuable insights into the model's decision-making process by combining LLMs' understanding and processing capabilities with XAI techniques. This approach can help improve the trust and acceptance of AI-driven recommendations by providing valuable explanations for diagnostic outcomes (Han et al., 2023). Furthermore, the creation of domain-specific LLMs specifically designed for medical applications, like GatorTron for clinical text processing (Gao et al., 2023), demonstrates the potential of specialized models to improve the

precision and effectiveness of diagnosis. The responsible and effective integration of XAI and LLMs in medical diagnosis will, however, require addressing issues like algorithmic bias, privacy concerns, and the requirement for on-premises model deployment (Abd-Alrazaq et al., 2023) to pave the way for revolutionary improvements in patient outcomes and healthcare delivery. Integrating XAI with LLMs can improve diagnosis accuracy for tropical febrile diseases by offering clear, intelligible, and pertinent contextual information during decision-making. This promotes trust, cooperation, and ongoing improvement in the use of AI in healthcare settings in addition to helping clinicians make well-informed decisions.

2.2.7 Interpretability and Transparency in AI Models and Medical Diagnosis

Medical diagnosis especially in the differential diagnoses of tropical diseases can benefit heavily from the interpretability and transparency of AI models. Comprehending the decision-making process of AI-integrated healthcare systems is imperative for regulatory agencies, patients, and clinicians. The following features underscore the significance of interpretability and transparency in the field of medical diagnosis:

- a) **Clinical Trust and Adoption:** If clinicians can comprehend how the model makes its recommendations, they are more likely to trust and use AI-assisted diagnostic tools (Antoniadi et al., 2021). Transparent models promote greater collaboration between AI systems and healthcare professionals by boosting clinician confidence in the technology.
- b) **Patient Understanding and Informed Consent:** Improved communication between patients and healthcare providers is made possible by transparent AI models (Lötsch et al., 2021). When patients are aware of the assumptions behind AI-generated diagnoses and recommendations, they can make better decisions about their healthcare.
- c) **Ethical Considerations:** Transparency and accountability in the application of AI models are mandated by numerous healthcare regulatory bodies (Arrieta et al., 2020). Clear models comply with legal and ethical requirements, guaranteeing that AI applications for medical diagnosis are compliant.

- d) **Error Detection and Diagnosis Improvement:** Transparent models make it easier to spot flaws or restrictions in the AI system (Widyasari et al., 2022). This information can be used by developers and clinicians to increase the accuracy and dependability of the model. Transparent models provide feedback that can be used to continuously improve the model and improve its performance over time.
- e) **Explainable Treatment Plans:** The reasoning behind treatment recommendations can be elucidated by transparent AI models (Pawar et al., 2020). By having a deeper understanding of the rationale behind a particular treatment plan, clinicians are better equipped to make educated decisions regarding patient care.
- f) **Educational Tool for Healthcare Professionals:** Healthcare workers can better grasp the fundamental ideas of AI in diagnosis by using transparent AI models as educational resources (Fiok et al., 2022). To successfully integrate into clinical workflows, this knowledge is essential.
- g) **Model Comparison and Validation:** Clinicians can compare the efficacy and decision-making mechanisms of various AI models thanks to transparency (Pawar et al., 2020). This makes it possible to choose models that best suit the requirements and preferences of the clinical setting. Transparent models make validation procedures easier and allow for impartial evaluations of the accuracy and dependability of the model.
- h) **Patient Safety:** Recognizing the process by which AI models arrive at diagnoses aids in preventing unforeseen outcomes that might jeopardize patient safety (Lee et al., 2023). The identification and reduction of risks related to artificial intelligence in healthcare are facilitated by transparent models.
- i) **Legal and Liability Considerations:** In the event of unfavorable outcomes or disagreements about diagnoses produced by AI, transparent models may help ensure legal accountability (Arrieta et al., 2020). Assigning responsibility when required is made easier with an understanding of the decision-making process.

Fostering collaborative decision-making among clinicians, patients, and regulatory agencies as well as ensuring ethical deployment all depend on the interpretability and transparency of AI models in medical diagnosis. These guidelines support the ethical and successful application of AI in healthcare environments.

2.2.8 Ethical Considerations in AI-based Diagnosis

To ensure responsible and equitable deployment, some ethical concerns raised by using AI in medical diagnosis must be carefully considered. Important ethical factors to think about are patient privacy, accountability, and bias:

- a) **Bias in Data and AI Algorithms:** Healthcare disparities may persist as a result of AI models that were trained on biased datasets. Especially for underrepresented or minority populations, biases in training data can result in predictions that are unfair or inaccurate (Mehrabi et al., 2021). Incorporating prejudices and discriminating against specific demographic groups are possible with the algorithms themselves and diagnosis and treatment recommendations may differ as a consequence.
- b) **Accountability and Transparency:** Many AI models are regarded as "black boxes" with opaque decision-making processes, particularly sophisticated deep learning models. In addition to making it more difficult to identify and correct biases or mistakes in the system, a lack of transparency can impede accountability. Determining accountability for decisions and results produced by AI presents difficulties (Arrieta et al., 2020). Whether the developer, the healthcare provider, or the AI system itself bears responsibility may not always be evident.
- c) **Patient Privacy:** Data security issues are brought up by the use of private patient information to train AI models. To stop unwanted access to or misuse of patient data, strong patient privacy protection measures are crucial (Guarda, 2019). Therefore, patients need to be fully informed about how AI applications will use their data. It becomes imperative to obtain informed consent, and patients ought to be able to decide how their data is shared and used.

- d) **Inequality and Access to Healthcare:** Using AI to diagnose patients could make already-existing healthcare disparities worse. The quality of healthcare could be negatively impacted by a wider technological divide caused by restricted access to cutting-edge technologies and AI tools in some communities or regions (Perez, 2023).
- e) **Explainability and Trust:** Patients and healthcare professionals may become less trusting if AI-generated decisions are not transparent (Antoniadi et al., 2021). Gaining confidence in AI technology requires an understanding of how it makes diagnoses. Sustaining confidence in the healthcare system requires striking a balance between automation and human oversight. Physicians need to be able to dispute or override recommendations made by AI when needed.
- f) **Legal and Regulatory Compliance:** It is crucial to create legal frameworks for the ethical application of AI in healthcare. Determining who is responsible for mistakes, unfavourable outcomes, or privacy violations is essential for accountability. Ensuring that AI applications in medical diagnosis adhere to ethical norms, patient rights, and privacy regulations requires efficient regulatory oversight (Arrieta et al., 2020).
- g) **Data Quality and Representativeness:** To avoid erroneous or biased model predictions, it is essential to guarantee the representativeness and quality of training data. Subpar results might result from incomplete or skewed datasets, especially when it comes to diverse patient populations (Mehrabi et al., 2021).
- h) **Continued Monitoring and Evaluation:** To evaluate the influence of AI systems on patient outcomes, detect biases, and guarantee continuous adherence to ethical norms, ethical audits, and monitoring should be carried out regularly (Mehrabi et al., 2021). Technology breakthroughs, shifting ethical standards, and adjustments to healthcare procedures should all be taken into account when designing AI systems.

Healthcare professionals, data scientists, ethicists, legislators, and patients must work together to address these ethical issues through a multidisciplinary approach. For AI technologies to be responsibly integrated into healthcare

systems, their use in medical diagnosis must adhere to the values of justice, accountability, transparency, and patient privacy.

2.2.9 User Acceptance and Trust in AI Diagnosis

Many factors affect patients' and healthcare providers' acceptance of AI-assisted diagnosis, among other stakeholders. The effective application and integration of AI technologies in healthcare depends on an understanding of these elements. Key elements affecting user acceptability are as follows:

2.2.9.1 Healthcare Professionals Acceptance

- a) **Accuracy and Reliability:** Healthcare practitioners give priority to AI systems that exhibit high diagnostic accuracy and dependability (Hua et al., 2023). The foundation of technological trust is its capacity to deliver accurate and reliable outcomes.
- b) **Clinical Validity and Evidence-Based Practice:** When AI systems are in line with evidence-based medical procedures, acceptance is higher (Lambert et al., 2023). Professionals in the medical field are more likely to accept AI recommendations that have been verified by thorough clinical trials.
- c) **User-Friendly Interface:** Acceptance is greatly influenced by how easy it is to use the AI system, both in terms of its interface and integration with clinical workflows (Kelly et al., 2023). Easy-to-use systems that blend in with current procedures have a higher chance of being adopted.
- d) **Explainability and Transparency:** Healthcare workers expect answers and openness regarding decisions made by AI. Trust is increased by systems that offer lucid insights into the decision-making process, along with justifications for diagnosis and suggested courses of action (Hassija et al., 2023).
- e) **Integration with Clinical Workflow:** The degree to which AI is incorporated into routine clinical procedures is critical (Alowais et al., 2023). Solutions that improve efficiency without interfering with current operations and fit in seamlessly are more likely to be adopted.
- f) **Education and Training:** It is crucial to receive sufficient instruction and training on the proper use of AI tools. The ability to understand and act upon

AI-generated information must be a source of confidence for healthcare professionals (Kelly et al., 2023).

- g) **Human Oversight and Decision-Making Control:** The capacity of medical personnel to exercise human oversight and retain control over clinical judgments boosts acceptance. Instead of taking the place of human expertise, AI is viewed as a supplementary tool (Lorenzini et al., 2023).

2.2.9.2 Patients Acceptance

- a) **Transparency and Trust:** In terms of using AI for diagnosis, patients appreciate transparency (Lötsch et al., 2021). It's critical to understand how artificial intelligence fits into their healthcare journey and to have faith that the technology is applied safely and morally.
- b) **Communication and Education:** Building trust and easing concerns are achieved through efficient communication and education regarding the use of AI in diagnosis (Kelly et al., 2023). When patients are aware of how AI enhances the knowledge of medical professionals, they are more likely to accept it.
- c) **Privacy and Data Security:** Patient acceptance is impacted by worries about the security and privacy of personal health information. Strong data security protocols and transparent information about privacy protections are essential (Guarda, 2019).
- d) **Informed Consent:** Patients value having the option to give informed consent and being made aware of how AI is being used in their treatment. Patients must understand the use of their data and how it might affect their choice of treatment (Guarda, 2019).
- e) **Accuracy and Positive Outcomes:** Evidence that AI systems can improve treatment outcomes and diagnose patients accurately has a positive impact on patient acceptance (Hua et al., 2023). Trust is increased when benefits in terms of effectiveness and efficiency are demonstrated.

2.2.9.3 Other Stakeholders Acceptance

The extent to which AI systems abide by current healthcare regulations affects stakeholders like legislators and regulators. Solutions that comply with legal and ethical requirements are more likely to be accepted.

- a) **Economic Viability:** Payers and healthcare organizations evaluate whether using AI-assisted diagnosis is economically feasible. Acceptance rates are higher for solutions that provide cost-effectiveness, efficiency gains, sustainability, and better resource utilization (Al-Emran & Griffy-Brown, 2023).
- b) **Interoperability:** Integrating AI systems with other health IT systems and the current healthcare infrastructure is essential (Carobene et al., 2023). The stakeholders in healthcare ecosystem management are more accepting when there is interoperability.
- c) **Evidence of Impact:** Stakeholders seek proof of how AI affects patient outcomes, healthcare expenses, and system performance as a whole. Acceptance is influenced by lucid examples of successful outcomes (Kelly et al., 2023).
- d) **Ethical Considerations:** The ethical aspects of AI use, such as accountability, transparency, and fairness, are crucial (Arrieta et al., 2020). Various stakeholders are more likely to support solutions that address these ethical issues.
- e) **Public Perception:** The acceptance of these technologies in healthcare is influenced by public perception and societal attitudes toward artificial intelligence (Kelly et al., 2023). Decisions and policies made by stakeholders can be influenced by a positive public image.

A complex interplay of factors about accuracy, transparency, usability, ethics, and societal attitudes determines user acceptance of AI-assisted diagnosis in the healthcare industry. For AI technologies used in medical diagnosis to be successfully integrated and widely accepted, a thorough understanding of these factors is necessary

2.2.10 Human-Machine Collaboration in Diagnosis

AI systems and medical professionals working together to make decisions have the potential to completely transform healthcare delivery, enhance patient outcomes, and boost overall medical process efficiency. Table 2.1 presents some salient aspects that underscore the possibility of cooperation.

Table 2.1. Potential for collaborative decision-making

Aspects	AI	Human
Complementary Expertise (Zhang et al., 2022)	Rapid analysis of large datasets, pattern recognition, and evidence-based decision support.	A comprehension of the patient's background, clinical experience, intuition, and empathy.
Improved Diagnostic Accuracy (Reverberi et al., 2022)	Healthcare professionals can gain insights from AI systems' analysis of patient data, which includes test results, imaging scans, and medical records.	Healthcare professionals make diagnostic decisions by considering patient history, AI-generated insights, and their clinical expertise.
Efficient Workflow Integration (Gu et al., 2023)	Facilitating the automation of repetitive tasks, freeing up healthcare professionals to concentrate on more intricate facets of patient care.	Supplying a human touch in patient interactions and making sure AI recommendations are in line with the overall patient care strategy.
Personalized Treatment Plans (Ali, 2023).	Identifying individualized treatment options through data analysis of large datasets, taking into account patient traits, genetics, and response to previous interventions.	Treating patients with a focus on their total well-being by considering their preferences, values, and unique situations when designing treatment regimens.
Enhanced Predictive Analytics (Lee et al., 2023)	Using patient data from the past to forecast the course of a disease, spot possible complications, and issue early alerts.	Verifying AI forecasts against the patient's present state, modifying treatment regimens, and making certain that human interaction is preserved with patients.
Patient-Centric Decision-Making (Cabitza et al., 2023)	Making recommendations based on evidence that puts patient outcomes and safety first.	Making decisions that keep the patient at the centre of care.
Continuous Learning and Adaptation (Zhao et al., 2022).	Accurate diagnosis can be improved by learning from real-world data and adjusting to advances in medical knowledge.	Ensuring that the AI system remains in line with current best practices.
Decision Support and Clinical Guidelines (Chen et al., 2022)	Providing quick access to the recent clinical recommendations,	Contextualizing AI recommendations by using

	evidence-based treatments, and pertinent medical literature.	clinical judgment and the particulars of each patient's case.
Improved Resource Allocation (Jain et al., 2023).	Finding areas for cost-effectiveness and efficiency improvements to help with resource allocation optimization.	Making strategic choices based on a deeper comprehension of the objectives of the organization and the needs of the patients.

Cooperative decision-making between AI systems and medical professionals can lead to a mutually beneficial partnership in which the advantages of both parties are utilized to enhance patient care, streamline processes, and increase medical knowledge. To fully realize the benefits of this partnership, there needs to be constant communication, mutual trust, and a dedication to a patient-centric methodology.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Machine learning is frequently used to analyze medical images to identify anomalies, diagnose diseases like tumors or fractures, evaluate genetic information, find mutations linked to disease, and customize treatment regimens based on unique genetic profiles. Massive clinical data sets, such as electronic health records (EHRs), can also be analyzed by ML algorithms to find trends and forecast the likelihood of developing a disease. ML and XAI have the potential to revolutionize the healthcare industry by providing cutting-edge approaches to patient care, treatment optimization, and diagnosis. Due to the importance of medical decisions and the requirement for interpretability in terms of ethics, XAI has garnered much attention in recent years for integration into clinical decision support systems (Umerenkov et al., 2023). Le et al. (2021) and Moncada-Torres et al. (2021) utilized XAI to predict cancer, while Duell et al. (2021) analyzed electronic health records, and Abeyagunasekera et al. (2021) applied XAI techniques to medical imaging. Alsinglawi et al. (2022) demonstrated the use of XAI in predicting the length of hospital stay for lung cancer patients, and Du et al. (2022) focused on predicting gestational diabetes mellitus. Similarly, Severn et al. (2022) employed XAI for analyses on medical images while Attai et al. (2023) applied XAI techniques to model comorbidities in pregnant women and children.

Suh et al. (2020) developed and validated an explainable artificial intelligence-based prostate biopsy decision-supporting tool. The risk calculator was developed and validated by the study using data from 3791 patients. The data was first split into sets for development and validation. Using five-fold cross-validation and hyperparameter tuning after feature selection in the development set, an extreme gradient-boosting algorithm was implemented on the development calculator. The Shapley value was used to calculate the model feature importance. For every calculator validation set, the receiver operating characteristic curve's area under the curve (AUC) was examined. PCa and csPCa were identified in about 1216 (32.7%) and 562 (14.8%) of the patients, respectively. While the data of 948 patients served as a test set, the data of 2843 patients were used for development. Using selection operator regression and the least absolute shrinkage, we chose the variables for each PCa and csPCa risk calculation. In contrast to the csPCa model, which had an AUC of 0.945 (95% CI 0.927–0.963), the final PCa model had an AUC of 0.869 (95% confidence interval [CI] 0.844–0.893). Important variables in the PCa model were discovered to be the prostate-specific antigen (PSA) level, free PSA level, age, prostate volume (both the transitional zone and total), hypoechoic lesions on ultrasonography, and testosterone level. The number of prior biopsies had a negative correlation with PCa risk but no correlation with the risk of csPCa. Before prostate biopsy, the study effectively created and validated a decision-supporting tool that uses XAI to calculate the probability of PCa and csPCa.

Peng et al. (2021) proposed an XAI framework to provide both local and global interpretation for auxiliary hepatitis diagnoses while maintaining high prediction accuracy. First, the framework's viability was evaluated using a public hepatitis classification benchmark from UCI. Afterward, both the transparent and black-box machine learning models were used to predict the progression of hepatitis. Clear models like k-nearest neighbour (KNN), decision tree (DT), and logistic regression (LR) were chosen. Random forests (RF), support vector machines (SVM), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) are examples of black-box models that were chosen. Lastly, the model interpretation of liver disease was enhanced by the use of Partial Dependence Plots (PDP), Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations

(LIME), and SHapley Additive exPlanations. The results of the experiments indicated that the complex models perform better than the simple ones. Out of all the models, the developed RF had the highest accuracy (91.9%). The suggested framework, which combines local and global interpretable methods, enhanced the transparency of complex models and provided insight into their conclusions. This helped to improve the prognosis of hepatitis patients and guide treatment decisions. Furthermore, the suggested framework might help clinical data scientists create a more suitable CAD structure.

El-Sappagh et al. (2021) developed a model for the diagnosis and progression detection of AD that is both accurate and comprehensible. This model gives doctors precise recommendations along with a series of justifications for each choice. The model specifically incorporates 11 modalities of 1048 subjects, 294 cognitively normal, 254 stable mild cognitive impairment (MCI), 232 progressive MCI, and 268 AD, from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) real-world dataset. With random forest as the classifier algorithm, the model is two layers deep. For early AD patient diagnosis, the model performs a multi-class classification in the first layer. To identify potential MCI-to-AD progression within three years of a baseline diagnosis, the model uses binary classification in its second layer. Key markers chosen from a wide range of biological and clinical metrics optimize the model's performance. In terms of explainability, we use the SHapley Additive exPlanations feature attribution framework to provide global and instance-based explanations of the RF classifier for each layer. Furthermore, to provide supplementary explanations for each RF decision in every layer, we implement 22 explainers based on fuzzy rule-based systems and decision trees. To further aid doctors in understanding the forecasts, these explanations are presented in plain language. In the first layer, the designed model achieves 93.95% cross-validation accuracy and an F1-score of 93.94%; in the second layer, it achieves 87.08% cross-validation accuracy and an F1-score of 87.09%. Thanks to the explanations provided, which are generally consistent with each other and with the AD medical literature, the resulting system is not only accurate but also trustworthy, accountable, and medically applicable. By offering thorough insights into how various modalities

affect the risk of AD, the proposed system can contribute to improving clinical understanding of the disease's diagnosis and progression processes.

Davagdorj et al. (2021) developed a deep neural network framework based on Deep Shapley Additive Explanations (DeepSHAP) and featuring a feature selection technique for predicting and explaining non-communicable diseases (NCDs) in the US population. To create a precise and understandable decision support system, the DeepSHAP-based DNN framework was furnished with an elastic net (EN) feature selection technique in addition to three distinct sets of important features generated from the NHANES dataset. There are three parts to the suggested framework: Third, the DeepSHAP approach provides two types of model explanation. Firstly, representative features are obtained using the elastic net-based embedded feature selection technique. Secondly, a deep neural network classifier is adjusted with hyperparameters and utilised to train the model using the chosen feature subset. Here, (I) the population-based risk factors influencing the model's prediction are explained; (II) a human-centred explanation of a single instance is attempted. According to the experimental results, the suggested model performs better than several cutting-edge models. Additionally, by offering broad insights into variations in disease risk on a local and global scale, the suggested model enhances medical understanding of NCD diagnosis. As a result, the explainable deep learning framework built on DeepSHAP not only benefits medical decision support systems but also meets practical needs in other fields.

Bogdanovic et al. (2022) used an explainable machine learning approach to present a comprehensive understanding of Alzheimer's disease. This study provided a comprehensive analysis of a sizable data set that included lifestyle, cognitive, and medical assessments from over 12,000 people. Given the results, the validity of several established hypotheses has been called into question. The research places a strong emphasis on the significance of using an appropriate experimental design. To properly preprocess the data set, a series of techniques for handling missing data, redundancy, data imbalance, and correlation analysis have been applied. As a result, the XGBoost model has been trained and evaluated with particular attention to the hyperparameter tuning. The Shapley values obtained from the SHAP method were

used to explain the model. XGBoost is regarded as being very competitive among those that have been published in the literature because it generated an F1-score of 0.84. But this accomplishment wasn't the paper's primary contribution. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the intelligent model's interpretability on a global and local level and draw insightful conclusions about the hypothesis that had been put forth. These techniques produced a single scheme that shows the values of each feature, whose significance has been verified using Shapley values, as having a positive or negative influence. This plan may be viewed as an extra resource for medical professionals and other specialists who are interested in precisely diagnosing Alzheimer's disease in its early stages. All of the preexisting theories were challenged by the conclusions drawn from the intelligent model's data-driven interpretability. The importance of an explainable machine learning approach that cracks open the mystery and makes the relationships between features and diagnoses visible was demonstrated by this study.

Vyas et al. (2022) used interpretable machine learning techniques on structured clinical records to determine the presence and severity of dementia. The techniques discussed in this paper are intended to address two dementia-related issues: (a) basic diagnosis, which is the process of determining whether a person has dementia, and (b) severity diagnosis, which is the process of forecasting both the presence and severity of dementia in an individual. The study used machine learning models based on random forests and decision trees to analyze structured clinical data from an elderly population cohort. These two tasks were formulated as classification problems. To ensure that curation decisions are meaningful, the study implemented a hybrid data curation strategy, involving a dementia expert and machine learning algorithms that categorized individual episodes into a particular dementia class that was used. Moreover, decision trees were used to improve the explainability of choices made by prediction models, enabling medical professionals to determine which patient characteristics are most important and at what threshold level to classify a patient as having dementia. The findings demonstrated that demographic characteristics and baseline math or cognitive tests can accurately predict dementia and its severity. Specifically, our prediction models have achieved an average f1-

score of 0.93 for problem (a) and 0.81 for problem (b). Furthermore, the decision trees generated for the two problems strengthen the prediction models' interpretability. This study demonstrated that by analysing different electronic medical record features and cognitive tests from the episodes of the elderly population, it is possible to accurately estimate the presence and severity of dementia disease. In addition, a collection of decision rules could serve as the foundation for a successful patient classification. Predictive features that are pertinent to clinical and screening tests serve as accurate indicators without requiring the computation of scores from widely used cognitive tests like the MMSE and CAMCOG. Not only is it able to recognize significant characteristics, but it can also recognize the rationale behind the classification. Therefore, the predictive ability of machine learning models over carefully selected clinical data is demonstrated, opening the door to a more precise dementia diagnosis.

Weng et al. (2022) created a framework that uses an explainable machine learning (ML) model to effectively distinguish between these two diseases. Intestinal data were gathered from Central South University's Second Xiangya Hospital; 160 patients with CD and 40 patients with ITB were included in the investigation. Every patient had an active medical condition. The clinical diagnosis of CD and ITB, as well as the European diagnostic guidelines, were combined with all cases. Nine variables are extracted in total after feature selection: intestinal dilatation, comb sign, bloody stool, PPD, knot, intestinal surgery, ESAT-6, and CFP-10. Also, the study contrasted the traditional statistical methods and machine learning's predictive performance. For the first time, this work also offered insights into the ML model's result using the SHAP method. Models are trained and validated using data from a cohort of 200 patients (CD=160, ITB=40). Findings showed that the XGBoost algorithm performs better than other classifiers in terms of the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC), sensitivity, specificity, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), and precision; these values are 0.891, 0.813, 0.969, 0.867, and 0.801, respectively. More importantly, the SHAP method provides an effective explanation for the prediction outcomes of XGBoost. The suggested

framework demonstrated how well interpretable machine learning can separate CD from ITB and provide both a general explanation and a patient-specific explanation. Kibria et al. (2022) proposed an ensemble method that combines an explainable AI and a soft voting classifier to predict the onset of diabetes mellitus. The study employed the Pima Indian diabetes dataset, which comprises 768 cases in total, 268 of which are diabetic, and 500 of which are non-diabetic but have multiple diabetic characteristics. To diagnose diabetes, an ensemble classifier was employed in conjunction with six machine learning algorithms: AdaBoost, XGBoost, logistic regression (LR), support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), artificial neural network (ANN), and logistic regression (LR). Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) were used to generate both global and local explanations for each machine learning model. These explanations were displayed in various graph types to aid medical professionals in comprehending the model predictions. With an F1 score of 89% and five-fold cross-validation (CV), the developed weighted ensemble model had a balanced accuracy of 90%. The dataset's classes were balanced using the synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTETomek), and the missing values were imputed using the median values. The suggested method can aid in the critical intervention at the earliest stages of the disease and enhance clinical comprehension of a diabetes diagnosis.

Islam et al. (2022) proposed an explainable AI model for stroke prediction using EEG data. This study aimed to predict acute stroke in active states by using machine learning (ML) models to classify the ischemic stroke group and the healthy control group. Additionally, the XAI tools Eli5 and LIME were used to identify the key features that go into stroke prediction models and to explain the model's behaviour. In this study, 75 healthy adults without a history of neurological disorders were compared to 48 patients who had been admitted to a hospital due to acute ischemic stroke. EEG was recorded using frontal, central, temporal, and occipital cortical electrodes within three months of the onset of symptoms associated with an ischemic stroke. While walking, working, and reading tasks were being performed, EEG data were being gathered. The Adaptive Gradient Boosting models in the ML approach's results demonstrated about 80% accuracy in classifying the stroke group and the

control group. The stroke prediction model's behaviour was explained by Eli5 and LIME, which were also used to interpret the model locally around the prediction. The spectral delta and theta features were highlighted by the Eli5 and LIME interpretable models as local contributors to stroke prediction. The stroke-prediction XAI model was anticipated to aid in post-stroke treatment and recovery, as well as assist healthcare professionals in making more explicable diagnostic decisions, based on the findings of this explainable AI research.

Kasani et al. (2023) used explainable machine learning techniques to assess the nutritional status and classify clinical depression. Using publicly available health data from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, this study sought to ascertain whether machine learning-based decision support methods could detect the presence of depression. For explanatory analysis across datasets, two exploration techniques were used: Pearson correlation and uniform manifold approximation and projection. The models were refined using a grid search optimisation with cross-validation in order to classify depression with the highest accuracy. The classifier performances were compared using a number of performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, confusion matrix, areas under the receiver operating characteristic curve and precision-recall curve, and calibration plot. The study also examined the significance of the following features: local interpretable explanations that are based on Shapley additive explanation and model-agnostic explanations, and visualised interpretation that employs ELI5, partial dependence plots, and explanations for prediction at the individual and population levels. The random forest model in the original dataset yielded an accuracy of 86.18% and an area under the curve of 84.96%, while the quantile-based dataset yielded an accuracy of 86.02% and an area under the curve of 85.34% for the XGBoost algorithm. These results indicate that the best model performed well. An additional observation of the relative changes in feature values was provided by the explainable results, which allowed for the identification of the significance of emergent depression risks. This study presented methods for both local and global interpretations to demonstrate the interpretability of ML models. ELI5 and PDP for worldwide interpretability and LIME and SHAP for local interpretation will be used

to address this problem. Generally speaking, based on the application requirements, both strategies might be equally appropriate. While local interpretability strategies provide explanations at the case-by-case level, global interpretability approaches have the advantage of being able to be applied to the entire population.

Islam et al. (2023) used machine learning algorithms to predict the risk of hypertension and Ethiopia provided the Hypertension (HTN) data, with 612 respondents and 27 factors. The study used a feature selection method based on Boruta to determine the key risk factors associated with hypertension. To predict HTN patients on the training set using the chosen risk factors, four well-known models, logistic regression, artificial neural network, random forest, and extreme gradient boosting, were created. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and area under the curve (AUC) were used to assess the models' performance on the testing set. Furthermore, one of the explainable artificial intelligence techniques, the SHAP method, was employed to look into the predictive risk factors linked to HTN. Patients with HTN are prevalent overall at 21.2%. This study demonstrated that the XGB-based model, which attained an accuracy of 88.81%, precision of 89.62%, recall of 97.04%, F1-score of 93.18%, and AUC of 0.894, was the most suitable model for predicting patients at risk of HTN. Age, weight, fat, income, body mass index, multiple diabetes, salt, history of hypertension, drinking, and smoking were found to be associated risk factors for developing hypertension, according to the XGB with SHAP analysis. The suggested framework offered a useful instrument for precisely identifying Ethiopians who are susceptible to HTN early on and may support early prevention and customized treatment.

Silva-Aravena et al. (2023) proposed a hybrid ML and XAI algorithm to prevent breast cancer. The work aims to present a machine learning and explainability algorithm-based decision support strategy for health teams. 200 of the 400 anonymous patient cases in the universe for this work had breast cancer and were from Indonesia. Several algorithms were employed in the methodology to categorize and choose the best candidates based on performance metrics like accuracy, recall, and precision. Furthermore, by using the SHAP algorithm, the methodology presented in this work offers new management components and an explainable

machine learning strategy that gives health professionals higher-quality information to use when making decisions about patients who may be at risk of breast cancer. With an accuracy of 0.813 for the train data and 0.81 for the test data, the results demonstrate that the XGBoost Algorithm has a better predictive capacity. Secondly, the SHAP algorithm makes it possible to identify the relevant variables, assess their significance in the prediction, and quantify the impact on the patient's clinical conditions. This enables health teams to provide early and customized alerts for each patient.

Zhu et al. (2023) proposed explainable machine-learning algorithms to distinguish bipolar disorder from major depressive disorder using self-reported symptoms, vital signs, and blood-based markers. To decrease the misdiagnosis of BD as MDD upon admission, the study set out to create a machine learning based diagnostic system based on electronic medical records (EMR) data. This system was to imitate the clinical reasoning of human physicians to distinguish between patients with MDD and BD (particularly BD depressive episodes) who were about to be admitted to a hospital. The study looked at how much the features that inform the predictions could be quantified and visualized to improve the interpretability of our ML model. We created three sub-cohorts with distinct feature combinations for the MDD-BD cohort and the MDD-BD depressive episodes cohort, respectively, by identifying 16,311 patients who were admitted to a hospital in western China between 2009 and 2018 and had a recorded main diagnosis of MDD or BD. The study employed four distinct machine learning algorithms, namely logistic regression, extreme gradient boosting, random forest, and support vector machine, along with four train-test splits, to develop and verify diagnostic models. Additionally, explainable methods, such as SHP and Break Down, were employed to examine the impact of individual and population-level features, such as feature importance, feature interaction, and feature effect on prediction decision for a particular subject. The best test performance (AUC: 0.838 (0.810–0.867), PPV: 0.810, and NPV: 0.834) for differentiating patients with BD from those with MDD was offered by the XGBoost algorithm. In addition to age, occupation, myocardial enzyme markers, diabetes-associated marker, bone function marker, non-enzymatic antioxidant, immune/inflammatory markers,

cardiovascular function marker, renal marker, liver biochemistry marker, and vital signs such as pulse, other core predictors included symptoms. The test's AUC was 0.777 (0.732–0.822), with PPV of 0.576 and NPV of 0.899, to distinguish patients with BD depressive episodes from those with MDD. Further validation using models constructed with self-reported symptoms eliminated from the feature set revealed an AUC of 0.701 (0.666–0.736) for the test of distinguishing between BD and MDD and 0.564 (0.515–0.614) for the test of identifying patients with BD depressive episodes from those with MDD. The AUC for the datasets that were validated without the comorbid patients removed was 0.826 (0.806–0.846). In a variety of clinical settings, the diagnostic system successfully identified patients with BD, and variations in peripheral marker patterns between BD and MDD may contribute to our comprehension of the pathophysiological mechanisms that underlie both conditions.

Huang et al. (2023) described a general machine learning pipeline that combines Shapley analysis with traditional machine learning to provide an explanation tool for biomarker discovery tasks in the medical domain. The PLCO Ovarian Biomarkers dataset case study was used in the study to illustrate the pipeline's efficacy and its agreement with established domain knowledge and conventional statistical analysis results. Concerning biomarker validation tasks, it sought to present best practices for integrating ML and XAI techniques. The study concentrated on classification tasks, utilizing a game-theoretic method based on Shapley values for model construction, assessment, and visualization of outcomes. To illustrate the pipeline's potential for accuracy and usefulness, the workflow was described and applied in a case study utilising the CDAS PLCO Ovarian Biomarkers dataset. The case study results show the ML pipeline's effectiveness, consistency, and benefits over traditional statistical methods. The guidelines that emerged from this process offered a broad framework for the useful implementation of XAI in medical research, which can enlighten physicians and validate and clarify cancer biomarkers.

Deshmukh et al. (2023) introduced a method for modelling medical data using explainable quantum clustering. An enhanced hybrid classical-quantum clustering approach, incorporating an additional explainable method, was presented in the study, which improved the qk-means algorithm. To diagnose abnormal activities

based on breast cancer images and Knee Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) datasets, the proposed model used learning strategies like the Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations method and improved quantum k-means (qk-means) algorithm and it then generated an explanation of the predictions. The accuracy of the generated clusters' clustering when compared to current algorithms boosts confidence in the explanations provided by the models. 510 knee MRI records with five features and 600 breast cancer (BC) patient records with seven features were used in the experiment. The outcome demonstrates that in the BC and Knee MRI datasets, the enhanced hybrid approach performs better than the classical one.

Ding et al. (2023) investigated the role of residential greenness for cardiac health in an explainable machine learning modelling to look at the epidemiological relationships between residential greenness and cardiac conduction abnormalities in rural residents. Participants in all came from the Henan Rural Cohort, totalling 27,294. Residential greenness was measured using two satellite-based indices: the enhanced vegetation index (EVI) and the normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI). Using the logistic regression model and the generalised linear model, associations between abnormalities in electrocardiogram (ECG) parameter values and residential greenness indices were assessed separately and in combination. In the modelling study, two algorithms were used: the Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) and the SHapely Additive exPlanations. For each interquartile range in the NDVI, the odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for abnormalities in the QRS interval, heart rate (HR), QTc interval, and PR interval were 0.896 (0.873–0.920), 0.955 (0.926–0.986), 1.015 (0.984–1.047), and 0.986 (0.929–1.045), respectively. Additionally, there was a 1.049-fold (1.017-1.081) and 1.298-fold (1.245-1.354) reduction in the risk for abnormal QRS interval and HR among the participants who reported higher levels of physical activity in addition to residential greenness (as determined by EVI). Similar outcomes from the sensitivity analysis were also noted. In the modelling study's analysis of QRS interval abnormality risk, the NDVI came in fifth place (SHAP mean value of 0.116). Heart conduction abnormalities were substantially correlated with higher residential greenness levels. Residents who engage in more physical activity may be more susceptible to this effect. This research

helped to improve preventive medicine and green design techniques while also demonstrating the critical role that environmental sustainability plays in cardiac functions.

Junaid et al. (2023) presented an explainable and accurate machine learning pipeline for PD progression prediction. The Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) real-world dataset included patient characteristics, biosamples, medication history, motor function data, and non-motor function data. The study investigated the fusion of various combinations of these five-time series modalities. Every patient saw six different doctors. A three-class based progression prediction with 953 patients in each time series modality and a four-class based progression prediction with 1,060 patients in each time series modality are the two approaches used to formulate the problem. Several feature selection techniques were used to choose the most illuminating feature sets after the statistical features of these six visits were computed from each modality. Several well-known machine learning models, such as stochastic gradient descent (SGD), extra tree classifier (ETC), random forests, light gradient boosting machines (LGBM), and support vector machines, were trained using the extracted features. We looked at several pipeline data-balancing techniques using various modality combinations. The Bayesian optimizer has been used to optimize machine learning models. After a thorough analysis of numerous machine learning techniques, the most effective models were expanded to offer a variety of explainability features. We compared the performance of machine learning models with and without feature selection, both before and after optimisation. With a 10-fold cross-validation (10-CV) accuracy of 90.73% using non-motor function modality, the LGBM model yielded the most accurate results in the three-class experiment and with different modality fusions. In the four-class experiment involving different modality fusions, RF yielded the best results with a non-motor modality 10-CV accuracy of 94.57%. The LGBM model performed better than the other ML models in both the 3-class and 4-class experiments using the fused dataset of non-motor and motor function modalities (i.e., 10-CV accuracy of 94.89% and 93.73%, respectively). The study used both global and instance-based explanations, utilising the Shapely Additive Explanations framework, to explain each ML

classifier's behaviour. Furthermore, by putting the LIME and SHAPASH local explainers into practice, we increased the explainability. It has been investigated whether these explainers are consistent. The resulting classifiers were more relevant and applicable in the medical field because they were precise and comprehensible. The literature and medical professionals validated the chosen modalities and feature sets. According to the different explainers, the most prevalent and reliable feature was bradykinesia (NP3BRADY). The proposed approach was anticipated to contribute to the advancement of clinical understanding of Parkinson's disease progression processes by offering comprehensive insights into the impact of multiple modalities on the disease risk.

Fan et al. (2023) sought to predict if a patient has hepatitis C using a variety of machine learning models. Additionally, they used explainable models to clarify the ML models' prediction process, thereby increasing transparency. They studied how serological testing could predict the presence of hepatitis C and offered thorough justifications for the prediction procedure. They modelled the benchmark dataset during the experiment and used independent testing experiments and fivefold cross-validation to assess model performance. The Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and AdaBoost black-box machine learning models were evaluated, and the study ultimately decided to use Bayesian-optimized RF as the classification algorithm. Regarding model interpretation, we employed the Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations with stability to provide local explanations for the model in addition to the common SHapley Additive exPlanations to provide global explanations. Independent testing and fivefold cross-validation both demonstrate that the suggested approach performs noticeably better than the state-of-the-art approach. Interpretable Hepatitis C prediction (IHCP) achieves good predictive performance while retaining excellent model interpretability. This made it possible to identify possible predictive patterns in the model and gave clinicians a better understanding of how the model makes decisions.

Bernard et al. (2023) developed a novel explainable machine learning framework to calculate a person's personalised physiological age (PPA). From NHANES 1999–2000 to NHANES 2017–2018, all NHANES study data were gathered from the

Centres for Disease Control and Prevention website. PPA was able to predict mortality and chronic illness without regard to age. It took only twenty-six variables to predict PPA. The study implemented a precise quantitative associated metric for each variable explaining physiological deviations from age-specific normative data using SHapley Additive exPlanations. Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) was one of the variables that showed a significant relative weight in the estimation of PPA. Lastly, distinct ageing trajectories were revealed by clustering profiles of contextualised explanations that were identical, providing opportunities for targeted clinical follow-up. According to these findings, PPA was a reliable, quantifiable, and understandable machine learning-based indicator of individualised health status. Furthermore, the method offered a comprehensive framework that can be applied to various datasets or variables, enabling accurate physiological age estimation.

Moreno-Sánchez (2023a) introduced an explainability-driven methodology to determine the optimal heart failure (HF) survival prediction model by weighing predictability and performance. The study uses a dataset of 299 patients with HF to present an explainability analysis and evaluation of two HF survival prediction models. First, the model applies survival analysis, using time and death events as target features; second, it treats the problem as a classification task to predict death. The model made use of an optimisation data workflow pipeline that can choose the best machine learning algorithm and the most advantageous feature set. Additionally, a variety of post hoc methods have been applied to the model's explainability analysis. With a c-index of 0.714 and a balanced accuracy of 0.74 (std 0.03) for the survival analysis and classification approach, respectively, the Survival Gradient Boosting model and Random Forest were the most balanced explainable prediction models. With the addition of "diabetes" for the survival analysis model, the SCI-XAI selected features for the two models like the first, selecting "serum_creatinine," "ejection_fraction," and "sex." Additionally, by ranking "serum_creatinine" and "ejection_fraction" as the most relevant features for the anticipated result, respectively, the application of post hoc XAI techniques also validated common findings from both approaches. The explainable prediction models for heart failure survival that were provided in this study would increase the uptake of clinical

prediction models by giving physicians a better understanding of the rationale behind the typically "black-box" AI clinical solutions, enabling them to make more logical and informed decisions.

Sharma et al. (2023) proposed a computerized, automated method for creating a machine learning model with explainable artificial intelligence capabilities. They classified CAP A and B phases and phases A sub-phases (A1, A2, A3) using wavelet-based Hjorth parameters. To shed light on the model, the study employs feature ranking based on SHAP. The MIT-BIH database's CAP sleep database (CAPSD) provided the experimental dataset used in this investigation. The Sleep Disorders Centre of the Ospedale Maggiore in Parma, Italy provided the 108 people's sleep recordings for the database, which was open to the public. 16 healthy people and 92 patients with a range of sleep disorders were included in these recordings. Of these, 9 patients had insomnia, 5 had narcolepsy, 40 had nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy (NFLE), 10 had periodic leg movement (PLM), 22 had REM behaviour disorder (RBD), and 4 had sleep-disordered breathing (SBD). Single-channel standardised EEG recordings from patients with nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy (NFLE), narcolepsy, periodic leg movement disorder (PLM), rapid eye movement behaviour disorder (RBD), and insomnia were used to develop the model. Using ensemble bagged trees (EbagT) and k-nearest neighbours (KNN) classifiers yields the best results. The proposed model successfully classified phases A and B with an average accuracy of 91.6% for healthy subjects and 94.33%, 86.3%, 88.68%, 84.43%, and 88.5% for narcolepsy, RBD, PLM, NFLE, and insomnia subjects, respectively. For the A subphases (A1, A2, A3), the model classified subjects with an average accuracy of 92.85% for healthy subjects and 93.9%, 84.9%, 88.0%, 80.92%, and 89.41% for narcolepsy, RBD, PLM, NFLE, and insomnia subjects, respectively. Using the microstructure of sleep, the suggested method might assist sleep specialists in automatically assessing an individual's quality of sleep.

Kırboğa et al. (2023) used explainable white box algorithms to diagnose troponin levels in the COVID-19 process and arrive at a lucid explanation. Troponin data was interpreted in the COVID-19 process using SHAP algorithms, utilizing pandemic data from Erzurum Training and Research Hospital (decision number: 2022/13-145).

There were five machine learning algorithms created. AUC (Area Under the Curve) values, recall, F1-score, test accuracies, training, and precision were used to assess the model's performance. Shapley values were used to estimate the importance of each feature by using the highly accurate SHAPley Additive exPlanations method on the model. Under the name CVD22, the model made with Streamlit v.3.9 was incorporated into the interface. With values of 1.0, 0.83, 0.86, 0.83, 0.80, and 0.91 in train and test accuracy, precision, F1-score, recall, and AUC values, respectively, the best machine learning model out of the five developed using pandemic data was chosen. Following feature selection and the application of SHAP algorithms to the XGBoost model, the features with the highest significance over the model estimation were found to be DDimer mean, mortality, CKMB (creatinine kinase myocardial band), and glucose. With the help of extensive historical datasets and recent developments in explainable artificial intelligence models, it is now possible to successfully predict the future. Therefore, CVD22 can be used as a guide to assist authorities or medical professionals in making timely decisions during the ongoing pandemic.

Mridha et al. (2023) presented a machine learning-based automated stroke prediction system. Two different explainable approaches, called SHAP and LIME, were applied to shed light on the black-box machine learning models. Especially in the medical field, well-proven and trustworthy methods for elucidating model decision-making are SHAP and LIME. The study's stroke prediction dataset, which was gathered from Kaggle, comprises 5110 rows and 12 columns. There were 4861 rows with a stroke value of zero and only 249 rows with a value of one, indicating an imbalance in the dataset. The SMOTE method was used to preprocess the data and balance it to improve accuracy. The experiment's results showed that more complex models performed better than simpler ones, with the best model obtaining an accuracy of nearly 91% and the other models achieving an accuracy of 83–91%. The suggested framework could help standardize complex models and gain insight into their decision-making, which can improve stroke care and treatment, and also include global and local explainable methodologies.

Moreno-Sánchez (2023b) reported on the creation and assessment of an explainable chronic kidney disease (CKD) prediction model that offers details on how various clinical characteristics of patients influence the early detection of CKD. The dataset, which included 400 patients with some missing values in their features, was gathered from the Apollo Hospital in Karaikudi, India, for about two months in 2015. Ten nominal, three ordinal, eleven numerical, and one target feature (notCKD/CKD) make up each dataset instance. The model was created with an optimisation framework that strikes a balance between explainability and classification accuracy. The primary contribution of the paper is its explicable, data-driven methodology, which provides quantitative insights into the role played by specific clinical features in the early detection of chronic kidney disease (CKD). Consequently, the best explainable prediction model uses three features (specific gravity, hypertension, and haemoglobin) to implement an extreme gradient boosting classifier. It achieves accuracy of 99.2% (standard deviation 0.8) and 97.5% with new, unseen data and a 5-fold cross-validation, respectively. Furthermore, haemoglobin is the most significant factor influencing the prediction, followed by specific gravity and hypertension, according to an explainability analysis. Due to the limited number of features chosen, early CKD diagnosis was now less expensive, suggesting a viable treatment option for developing nations.

Li et al. (2023) created a machine learning model that links the identification of CHD and exposure to heavy metals effectively and understandably. The US National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (US NHANES, 2003–2018) provided the datasets used to examine the relationships between heavy metals and CHD. To detect CHD based on exposure to heavy metals, five machine learning models were created. In addition, the models' strength was evaluated using eleven discriminating characteristics. The model that performed the best was chosen to be identified. Lastly, the features were interpreted using the SHapley Additive exPlanations tool to visualize the decision-making ability of the chosen model. 12,554 people in total met the eligibility requirements for this study. The optimal random forest classifier (RF) for identifying CHD was selected using data from 13 heavy metals (AUC: 0.827; 95%CI: 0.777–0.877; accuracy: 95.9%). The results of the SHAP analysis showed

that the model was positively influenced by cesium (1.62), thallium (1.17), antimony (1.63), dimethylarsonic acid (0.91), barium (0.76), arsenous acid (0.79), total arsenic (0.01) in urine, lead (3.58) and cadmium (4.66) in blood, and negatively influenced by cobalt (-0.15), cadmium (-2.93), and uranium (-0.13) in urine. Among US NHANES 2003–2018 participants, the RF model demonstrated efficiency, accuracy, and robustness in detecting a correlation between exposure to heavy metals and CHD. Positive correlations with CHD have been found for cesium, thallium, antimony, dimethylarsonic acid, barium, arsenous acid, and total arsenic in urine; negative correlations have been found for cobalt, cadmium, and uranium in urine.

Rajab et al. (2023) presented a transparent approach to malaria diagnosis by offering meaningful interpretations of severe malaria predictions made by machine learning models, using SHAP and LIME. In the study, several models were used, including AdaBoost, Naive Bayes, Explainable Boosting Machines (EBMs), Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, K-means, K-Nearest Neighbour, Support Vector Machine, Naive Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes. The study's findings demonstrated that Explainable Boosting Machines and Random Forest had the highest accuracy, at 84%. Additionally, EBM offered a useful clinical comprehension of the characteristics that lead to accurate prediction. After using GridSearchCV to improve prediction accuracy, the LR's accuracy was 81%. Moreover, XGBoost was utilized to estimate the model's skill on fresh data using K-fold validation. XAI improved the interpretations by identifying characteristics that lead to severe malaria. By using these methods, medical practitioners can make more informed decisions and the accuracy of severe malaria predictions can be greatly increased.

Ahmad et al. (2024) presented a novel framework that includes Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), a Bagged Tree-based classifier (BTBC), and coefficient and distance correlation feature selection algorithms for effective epileptic seizure detection. The discrete wavelet transform (DWT) is utilised to break down the EEG signals and extract different eigenvalue features of the statistical time domain (STD) as linear and Fractal dimension-based non-linear (FD-NL). The Butterworth filter is used to remove various artifacts. Correlation coefficients with P-value and distance correlation analysis are then used to identify the best features. The Bagged Tree-

based classifier (BTBC) then makes use of these features. Among machine learning models using popular Bonn and UCI-EEG benchmark datasets, the proposed model outperforms the others in terms of mitigating overfitting issues and improves the average accuracy by 2% using (CD, E), (AB, CD, E), and (A, B) experimental types. Ultimately, the suggested model's decision-making process was interpreted and explained using SHAP. The findings demonstrate how well the framework can classify ES, which will help patients with brain dysfunctions receive better diagnoses.

Alamatsaz et al. (2024) proposed a lightweight hybrid CNN-LSTM explainable model for ECG-based arrhythmia detection. The most common and standard diagnostic device for tracking and assessing cardiac electrical signals is the electrocardiogram (ECG). Numerous conditions can affect the human heart, including cardiac arrhythmias. An arrhythmia is an irregular heart rhythm that can be identified with ECG recordings. Severe cases of arrhythmia can result in stroke. Over the past few decades, there has been a lot of interest in the computerized and automated classification and identification of these abnormal heart signals due to the critical nature of early cardiac arrhythmia detection. To detect eight distinct cardiac arrhythmias with high accuracy and normal rhythms, the study used a light Deep Learning approach. The ECG signals were preprocessed using baseline wander removal and resampling methods to use DL techniques. An 11-layer network that combined long short-term memory and convolutional neural networks was used to perform the classification. ECG signals are selected from the two physionet databases, the long-term AF database and the MIT-BIH arrhythmia database, to assess the suggested method. Compared to the majority of state-of-the-art techniques, the CNN and LSTM combination used in the proposed DL framework produced more encouraging results. The mean diagnostic accuracy achieved by the suggested method is 98.24%. To better understand how our model makes predictions, a trained model for arrhythmia classification using a variety of ECG signals was developed and tested using SHAP, the most widely used XAI technique. According to the findings, the characteristics (ECG samples) that have made the biggest contributions to predictions align with the choices made by medical professionals. As a result, the

adoption of interpretable models raises clinicians' confidence in AI and reduces the amount of cardiovascular disease misdiagnoses.

Wani et al. (2024) proposed a hybrid model for the detection of lung cancer based on clinical data to assist healthcare professionals in making better decisions, explainable AI is used. To detect lung cancer and provide explanations for the predictions, this study presents "DeepXplainer," a novel interpretable hybrid deep learning-based technique. This method is predicated on XGBoost and a convolutional neural network. After "DeepXplainer" has automatically learned the features of the input using its numerous convolutional layers, XGBoost is used for class label prediction. SHAP is an explainable artificial intelligence method used to provide explanations or explainability of the predictions. This approach was used to process the "Survey Lung Cancer" dataset, which is publicly available. In terms of accuracy, sensitivity, F1-score, and other metrics, the suggested approach performed better than the current ones. The suggested approach produced results with an F1-score of 98.08, a sensitivity of 98.71%, and an accuracy of 97.43%. Following the model's exceptionally accurate predictions, each prediction is explicated through the local and global application of explainable artificial intelligence techniques. Numerous metrics have been used to assess the proposed "DeepXplainer," and the findings show that it performs better than the existing benchmarks. By offering explanations for the forecasts, the suggested method might make it easier for medical professionals to identify and treat lung cancer patients.

LLMs have enormous potential in medicine; they can be used for anything from enhancing clinical decision-making to increasing diagnostic accuracy (Karabacak & Margetis, 2023). LLMs can extract important information from electronic health records, discharge summaries, and other medical texts. Efficient data retrieval can be facilitated by the ability of large language models to identify and extract critical clinical information, including medication histories, treatment plans, patient demographics, and medical histories. In addition to integrating patient data from multiple sources to help diagnose complex cases by taking a wider view of information, LLMs can help analyze symptoms as reported by patients, giving medical professionals more context for diagnostic decision-making (Umerenkov et

al., 2023). LLMs can interpret and summarize laboratory results, diagnostic imaging reports, and pathology reports (Thirunavukarasu et al., 2023) in addition to helping physicians comprehend complex findings and can also help create treatment recommendations based on the most recent clinical guidelines and evidence. Social media and other textual data can be analyzed by LLMs to track public opinion (Törnberg et al., 2023) and spot possible outbreaks or health issues and by searching textual data for patterns suggestive of new health risks, LLMs can aid in the early detection of disease outbreaks.

Agbavor and Liang (2022) suggested using large language models to predict dementia from spontaneous speech. The study produced text embedding, a vector representation of the speech transcription that captures the semantic meaning of the input, by utilizing the extensive semantic knowledge encoded in the GPT-3 model. We show that using only speech data, the text embedding can be used to (1) reliably distinguish AD patients from healthy controls, and (2) infer the subject's cognitive testing score. According to the study, text embedding performs on par with existing fine-tuned models and significantly outperforms the traditional acoustic feature-based method. The findings indicated that GPT-3-based text embedding is a workable method for assessing AD straight from speech and may enhance dementia early diagnosis.

Almazayad et al. (2023) introduced a novel way to use ChatGPT-4 to improve expert panel discussions during a medical conference. The study examined how well ChatGPT-4 performed in optimizing and summarising the recommendations made by the medical conference panel at the inaugural Pan-Arab Paediatric Palliative Critical Care Hybrid Conference, which took place in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. First, the AI model optimized scenarios to encourage in-depth conversations; then, the model identified, summarised and contrasted important themes from the panel and audience discussions. This is how ChatGPT-4 was integrated into the discussions. Based on a summary of important themes like good communication, teamwork, patient- and family-centered care, trust, and ethical considerations, the findings indicate that ChatGPT-4 successfully supported complex do-not-resuscitate (DNR) conflict resolution. Incorporating ChatGPT-4 into panel discussions about paediatric

palliative care has shown potential advantages for improving medical professionals' critical thinking skills. The study recommended that more research is necessary to validate and expand these insights across different contexts and cultures.

Yang et al. (2023) examined the use of an optimized model-based outpatient treatment support system for the treatment of diabetes patients and evaluated its possible advantages. The investigation's focus was the ChatGLM model, which was trained using the P-tuning and LoRA fine-tuning techniques. The refined model was then effectively incorporated into the Hospital Information System (HIS). Based on the basic information, primary complaints, medical history, and diagnosis data of each patient, the system generates personalized treatment recommendations, suggestions for laboratory tests, and medication prompts. The results of the experimental testing demonstrated that the improved ChatGLM model can produce precise treatment recommendations based on patient data, along with suggestions for suitable laboratory tests and medication reminders. The model's outputs, however, may come with risks for patients with complicated medical records and are not a complete replacement for outpatient physicians' clinical judgment and decision-making skills. The electronic health record (EHR) is the only source of data used by the model, which makes it difficult to fully reconstruct the patient's treatment course and occasionally results in inaccurate assessments of the patient's treatment objectives.

Zhang et al. (2023) evaluated ChatGPT and GPT-4 on several medical domain tasks. Nevertheless, none have examined its effectiveness in providing clinical diagnostic support for patients across the entire spectrum of disease presentation, nor evaluated its performance using a large-scale real-world electronic health record database. Using a real-world large electronic health record database, the study conducted two analyses using ChatGPT and GPT-4: one to identify patients with specific medical diagnoses, and the other to assist healthcare providers in the prospective evaluation of hypothetical patients by offering diagnostic support. The findings demonstrate that GPT-4 can achieve up to 96% F1 scores on various disease classification tasks when chain of thought and few-shot prompting are used. In terms of patient assessment, GPT-4 has a three-out-of-four diagnostic accuracy rate. There were, however,

references to factually false claims, missing important medical discoveries, suggestions for pointless research, and overtreatment. These problems, along with privacy concerns, render these models unsuitable for clinical use in the real world at this time. In contrast to the configuration of traditional machine learning workflows, prompt engineering requires less data and less time, which highlights its potential for scalability across healthcare applications.

Liu et al. (2023) developed and evaluated the efficacy of large language models that had been fine-tuned to generate responses to patient messages sent via an electronic health record patient portal. The authors used an OpenAI API to update physician responses from an open-source dataset into a format with informative paragraphs that offered patient education while emphasizing empathy and professionalism. They did this by using a dataset of messages and responses that were extracted from the patient portal at a large academic medical centre. The model they developed, called CLAIR-Short, was based on a pre-trained large language model, called LLaMA-65B. Ten typical patient portal questions in primary care were used to generate responses to assess the fine-tuned models. The datasets were combined to further refine our model (CLAIR-Long). Primary care physicians were asked to rate the empathy, responsiveness, accuracy, and usefulness of generated responses from ChatGPT and our models. Compared to CLAIR-Short responses, CLAIR-Long responses offered more patient education, and they were evaluated similarly to ChatGPT responses, with favourable ratings for accuracy, responsiveness, and empathy, and a neutral rating for usefulness. The results indicated that there was a great deal of promise for improving communication between patients and primary care physicians by using large language models to produce replies to patient messages.

Barnard et al. (2023) assessed the potential of large language models as a tool for general user self-diagnosis along with how LLMs could contribute to the dissemination of false information about medical conditions. Although these models' success on medical exams has been used to support their use in medical diagnosis and training, the effects of their unavoidable use as a self-diagnostic tool and their role in disseminating false information about healthcare have not been assessed. A testing methodology that can be applied to assess answers to open-ended questions

that resemble real-world use cases was developed as part of the study. In the process, it became clear that: a) these models perform worse than previously thought; and b) they display strange behaviours, such as overconfidence when making incorrect recommendations, which raises the possibility of disseminating false information about medicine.

Omiye et al. (2023) evaluated the extent to which four large language models that are commercially available propagate harmful or inaccurate content based on race in response to eight distinct scenarios. These scenarios have in the past involved race-based medicine or the propagation of widespread misconceptions about race. Four medical experts' discussions and earlier research on medical trainees' racial misconceptions about medicine served as the basis for the questions. Four extensive language models were evaluated using five interrogations of eight distinct questions, yielding a total of forty answers for each model. In their responses, all models included instances of how race-based medicine is still practiced. When asked the same question repeatedly, models' responses weren't always consistent. According to the study, LLMs are being considered for application in the healthcare industry, and certain models have already been shown to interface with EHRs. However, the research revealed that these LLMs might be harmful because they continue to promote racist and debunked ideas.

Meskó et al. (2023) contended that regulatory supervision ought to guarantee that patients and medical practitioners can utilize large language models without risking harm or jeopardizing their privacy or data. Because of their many applications, LLMs have already attracted a lot of attention regarding their possible use in healthcare settings. Since LLMs are trained differently from AI-based medical technologies that are already regulated, especially in the crucial context of patient care, extreme caution is warranted when using them. The most recent version, GPT-4, was released in March 2023 and expands on the technology's potential to support a variety of medical tasks. However, it also increases the risk of mishandling the results it provides and its varying reliability. It will be able to read texts on images and assess the context of those images in addition to being an advanced LLM. In order to guarantee safety, uphold moral principles, and safeguard patient privacy, the

regulation of GPT-4 and generative AI in medicine and healthcare without undermining their fascinating and revolutionary potential is an urgent and vital task.

According to Thirunavukarasu et al. (2023), several biomedical contexts have already used LLM chatbots, with impressive but inconsistent results. Certain issues and concerns, like transfer learning, domain-specific fine-tuning, and ethical and legal frameworks, must be addressed for their successful integration (Karabacak and Margetis, 2023). Notwithstanding these challenges, LLMs have demonstrated promise in healthcare and medical research. One study showed how to develop a clinical generative LLM called GatorTronGPT, which performed better than NLP models trained on actual clinical text (Peng et al., 2023). Moreover, LLMs in conjunction with local training have demonstrated efficacy in managing intricate, domain-specific medical tasks, like the extraction of structured condition codes from pathology reports (Bumgardner et al., 2023).

Harskamp and De-Clercq (2024) evaluated the accuracy of ChatGPT's recommendations for medical questions about common cardiac conditions or symptoms. Two approaches were used in the study to assess ChatGPT's capacity to respond to medical queries. Firstly, by evaluating its precision in accurately responding to trivia questions about cardiovascular disease that are based on tests administered to medical professionals. Secondly, by entering 20 clinical case vignettes into the ChatGPT platform, the accuracy was assessed with both expert judgment and clinical instruction. The most recent research version (v3.5; September 27, 2023) was compared to a previous version (v3.5; January 30, 2023) to assess progress over time. The findings indicated that the most recent version of ChatGPT answered 92% of the trivia questions correctly, with slightly different accuracy in the following domains: heart failure (90%) and cardiovascular risk management (80%), atrial fibrillation (90%), pulmonary and venous thrombotic embolism (100%), coronary artery disease (100%), and atrial fibrillation (90%). Of the 20 case vignettes, ChatGPT's response corresponded with the real advice in 17 (85%) of the cases. All of the simple questions posed by patients to the doctors were accurately answered (10/10). When compared with expert consultation, ChatGPT provided incomplete, inconclusive, or inappropriate recommendations in 70% of cases

involving more complex medical cases involving general practitioners who sought assistance from cardiologists. The January version of ChatGPT correctly answered 74% (vs92%) of trivia questions ($p=0.031$), and only 50% of complex cases. This indicates that ChatGPT has significantly improved over time. According to the study, ChatGPT has potential as an AI-assisted decision support tool in medicine, especially for simple, low-complex medical queries. However, more investigation is required to completely assess this potential.

Accurate disease diagnosis significantly depends on the predictive ability of ML and soft computing techniques, even though XAI adds transparency and trust to the decision-making process, and LLM uses natural language processing to improve understanding of complex medical data. ML and soft computing techniques provide strong algorithms that can find patterns in huge datasets, allowing for accurate diagnosis. However, these techniques lack interpretability, so combining them with XAI is crucial to guarantee that medical professionals can comprehend and have faith in their decision-making process. The application of ML and soft computing techniques to disease diagnosis is examined in the next section.

Uzoka et al. (2011) compared the efficacy of the AHP and fuzzy methodologies in the medical diagnosis of malaria to offer a framework for choosing the proper kernel in a hybrid system that combines AHP and fuzzy logic. Six doctors from four hospitals (two public and two private) helped gather data from thirty patients so that the experiment could be carried out. Five patients with malaria were sent to each doctor to get a diagnosis. The doctor rated each patient using a "diagnosis sheet," with the patient's permission, based on 22 possible symptoms of malaria. The diagnosis sheets for each patient's symptoms were then processed independently by the AHP and fuzzy methodologies to produce diagnoses. These diagnoses were then compared with the final diagnoses made by the medical professionals to assess the accuracy of the diagnosis made by the AHP and fuzzy methodologies. In comparison, the fuzzy system had an 80% accurate diagnosis with the medical expert, compared to 67% for the AHP. The fuzzy system had a higher correlation (0.821) than the AHP method (0.717) in the diagnosis correlation between the medical experts and the two methods. Overall, there was an exact match in 76.67% of the fuzzy and AHP

diagnoses. The study's findings demonstrate that expert computer-based diagnostic systems that support less-experienced doctors in diagnosing malaria can be successfully created using fuzzy logic and the AHP system. Fuzzy logic, on the other hand, performed marginally better than the AHP, with non-significant statistical differences. The study's limitations included the following: insufficient experience and imprecise symptomatology lead to higher rates of morbidity and mortality; additionally, doctors with little training have difficulty making accurate diagnoses; and the system could only diagnose a single febrile illness.

Samuel et al. (2013) utilized fuzzy logic (FL) to power a web-based decision support system for Typhoid Fever diagnosis. The system was developed to give medical professionals, researchers studying typhoid fever, and healthcare providers in underdeveloped nations around the globe a platform for decision support. Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) with Fuzzifier, Fuzzy Inference Engine (FIE), and Defuzzifier were the techniques employed; FIE employs the Root Sum Square (RSS) approach to produce valid conclusions. A fuzzy inference system (FIS) and a knowledge base (KB) are the two components that make up the system and the FIS comprises a Fuzzy Inference Engine (FIE), Defuzzifier, and Fuzzifier. The efficiency of the proposed system in providing accurate diagnosis was 94%. The study's limitation stemmed from the fact that making an accurate and timely diagnosis was challenging due to multiple variables involved in the diagnosis process and it could only diagnose a single illness. The research recommended that future studies in the field of medical diagnosis systems explore the idea of neural networks and apply it to medical diagnosis systems based on fuzzy logic to maximize performance.

A study by Oguntimilehin et al. (2013) developed an approach to diagnose typhoid fever using a machine learning technique. A total of 150 datasets on cases of typhoid fever were gathered from respectable hospitals in Ekiti State, Nigeria, and used in training and testing. Medical professionals provided explanations on the symptomatic diagnosis of typhoid fever while carefully selecting and examining the patient records of those who had been diagnosed with the disease. The data had 18 symptoms and typhoid fever was grouped into five classes (very-low, low, moderate, High, and very-high) by the medical experts. The study utilized a rough set in

building the classification model for diagnosing typhoid fever. The classification accuracies of the training set and testing sets are 95% and 96% respectively and the researchers recommended a hybrid system, that could provide a better performance in the diagnosis of typhoid fever. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

Imianvan and Obi (2014) conducted a study in which they proposed an expert system to reduce uncertainty and imprecision in the diagnosis of enteric fever using Fuzzy classifier. Enteric fever can cause life-threatening symptoms such as high fever, headache, constipation, chills, mild vomiting, abdominal pain, tongue changes, thirst, diarrhea, fatigue, slow heartbeat, myalgia, and anemia. The limitation of the study is the way in which membership functions are designed affects how well a fuzzy classifier performs. Membership functions specify how input variables, like test results or symptoms, are mapped to fuzzy sets. A great deal of domain expertise and meticulous tuning are needed to design membership functions that are accurate and representative. Typhoid fever misdiagnoses or missed diagnoses can arise from inaccurate or subpar membership functions that cause poor classification performance. In clinical settings, fuzzy classifiers may not be as robust and reliable due to their sensitivity to membership function design. The study also revealed that the machine learning approach improves diagnostic accuracy for typhoid fever.

Andrianto et al. (2019) developed a decision support system for diagnosing typhoid fever using machine learning techniques. This study aimed to assist medical professionals in making medical decisions by integrating clinical variables and laboratory blood variable testing. The medical data used in this paper was obtained from Jemur Sari Islamic Hospital in Surabaya, Indonesia. The data included medical history information, complete blood test data (CBC), and diagnosis information from internists and children's Poli units, with 831 cases of negative typhoid fever and 701 cases of positive fever making up the total dataset of 1532. This study employed Naïve Bayes (NB), K-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification techniques. kNN, SVM, and NB had the following performance metrics precision (88.1%, 67%, and 56.8%), recall (88.6%, 56.4%, and 72.2%), and F1_score (88.7%, 65.5%, and 60%), respectively. According to the researchers, the

optimal kNN classification results can be applied to a clinical decision support system and this can aid medical professionals in diagnosing typhoid fever, particularly in primary care settings where specialists are still in short supply. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

Obot et al. (2014) proposed an intelligent system based on fuzzy Logic and fuzzy clustering to help doctors diagnose confusable diseases accurately and quickly. The methods used were Fuzzy Clustering Means (FCM) and Adaptive Neuro-fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS). General hospitals in Nigeria's Akwa Ibom State provided the datasets for the study. Patients with confirmed diagnoses of any of these tropical diseases, malaria, typhoid, viral hepatitis, and urinary tract infections, were given details by specialized physicians. Based on the patient's self-reported symptoms and the physical examination, the medical professional assigns linguistic values that indicate the stage of the 22 symptoms used in the study. The Partition Coefficient (PC) and Partition Entropy Coefficient (PE) values from the cluster validation analysis are 0.396 and 0.795, respectively. The PC value falls within the range $[\frac{1}{4}, 1]$ and is closer to the lower bound (0.25), indicating the presence of fuzzy partitions. Similarly, the PE value of 0.795 falls within the required range of $[0, \log_4 4]$ (0,1), explaining the existence of fuzzy clusters. The results indicate that the system provides the patient's level of severity for each confusable disease and compares favourably with diagnoses made by skilled physicians. The limitation of the study is that the dataset used was quite small and only four febrile diseases were considered.

A study by Uzoka et al. (2016) developed a fuzzy cognitive map model (FCM)-based soft computing system for the differential diagnosis of tropical diseases. Twenty patients were used in the FCM model's diagnosis of malaria. The dataset includes the patient's demographic data, symptoms, the doctor's preliminary theory, further investigation, and the doctor's definitive diagnosis. This study employs a two-phase model application and assessment methodology. The initial phase addresses the static framework of the fuzzy cognitive map methodology, which combines malaria symptoms and risk factors and utilizes semantic cause-effect relationships to diagnose cases, which is encoded in the inference mechanism and knowledge base. The second step entails applying the interrogation algorithm to the diagnosis

procedure to maximize its effectiveness. The study comprised patients who were over 40 years old (45%), 20% of whom were younger than 10 years old, 35% of whom were between the ages of 11 and 40 and 80% of the doctors had five years and more experience in diagnosing tropical diseases. The results show that while the FCM's diagnosis was accurate in 85% of cases, the doctors' initial theories were accurate in only 55% of cases. This finding is intriguing since it would seem that the doctors would have better classification accuracy than the FCM system. It's also crucial to note that there was only a negligible correlation (0.14) between the doctor's experience level and the initial hypothesis' accuracy. The study's limitation is its limited generalizability due to the small sample size of test data used.

Nathaniel et al. (2017) developed a system to diagnose typhoid fever using fuzzy logic because fuzzy logic can accurately simulate human thought processes. The system demonstrated the ability to receive patient data and symptoms, process the data, and then output a diagnosis to the user. The system has over 200 inference rules and uses twenty-one (21) membership functions as inputs and demonstrated reliability, with an accuracy rate of 97.5%, positioning it as a dependable method for diagnosing typhoid fever. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

Uzoka et al. (2017) employed the AHP model to diagnose tropical febrile diseases. Using the AHP data collection instrument, the study gains firsthand knowledge from medical professionals about the diagnosis of tropical confusable diseases by extracting 15 doctors experience knowledge who specialize in diagnosing tropical diseases. In total, eighteen symptoms were taken into account in the study and a tool was devised to identify the risk factors linked to the diseases that are being studied. Using statistical tests of significance, the following risk factors were identified: working as a street vendor, having poor personal hygiene, traveling to an endemic area, and coming into contact with sick people. The researchers created a model-implementing Android application and installed it on 35 tablet computers so that doctors in Africa could test the system. Despite the common symptom overlap of tropical diseases, one of the main features of the system is its ability to detect comorbidity. The limitation of the study is that the system was unable to handle

diseases that are not included in the model and the system indicates the diagnosis as "other," necessitating additional investigation on the part of the doctor.

Hezekiah et al. (2020) created a system of artificial intelligence called ARIS to diagnose typhoid fever. The primary goals were to identify the most important risk factors for Typhoid Fever (Typhoid Responsive Expert System, or TyRes), develop a fuzzy logic base-expert system that can forecast the illness based on symptoms, and utilize TyRes to predict TyF in patients. To gather data, two sets of questionnaires were employed. Patients in 25 hospitals in Lagos, Abeokuta, and Ifo, South-West Nigeria, received 325 copies. To gather information about TyF and its symptoms, another 200 copies were given to human medical experts (HME), which included 140 certified nurses and 70 doctors. Chi-Square was used to analyze the data and determine the primary symptoms that the majority of the HME observed. Matlab 2015a was used to implement TyRes with the primary factors serving as input variables. The development of TyRes involved the use of input variables such as vomiting, loss of appetite, abdominal pain, weakness, and high temperature. A 76% accuracy rate was obtained when predicting TyF in 25 patients by comparing HME predictions with TyRes outcomes and the study concluded that 76% of all TyF predictions can be modelled by TyRes. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

Okagbue et al. (2021) utilized data mining models to diagnose malaria by utilizing 15 symptoms from 337 patients in Nigeria. Weak associations between symptoms and outcomes were discovered after eight ML algorithms were applied to the data. However, a secret pattern was discovered that accurately predicted results according to symptoms, age, and sex. The top model was the Adaboost, which had a 1.8% error rate, 98.2% classification accuracy, and 96.6% precision. The result implies that the Adaboost model could be utilized in malaria-endemic areas to create quick diagnostic tools or decision support systems for malaria diagnosis, thereby lowering misdiagnosis and enhancing public health.

Maidabara et al., (2021) developed an effective system for diagnosing patients with typhoid and malaria. Data was gathered from the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital over four years, spanning from 2017 to 2020. The study investigated the

possible advantages of putting forth a novel model for symptom-based diagnosis and prediction of typhoid and malaria using the Naive Bayes (NB) model, which was implemented in Python. In under thirty minutes, the system provides a real-time diagnosis and does so without requiring a trip to the laboratory for testing. The study employed three distinct algorithms: NB, SVM, and Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The outcomes show that NB and SVM yield the highest diagnostic accuracy of 100%.

Muhammad and Varol (2021) used the decision tree classification to develop a predictive diagnostic model for malaria diagnosis. Collected with the symptomatic features of experimental laboratory data from patients, a total of 500 hospital samples were gathered; 300 of which were utilized for training, 150 for testing, and 50 for validation. Demographic information, including age, sex, and tribe, was also gathered at the Maryam Abacha Hospital in Sokoto, Nigeria. These all functioned as input variables for the algorithm. Better pre-processing results were obtained by replacing all missing values with software after the data were preprocessed. By identifying the patients' malaria stages based on their symptoms, a 77% accurate decision algorithm was created. This study also revealed that, contrary to what many other research studies have suggested, malaria does not only kill young people (those under five years old). According to this study, older women are more likely to contract malaria at a severe stage. Because decision trees are so sensitive to even slight variations in the data, small changes in the data can produce entirely different trees. This instability may lead to unreliability in the model.

Odion and Ogonnia (2022), proposed a web-based machine learning system for diagnosing malaria and typhoid fever using the Flask web framework and the XGBoost machine learning algorithm for better classification results. 690 data was collected from a single diagnostic centre located in Nnewi, Anambra state, Nigeria, which included patients' lab test results along with their symptoms for this study. The input variables used were high temperature, headache, weakness, body and Abdominal pain, vomiting, age, gender, and widal count. The binary classifier for malaria has a 99.2% F1-Score and an accuracy of 98.6%, while the multi-class classification for malaria has a 96.8% F1-Score and an accuracy of 97.6%. Similarly,

the multi-class classifier for typhoid has an accuracy of 96.1 % and an F1-Score of 95.1 %, while the typhoid binary classifier has a 96.1% accuracy and a 98.5% F1-Score. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose two diseases (typhoid fever and malaria).

Mariki et al. (2022) aimed to demonstrate supervised ML models for diagnosing malaria utilizing demographic information and patient symptoms. The study utilized a malaria diagnosis dataset from two regions in Tanzania, selecting important features to speed up processing and improve model performance. ML classifiers, including SVM, K-Nearest Neighbour, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and Random Forest, were employed with k-fold cross-validation. High accuracy was attained by the study; RF in Kilimanjaro reached 95% accuracy, Morogoro 87%, and the combined dataset 82% accuracy. However, the paper does not provide specific quantitative metrics such as recall, precision, or F1 score for the classifiers used.

Uzoka et al. (2022) developed an AHP model for the diagnosis of Typhoid fever by mining the experiential knowledge of medical professionals with expertise in treating similar conditions and having firsthand experience with them. The Analytic Hierarchy Process model for typhoid fever diagnosis and the physicians' firsthand experience treating tropical diseases were the study's methods. The AHP model was tested on 2044 patient data, and the model effectively identified whether typhoid fever was present in 78.91% of the cases, indicating the effectiveness of AHP in typhoid fever diagnosis. The study's limitation was that the model was only intended for one febrile illness (typhoid fever), and that techniques like the adaptive AHP approach and linguistic preference relations, which also improve consensus, could have improved the pairwise comparison's consistency.

Awotunde et al. (2022) developed a system that utilizes Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (GENFIS) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) to diagnose typhoid fever and malaria. To train the GENFIS, the GA component first verifies the ideal collection of network features and saves and delivers these features to the right hidden layer nodes. The system is tested and evaluated in the study using the MATLAB environment. The model outperformed some of the current systems, yielding an accuracy performance of 97.2%. The recommended strategy may lessen the main problems

with GENFIS systems if it is fully implemented. Additionally, it can be applied to challenging problems in various fields.

Obot et al. (2023a) developed a mobile app to aid CHWs in diagnosing, and treating tropical febrile diseases in low-to-middle-income countries due to the acute shortage of experienced physicians in the rural communities in these regions. This work aimed to create a decision support system (DSS) that frontline health workers (FHWs) can use to diagnose febrile illnesses. The methods used in the study were AHP, Agile methodology, and experiential knowledge of physicians. Experiential knowledge was extracted from 62 experts in the field of diagnosing febrile diseases and their related symptoms in secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities in some states in the southern part of Nigeria. 11 illnesses and 50 symptoms were used in this study. 3253 patient data was also obtained from these healthcare facilities by these medical experts, and these patients provided information on the symptoms of the 11 different febrile diseases. The analytic hierarchy process, which is a multi-criteria decision technique, was used to develop the diagnostic engines. The linear consensus models in the AHP engine determine which disease the decision support filters should activate. The AHP diagnostic engines facilitate the identification of suspected illnesses based on the patient's symptoms and risk factors, helping to differentiate between the symptoms of febrile illnesses and recommend the best course of action. The AHP model showed 90% diagnosis accuracy and 91% precision. The limitation of the study is that it relied on the experience and knowledge of 62 doctors.

Obot et al. (2023b) created an FCM-based MDSS for febrile diseases to address the issue of patients with febrile illnesses often having limited access to medical care in resource-scarce regions and the issue of inexperienced doctors often struggling to distinguish between the signs and symptoms of febrile diseases. A fuzzy cognitive map model was developed in response to this, to provide medical professionals with a decision-support tool for diagnosing febrile diseases. The model was created by fuzzifying and weighting 2465 datasets from four states in Nigeria's regions that are prone to febrile diseases, with the assistance of 60 medical doctors involved in the process of obtaining the datasets. In this study, 11 diseases and 50 symptoms were used to illustrate the FCM ideas. For the 11 febrile diseases included in the study, the

average accuracy of the computations used to predict diagnosis results for the 2465 patients and those diagnosed by the doctors on the scene was 87%. The presence of enteric fever and malaria in over 80% of the datasets is concerning, as the combined percentage of yellow fever, dengue fever, and laser fever in the datasets is only 2% and this imbalance in the dataset contributed to the unsatisfactory results. Another flaw in the study is the early convergence of FCM, which shows up in situations where the equilibrium is reached after as few as six iterations. The study will eventually be expanded to include intuitionistic fuzzy logic and interval type-2 and it suggests conducting additional research excluding dengue, Lassa, and yellow fever from the dataset. The study's drawback is that patient records older than 16 were chosen, depriving patients younger than 16 from using the system.

Bhuiyan et al. (2023) proposed predictive models for diagnosing enteric fever, another name for typhoid fever. Deep learning and machine learning techniques were used in the study to develop prediction models. The study demonstrated the effective use of machine learning algorithms, like XGBoost, in diagnosing typhoid fever with a high accuracy rate of 97.87% before clinical trials are conducted. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

Suryani et al. (2023) developed an android-based expert system for diagnosing enteric fever. fuzzy logic algorithm was utilized to reduce the uncertainty and imprecision involved with conventional medical diagnosis techniques. Expert knowledge about the general and clinical symptoms that typhoid fever patients frequently experience, as well as information about the severity of the disease, were incorporated into the development of the application. Direct observation at the hospital and in-person interviews with physicians were used to gather data. After processing the data, the system generated output in the form of suggested solutions and diagnostic findings. Three user levels can be found in the application: Administrators, who can handle user data; Users, who can diagnose their diseases by answering questions in the application; and Experts, who can handle symptom, disease, and solution data. The research findings are available as an application that can be used at any time to serve as a stand-in consultant for the community, providing

diagnostic results in the form of negative, positive, or strongly positive typhoid. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

Mariki (2023) used symptomatic and non-symptomatic patient data to develop an ML model for Tanzanian malaria diagnosis. Significant features such as fever, body malaise, visit date, residence area, age, and headache were chosen, and the model was trained using k-fold cross-validation techniques. For the Kilimanjaro, Combined, and Morogoro datasets, respectively, RF and DT methods yielded the highest prediction accuracy rates, at 96%, 99%, and 98%. Using observable symptoms and non-symptomatic variables, the model allows for the prediction of the patient's malarial status before the prescription of antimalarial drugs. The findings have the potential to lower medication resistance and enhance the management of malaria in medical facilities and drug distribution centres.

Bhuiyan et al. (2023) created a typhoid fever prediction model using deep learning and machine learning before conducting a clinical trial in Africa. More health industries are using machine learning techniques as a result of the amazing results that machine learning and deep learning have produced for extrapolative analysis. Deep learning and ten different machine learning algorithms were used in this paper to create the model and the XGBoost classifier yielded the best performance with an accuracy of 97.87%. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose typhoid fever.

In related work, Suryani et al. (2023) developed an Android-based typhoid fever diagnostic application using a fuzzy logic algorithm. The application was developed using data on the severity of typhoid disease as well as expert knowledge about general and clinical symptoms that patients with the illness frequently experience. Direct observation at the hospital and in-person interviews with physicians were used to gather data. After being processed, the data was output in the form of the system's recommended solutions and diagnostic results. The application is divided into three user levels: experts who can process symptom, disease level, and solution data; users who can diagnose their diseases by answering questions in the application; and administrators who can process user data. The research findings are available as an application that can be used at any time to serve as a stand-in consultant for the

community, providing diagnostic results in the form of negative, positive, or strongly positive typhoid. The limitation of the study is that medical diagnostics frequently deal with noisy, high-dimensional data, which presents challenges for fuzzy logic algorithms. The diagnosis of typhoid fever requires a number of symptoms, test results, and patient history information. The complexity of creating suitable fuzzy rules and membership functions rises with the number of input variables.

Barracloug et al. (2023) present a study aimed at enhancing the accuracy of diagnosing types of malaria by incorporating feature selection strategies and parameter tuning approaches based on AI and ML classifiers into InfoGainAttributeEval. The aim is to build a method that can correctly diagnose types of malaria by leveraging AI and ML classifiers, addressing the challenges associated with traditional methods like blood smear analysis. The study uses 100 features extracted from 4000 samples related to malaria cases. These features are applied to train and assess the performance of the proposed AI system. The methodology involves integrating parameter tuning methods and feature selection techniques with AI and ML classifiers. The study evaluates the performance using ANN, NB, ensemble methods, and RF classifiers. The results indicate that the NB classifier achieved 100% accuracy within a short time, outperforming other classifiers. Additionally, the RF algorithm demonstrated high performance with 100% accuracy in classifying different types of malaria, and the Ensemble methods also achieved 100% accuracy consistently across the feature sets. The study does not explicitly discuss the interpretability or explainability of the model's decision-making process. This could be a limitation in terms of understanding how the model arrives at its diagnosis.

Apanisile and Ayeni (2023) developed an extended diagnostic system (EDS) to diagnose malaria and typhoid fever using the Naïve Bayes technique. The medical records of patients at the Lagos University teaching hospitals in Lagos State, Nigeria, were used to create a localized clinical database for observed symptoms. Two hundred and fifty (250) records with five (5) attributes, including ailment type, risk level, gender, and symptoms 1 and 2, are included in the dataset. The accuracy of true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN)

were the established metrics used to evaluate the performances of the system. Both typhoid and malaria fevers showed a highly significant improvement in the EDS's performance. A significant limitation of the study is the relatively small dataset size of 250 records. When working with large datasets, where feature independence is more likely to hold, naïve Bayes classifiers perform well. The model might not have enough information to fully represent the subtleties and underlying patterns linked to typhoid and malarial fever due to its small dataset. This may result in overfitting, a phenomenon in which the model learns more specific details and noise from the training set than it does broadly applicable patterns. When a model is overfitted, it becomes less able to generalize to new and unseen data, which could lead to subpar diagnostic performance when used on different patient populations or in actual clinical settings. Furthermore, a small dataset might not fully capture the range of clinical presentations, which could result in incomplete or biased conclusions.

Kandula et al. (2023) proposed a method that involves training the VGG19 algorithm on a large dataset of images that detects the presence of malaria parasites. The proposed method identified malaria-infected cells with a 95% accuracy rate, and it may improve the efficacy of malaria diagnosis, particularly in settings with limited resources and limited access to trained medical personnel. The study's main drawback is that, despite the model's high accuracy rate, differences in image quality, staining methods, and equipment between laboratories and healthcare facilities may make it difficult for it to perform well in a variety of clinical settings. In a related study, CNN, ResNet50, and VGG19 models were utilized by Dath et al. (2023) to identify the Plasmodium parasite in thick blood smear images. Compared to other methods, the experimental results show that the VGG19 model performed the best, achieving an accuracy of 98.46%. The study demonstrates how artificial intelligence can increase pathogen detection speed and accuracy, which is more efficient than manual analysis. When a model achieves a 98.46% accuracy rate, it may have overfitted the training dataset, which is a possible limitation of the study.

Chattopadhyay (2024) explored the application of ML in grading infectious diseases, focusing on Typhoid fever. The study's objective is to model how a computer can grade Typhoid fever using an ML-based approach that mirrors how novice doctors

learn from senior doctors. The data used in the study comprises 'weighted' sign symptoms and matching 'labeled' grades of synthetic cases of Typhoid fever (N = 198, respectively). Ten Machine Learning Classifiers (MLCs) were used to create ten Virtual Junior Clinicians (VJCs) and were trained based on the provided data. The methodology involved training the VJCs with the data, and Each VJC's performance was evaluated using the diagnostic metrics of F1-score, Accuracy, Precision, and Recall. Notably, RF- and DT-based Clinical-Based Support Systems (CDSS) achieved an average accuracy of 87%, surpassing human clinicians' accuracy. The study's results show that RF and DT classifiers performed well in grading Typhoid fever. The study delivers insights into choosing the right MLC algorithm for Infectious Disease diagnosis and discusses challenges in implementing MLC-based CDSS in real-world scenarios. Limitations of the study include the synthetic nature of the data used and the assumptions made in mimicking the learning process of novice doctors.

Asuquo et al. (2024) developed AHP models for differential diagnosis of febrile conditions. The study aimed to create a multi-criteria decision analysis technique for tropical febrile disease differential diagnosis. Utilizing the Open Data Kit application, data were gathered using two instruments that were verified by domain experts. From one data source, experiential knowledge was extracted from Sixty-two (62) doctors with experience in diagnosing febrile illnesses from both public and private health facilities. The second source of data came from a patient consultation tool that was meant to help doctors gather information about their patients' symptoms, record early diagnoses that included additional testing, and record the results of final diagnoses. The models were developed based on the physicians' experience and the accuracy of the differential diagnosis of febrile diseases was assessed by testing the AHP model's performance using the patients' dataset as a baseline. When comparing the results of the AHP models with the physician's suspected diagnosis, the AHP model performs slightly better. For a variety of diseases, the accuracy of the model ranged from 85.4% to 96.9%, exceeding doctors' predictions for Lassa, Dengue, and Yellow Fevers. The limitation of the study is that the AHP model may be biased and subjective due to the dataset used, and different

expert viewpoints may cause discrepancies in the weights and priorities given to different criteria and options.

Balerdi-Sarasola et al. (2024) applied ML to forecast malaria cases in passengers who had a fever. The model was developed to predict the occurrence of malaria cases among travelers who exhibit fever based on data from a multicentric prospective study of febrile travelers. Features included variables from the laboratory and the clinical and demographic domains. In a Training set, fifty-fold cross-validation was used to assess eleven machine-learning classification models. The model selected for parameter optimization and assessment in the Test set was the one with the best performance, as indicated by the Area Under the Curve (AUC). Ultimately, the features that added the most value to the reduced model were elaborated. They employed variables from laboratories, clinical settings, and demographics as features. XGBoost had the best performance out of 11 models. Six characteristics were used to produce a scaled-down model (MALrisk): consumption of chemoprophylaxis, rash, platelet count, respiratory symptoms, and Africa as a travel destination. MALrisk aided in prompt diagnosis by predicting malaria cases with 100% sensitivity and 72% specificity.

La-Ariandi et al. (2024) aim to assess the precision of the NB classifier in predicting the category of malaria based on symptoms displayed. The objective is to estimate the effectiveness of the NB algorithm in classifying types of malaria based on symptoms, aiming to assist in the diagnosis of malaria. The Darun Nahdla Capita Sharia Cooperative provided the data utilized in this study, which includes private information not used in earlier research. The dataset includes 166 data points with 10 variables from cooperative customers between 2020 and 2022. The dataset is split into testing and training sets, with 40% and 60% of the dataset devoted to each. The methodology involves using the NB classification method to predict malaria categories from symptom data. The study evaluates the model's performance using a confusion matrix, ROC curve, and measures like classification accuracy, error rate, and Area Under the Curve (AUC). The NB algorithm predicted malaria categories with a high accuracy rate of 99.8%. Evaluation metrics were reported, including an AUC of 0.999, an error rate of 0.002, and a classification accuracy of 0.998. Based

on precision, recall, and F1-score, the classification report shows that the Quartana, Tertiana, and Tropica categories were more prevalent than the Ovale category. NB can struggle with small datasets because the probability estimates can become unreliable. When there are few examples, the model may not accurately capture the underlying distribution of the data.

Machine learning is an important tool for diagnosing dengue because it provides creative ways to identify and categorize the illness early on. The prediction and classification of dengue fever have been the subject of numerous studies investigating the use of machine learning algorithms, including Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) (Khan and Raza, 2023; Gupta et al., 2023; Mayrose et al., 2023; Al-Nasar et al., 2023; Hassan et al., 2022). These algorithms have demonstrated encouraging results, with high accuracy rates in identifying dengue fever from other illnesses. Furthermore, the automated peripheral blood smear examination process, which incorporates AI and machine learning, has made it easier to identify dengue from digital microscopic images, giving medical professionals crucial assistance in accurately diagnosing the illness. In general, there is a lot of promise for improving early detection, raising treatment outcomes, and eventually saving lives with the development of machine learning-based models for dengue diagnosis.

Imianvan et al. (2011) conducted HIV diagnosis using the fuzzy cluster means system. A series of methodological and analytical decision steps were used in the study to improve the quality and significance of the clusters that were generated. Fuzzy cluster means a system for HIV diagnosis and a framework for partitioning data into disease clusters were the methods applied in the study. The proposed system eliminates the uncertainties often associated with the analysis of HIV test data. The machine learning approach improves the meaning and quality of diagnosis clusters, which was a new insight. The study's sensitivity to membership function design poses a limitation that may compromise the robustness and dependability of fuzzy classifiers in clinical settings.

Taylor et al. (2018) proposed a model for predicting urinary tract infections based on a single-center, multi-site, retrospective cohort analysis of 80,387 adults with

symptoms and urine culture results. Six machine learning algorithms were used to develop the models for UTI prediction based on demographic data, vital signs, lab results, prescription drugs, past medical history, chief complaint, and organized findings from the physical and history exams. Both the complete set of 211 variables and a condensed set of 10 variables were used to create the models. The area under the curve for the machine learning models ranged from 0.826 to 0.904, and the best algorithm for both full and reduced models was XGBoost. When compared to the provider judgment proxy of UTI diagnosis OR antibiotic administration, the XGBoost full and reduced models showed significantly improved specificity (specificity differences of 33.3 (31.3–34.3) and 29.6 (28.5–30.6)). They also showed superior sensitivity (sensitivity differences of 38.7 (38.1–39.4) and 33.2 (32.5–33.9)) when compared to documentation of UTI diagnosis. Approximately 1 in 4 patients (4109/15855) would be reclassified from a false positive to a true negative and approximately 1 in 11 patients (1372/15855) from a false negative to a true positive in the admission and discharge cohorts using the full XGboost model. The limitation of the study is that only one febrile illness was considered.

Ozkan et al. (2018) created a model that uses symptoms from urinary tract infections to diagnose nonspecific urethritis diseases and cystitis. A UTI dataset was created by compiling the results of 59 UTI patients' final diagnoses and routine examination data. The composed UTI dataset was used to create three classification models, decision tree (DT), support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), and artificial neural network (ANN), which are commonly used in medical diagnosis systems to model the definitive diagnosis results. The developed models were evaluated using statistical measures of accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity. The accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity results of the DT, SVM, RF, and ANN models are 93.22%, 96.61%, 96.61%, 98.30%, 95.55%, 97.77%, and 95.55%, 97.77%, respectively. The limitation of the study is that only one febrile illness was considered.

Olayemi et al. (2018) proposed a machine learning approach to diagnose lower respiratory tract infections in paediatric patients. Using Java programming language, Naïve Bayes and K-nearest neighbour machine learning models were implemented using the preprocessed LRTI dataset from Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Owo in

Ondo State. Relevant attributes were extracted from the dataset. Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and precision were the metrics used to assess the models' performance. The outcomes of utilizing all features (18) in Naïve Bayes and k-nearest neighbour analysis are 94.25% and 94.43%, respectively. While k-nearest neighbour results in 94.35% accuracy with 10 features, Naïve Bayes with an information-based feature selection method shows 99.60% accuracy. Additionally, k-nearest neighbour achieves 95.40% accuracy with only six (6) features, while Naïve Bayes with the Correlation-based feature selection method displays 95.40% accuracy as well. Analytical results demonstrate that Naïve Bayes performs stronger and better than other feature selection methods when combined with information. In a similar study, Mittal et al. (2019) proposed a method based on time-frequency analysis to diagnose respiratory diseases. To train the neural networks for the classification, two features, the dominant frequency of the spectrogram and the concentration measure, were used. Both normal and abnormal respiratory sounds were used to test the method's performance. For the classification of normal and abnormal sounds, the accuracy and sensitivity of the suggested methods were 95.2% and 91.3%, respectively. For the detection of pertussis and bronchitis, the corresponding values were 88.1% and 90%. The limitation is that the studies could only address respiratory tract infections.

Caicedo-Torres et al. (2018) proposed using machine learning for the differential diagnosis of dengue and chikungunya in pediatric patients using blood test results. The algorithms used were Support Vector Machine, Logistic Regression, and CART Decision Tree classifiers. The L2 Logistic Regression model performed the best. Using Machine Learning classifiers for the differential diagnosis, gathering data from pediatric patients, performing Grid Search with Cross-Validation, and selecting L2 Logistic Regression with second-degree polynomial features as the best-performing model were all part of the methodology. A cross-validated Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC AUC) score of 0.8694 indicates that the L2 Logistic Regression model with second-degree polynomial features outperforms the other models examined. The ROC AUC score results show promise in supporting our approach for dengue and chikungunya differential diagnosis, even with a smaller

sample size and a highly unbalanced data set. The limitation of the study is that it could only diagnose two tropical diseases.

Sabara et al. (2019) proposed a dengue fever diagnosis classification model using genetic algorithms and neural networks. Data and sources from Tegal City's Kardinah Hospital and Dr. Nurhayati, a general practitioner in 2010–2015, were used in this study. The number of experimental data and 170 data with characteristics like gender, body temperature, haemoglobin, platelets, hematocrit, and diagnosis were used in this investigation. 170 records of dengue fever examinations, both infected and uninfected, provided the data for this study. To increase the accuracy of diagnosing dengue fever, a neural network method based on genetic algorithms is employed. The results indicated the use of genetic algorithms in optimization techniques, which can facilitate the process of identifying parameter values optimally and improve the accuracy of the Neural Network algorithm. As a result, medical professionals and other healthcare professionals can use the obtained model to diagnose dengue fever. The lack of accepted practices for determining parameters in neural networks and the requirement for optimization methods like genetic algorithms for parameter values constituted the limitation.

Burton et al. (2019) used artificial intelligence to lessen the amount of work involved in diagnostics while maintaining the ability to detect UTIs. In a single clinical microbiology lab serving three hospitals and community services in Bristol and Bath, UK, the urine sample screening procedure before culture was modeled. A retrospective analysis of all urine microscopy, culture, and sensitivity reports over a one-year period was utilized to compare two approaches to classification: a machine learning approach testing three algorithms (Random Forest, Neural Network, and Extreme Gradient Boosting) and a heuristic model based on a combination of white blood cell count and bacterial count while accounting for independent variables such as demographics, past urine culture results, and clinical information included with the specimen. Analysis was done on 212,554 urine reports in total. Preliminary results showed promise for machine learning algorithms, surpassing the heuristic model in terms of relative workload reduction at a classification sensitivity greater than 95%. Further examination of the classification sensitivity of subpopulations led

us to the conclusion that samples from children (11 years of age or younger) and pregnant patients need to be evaluated independently. Initially, it was looked into whether pregnant patients and kids should be excluded from the classification process, but this lessened the amount of work that was cut down. Three Extreme Gradient Boosting algorithms, each trained independently for the classification of children, pregnant patients, and all other patients, were found to be the best solution. When combined, this system allowed for a 95% sensitivity and a 41% relative workload reduction for each of the stratified patient groups. The following limitations were observed in the study. Firstly, due to its retrospective design, certain details, such as possible mislabeled samples, may not have been easily clarified. Second, the requesting clinicians supplied comparatively few clinical details. Thirdly, keeping in mind that the outcome examined was not clinical or therapeutic, but rather a predictability of culture.

Chen et al. (2020) presented a computer-aided diagnostic scheme for the chest X-ray images of several common pulmonary diseases in children. The research employed two primary methodologies: firstly, a YOLOv3 architecture-based model was trained to automatically crop the lung field's appropriate location; secondly, three distinct multi-classification strategies were compared and evaluated, namely: one-versus-one, one-versus-all, and convolutional neural network-based classifier model training. Of these three approaches, the one-versus-one scheme presented the best results. Additionally, it could determine with 92.47% accuracy if a chest X-ray image is abnormal, and with 71.94%, 72.19%, 85.42%, 85.71%, and 80.00% accuracy, respectively, if the image shows bronchiolitis/bronchitis, bronchopneumonia, lobar pneumonia, pneumothorax, or normal. Additionally, the study offered a deep learning-based computer-aided diagnostic plan for common paediatric pulmonary illnesses. In addition to helping to review the chest X-ray images that clinicians interpret and possibly reminding them of potential negligence, this scheme was primarily helpful in screening children for normal versus lower respiratory problems.

Paraschiv and Rotaru (2020) proposed machine learning techniques based on wearable technology to diagnose respiratory disorders. Scientific Challenge: Respiratory Sound Database for Biomedical and Health Informatics (ICBHI' 17).

The process involved classifying the database by computing a Convolutional Neural Network and extracting features using Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC). The suggested method, according to the results, has an accuracy of 90.21%, making it a suitable way to quickly classify any respiratory sounds that have been collected from various devices. The limitation of the study is the shortage of medical specialists who can correctly diagnose patients based only on respiratory sounds.

Vaid et al. (2020) developed machine learning models based on patient characteristics at admission to forecast the patients' hospital courses over clinically meaningful time horizons. Their analysis involved looking through the electronic health records (EHRs) of patients who were admitted to hospitals within the Mount Sinai Health System in New York City after testing positive for COVID-19. To predict in-hospital mortality and critical events at time windows of 3, 5, 7, and 10 days from admission, Extreme Gradient Boosting was employed along with baseline comparator models. Harmonized electronic health record data for 4098 COVID-19-positive patients admitted between March 15 and May 22, 2020, from five hospitals in New York City, comprised our study population. Before or on May 1, the models were externally validated on patients from four other hospitals ($n = 2201$) before or on May 1, and then prospectively validated on all patients ($n = 383$) after May 1. The models were initially trained on patients from a single hospital ($n = 1514$). The study determined the interpretability of the model to determine and prioritize the variables that influence model predictions. With an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) for mortality of 0.89 at 3 days, 0.85 at 5 and 7 days, and 0.84 at 10 days, the XGBoost classifier outperformed baseline models after cross-validation. Critical event prediction was another area where XGBoost excelled, with an AUC-ROC of 0.80 at 3 days, 0.79 at 5 days, 0.80 at 7 days, and 0.81 at 10 days reported. During the external validation, XGBoost was able to predict mortality with an AUC-ROC of 0.88 at 3 days, 0.86 at 5 days, 0.86 at 7 days, and 0.84 at 10 days. AUC-ROC values of 0.78 at 3 days, 0.79 at 5 days, 0.80 at 7 days, and 0.81 at 10 days were also attained by the unimputed XGBoost model. Performance trends on future validation sets were comparable. The strongest predictors of critical events at 7 days were acute kidney injury at admission, elevated LDH, tachypnea, and

hyperglycemia; the strongest predictors of mortality were older age, anion gap, and C-reactive protein. Machine learning models for mortality and critical events for patients with COVID-19 at various time horizons were trained and validated by the study. These models found underlying relationships that predicted outcomes and identified at-risk patients.

Hu et al. (2021) used a machine learning technique to forecast early patient outcomes for those with severe COVID-19 infection. The predictive models were developed using a dataset of 183 patients from the Sino-French New City Branch of Tongji Hospital, Wuhan, who had a severe COVID-19 infection (115 survivors and 68 non-survivors). The features were chosen and the patient outcomes were predicted using machine learning techniques. The performance of the models was compared using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC). The model was validated using 64 patients from the Optical Valley Branch of Tongji Hospital in Wuhan who had severe COVID-19 infection. Between the survivors and non-survivors, there were notable differences in the baseline traits and laboratory tests. All five models selected four variables: age, lymphocyte count, d-dimer level, and high-sensitivity C-reactive protein level. Because of its ease of interpretation and simplicity, the logistic regression model was chosen as the final predictive model, despite the models performing similarly. The external validation sets' AUROCs were 0.881. Using a 50% chance of death as the cutoff, the validation set's sensitivity and specificity were 0.839 and 0.794, respectively. The mortality risk can be evaluated using a risk score that is based on the variables that have been chosen. The COVID-19 patients' age, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein level, lymphocyte count, and d-dimer level at admission are predictive of their prognosis.

Mutai et al. (2021) proposed machine learning techniques to determine HIV predictors in sub-Saharan Africa. XGBoost, k-Nearest Neighbors, Elastic Net (EN), RandomForest, Support Vector Machine, and Light Gradient Boosting (LGBT) algorithms were used in training and validating the data. Using population-based HIV Impact Assessment (PHIA) data for 41,939 male and 45,105 female respondents with 30 and 40 variables, respectively, from four sub-Saharan countries, machine learning techniques were used to build models. 80% of the data was used for

algorithm training and validation, with the remaining 20% being used for testing. By using the XGBoost algorithm, the f1 scoring mean for males and females was 92% and 90%, respectively, higher than the other five algorithms, suggesting a significant improvement in HIV positivity identification. The model's validity was one of the study's limitations. The training data may have been impacted by the high level of missingness and inconsistency from the self-reported data.

Osamor and Okezie (2021) use an extended weighted voting ensemble method to develop a predictive model that would aid in tuberculosis diagnosis. The classification model was created using a combination of Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine classifiers. The NCBI GEO site provided a dataset on tuberculosis gene expression, which included 48,803 genes compared to 498 samples. These samples were divided and categorized into 395 samples for other diseases and 103 samples for patients with PTB (Active TB). After removing duplicate genes, there were 25,159 genes left, which were utilized for feature selection and dimensionality calculations. The transcriptional signatures were derived from gene expression data, which was utilized in the developed model. Eighty percent of the dataset was used to train the model, and the remaining twenty percent was used to test the model's accuracy. An enhanced weighted voting ensemble method was employed to complete the model development and enhance the classification accuracy of the individual classifier. This resulted in an accuracy of 0.95, which was higher than the accuracies obtained from the single classifiers. The model was developed using two classifiers, NB and SVM. This suggests that applying ensemble techniques enhances the accuracy of a classification model created by combining individual classifiers. The limitation of the study was that it could only diagnose one febrile illness.

Nguyen et al. (2022) proposed a way to diagnose tuberculosis on X-ray images (CXR) automatically using the graph neural network approach. Due to the serious consequences of tuberculosis on patient health and the disease's quick spread, early screening for the illness is vital. Because of their affordability and ease of use, chest X-ray images are frequently utilized as resources for clinical diagnosis of tuberculosis. Machine learning is currently being used in research on Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems to give physicians analytical, diagnostic, and

disease-monitoring tools. Recent years have seen an increase in the use of graph neural networks (GNNs), which provide perfect accuracy in a wide range of fields. The CRX dataset was divided into two categories by us: TB and non-TB. With the suggested model, the study's results were encouraging: accuracy 99.33%, recall 99.07%, precision 99.63%, f1-score 99.35%, and AUC 99.97%. The limitation of the study was that it could only diagnose one febrile illness.

Rahhal et al. (2022) used a publicly available symptoms dataset and a machine learning approach to differentiate COVID-19 from other upper respiratory tract infections. They then used Apriori algorithms to identify the most significant relationships between the symptoms. A total of six classifying algorithms, Bagging, Random Forest, Extra Trees, Ada Boost, Stochastic gradient boosting, and voting ensemble, were employed to infer the disease type from its symptoms. According to the experiments, the voting ensemble algorithm (approximately 96.22%) had the highest classification testing accuracy. The study showed, in its conclusion, that the application of an ensemble technique may significantly improve classification accuracy and facilitate the differentiation of COVID-19 from other similar diseases. The limitation of the study was that it could only distinguish COVID-19 from other upper respiratory tract infections.

Orjuela-Cañón et al. (2022) proposed machine learning in the loop for tuberculosis diagnosis. Data were gathered at Hospital Santa Clara (HSC) in Bogotá, D.C., Colombia, as part of the TB programme. The data was gathered using the hospital's conventional tuberculosis diagnosis procedure. Data from 233 clinically suspected pulmonary tuberculosis subjects were taken into consideration. These subjects' data had been collected between January 2017 and December 2019. Following the national protocol to diagnose tuberculosis, 184 subjects (79%) had their TB confirmed, and 36 subjects (15%) were found to be disease-free based on smear microscopy, culture, and molecular examination. Thirteen subjects were excluded from consideration due to the lack of information regarding their TB status. The five machine learning models that were employed in the study were artificial neural networks, random forests, logistic regression, and classification trees. The findings demonstrated that artificial neural networks achieve the highest accuracy and

sensitivity values, at 0.80 and 0.82, respectively. These findings are superior to smear microscopy, a method that is frequently employed to identify tuberculosis in specific situations. Results show that machine learning in the tuberculosis diagnosis loop can be strengthened with accessible data to function as a substitute diagnosis tool based on data processing in locations with limited health infrastructure. One of the study's limitations is that the data set had a high incidence of tuberculosis, which may have caused bias in the data analysis. To address this, more detailed scenarios involving clinical observation will be needed. In certain instances, TB culture is also regarded as the gold standard for diagnosis, particularly in situations where GenExpert's infrastructure is unavailable.

Kaur et al. (2022) proposed a model to predict a patient's dengue fever infection levels by identifying dengue hemorrhagic fever, dengue shock syndrome, and dengue fever. A machine-learning-based tertiary classification technique was employed to determine which group of dengue infections the patient has by collecting and analyzing data, predicting the presence of dengue infections, and estimating risk levels. The system worked in real-time to diagnose patients based on symptomatic and clinical investigations. The patient was warned to seek medical attention in the event of an emergency related to the disease, employing warning indicators that alert them to the possibility of internal bleeding. Based on the World Health Organization's classification system, which includes dengue fever, dengue hemorrhagic fever, and dengue shock syndrome, the suggested model forecasts a patient's infection levels with a notably high accuracy of over 90% as well as high sensitivity and specificity values. The limitation of the study was that it could only predict dengue fever.

Abdualgalil et al. (2022) proposed a dengue prediction system to assist doctors in accurately predicting dengue disease. The main goal of this work was to use Efficient Machine Learning Techniques (EMLT) to develop a diagnostic model for the early diagnosis of dengue disease. EMLT-based prediction models for dengue fever were proposed which included five distinct and effective machine learning models: eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), Extra Tree Classifier (ETC), Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC), K-Nearest Neighbour, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM). The dataset was used to train and evaluate each classifier using the 10-

Fold Cross-Validation and Holdout Cross-Validation techniques. Different metrics, including accuracy, F1-score, recall, precision, AUC, and operating time, were used to assess each model on a test set. According to the results, the ETC model had the best accuracy in 10-fold cross-validation and hold-out, scoring 99.03% and 99.12%, respectively. The finding showed that ETC, which achieved 99.12% accuracy, was the best classifier with high accuracy using the Holdout cross-validation approach. The lengthy time it took for clinical examinations to provide an accurate diagnosis of dengue was the limitation and the requirement for a new diagnostic framework to identify dengue early.

Rana et al. (2022) proposed a dengue fever expert system using machine learning analytics (DFES-MLA) to predict dengue fever disease more efficiently considering only the symptomatic features. The study employed Decision Tree and Random Forest (RF) classifiers along with all the data pre-processing steps for Dengue Fever prediction. Fever, joint pain, headaches, vomiting, and other symptoms are typical of dengue; however, if the disease is not identified in time, it can cause severe bleeding, shock, and even death. SMOTE, Borderline SMOTE, ADASYN, Gaussian SMOTE, Decision Tree, and Random Forest classifiers were the methods applied in the study. The dengue dataset's imbalance and the requirement for oversampling techniques to address class imbalance constituted the study's limitations.

Veena et al. (2022) proposed a multilabel classification and clinical data analysis for dengue fever prediction. Real patient data with one target value and eighteen attributes were used in the research project, and it was gathered from the General Medicine Department at PESIMSR, Kuppam, Andrapradesh. From January 2020 to June 2021, a total of eighteen months were dedicated to gathering data. The proposed model used the Random Forest with Gridsearch algorithm to tune the hyperparameters for the grid search approach for the prediction to diagnose the class or level of dengue fever. To address the issue of model bias, the 10-fold cross-validation technique was utilized and the accuracy of classification was positively impacted by hyperparameter tuning. Accuracy, precision, recall, and f1 score are performance metrics that were used in the analysis to compare the suggested model with other machine learning models. The experimental analysis shows that for the

training and testing datasets, the RF using GridsearchCV achieved 100% and 98.79% accuracy, respectively.

In a related study, a method using supervised machine learning and the influence of seasonality was proposed by Ming et al. (2022) for diagnosing dengue in patients presenting with acute febrile illness. The study presented a supervised machine learning model to determine if dengue or other febrile illnesses (OFI) were diagnosed in patients suffering from acute febrile illnesses, and also examined the impact of seasonality on model performance over time. 8,100 patients were enrolled in the study between October 16, 2010, and December 10, 2014, and 2,240 (27.7%) patients were diagnosed with dengue infection. The enrolled patients had been sick for less than 72 hours with an acute febrile illness. The final diagnosis was predicted using a gradient boosting model (XGBoost) utilizing enrollment-related data on age, sex, hemoglobin, platelet, white blood cell, and lymphocyte counts. Eighty percent of the data were randomly divided into a hold-out set and a training set. The latter was not used in the development of the model. In predicting the final diagnosis, the optimized model derived from training data had an overall median area under the receiver operator curve (AUROC) of 0.86 (interquartile range 0.84–0.86), specificity of 0.92, sensitivity of 0.56, positive predictive value (NPV) of 0.73, negative predictive value (NPV) of 0.84, and Brier score of 0.13. One of the study's limitations is that seasonality and other factors caused the model's performance to fluctuate over time.

Hassan et al. (2022) used deep learning and spectroscopic images to develop a model for diagnosing dengue virus infection. 2,000 Raman spectra images were used which 1,200 were human blood sera samples infected with DENV, and 800 were of healthy individuals. The methods used were deep learning and Raman spectroscopy. By using Raman spectroscopic data from human blood sera, the ResNet101 deep learning model is altered by utilizing the transfer learning (TL) concept. With testing data, the system provided 96.0% accuracy in diagnosing DENV infection. Furthermore, compared to other state-of-the-art methods, the developed approach showed a minimum improvement of 6.0% and 7.0% in terms of AUC and Kappa index, respectively. The developed method's sole limitation was that it needs skilled

personnel to obtain Raman spectra and feed them to the DENV-TLDNN for diagnosis.

Gupta et al. (2023) proposed a diagnosis and prediction model for dengue fever using sentiment analysis and machine learning methods since dengue is a major global health risk. Artificial Neural Network, Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, K-nearest Neighbour, and support vector machine were utilized in the study. Bayesian inferences and support vector machine algorithms were employed in the study to mine viewpoints and extract emotions from text. Even though the results produced by the DT., KNN, SVM, and GNB methods are all better, the R.F. method takes a lot longer to compute because it produces better results. It seems that the R.F. technique is the best option based on the results. Because of this, it has been found that the RF-based diagnostic model is the most suitable for correctly diagnosing dengue fever at an early stage among all of these different machine learning algorithms. These techniques are weak miners of sentiment at the level of the sentence or phrase, and they only function well when the text passage inputs are at the page or paragraph level. They are also weak semantically.

Khan and Raza (2023) developed and assessed a Machine Learning-Based Predictive Diagnostic System to identify dengue fever early and classify different forms of dengue fever using machine learning algorithms (Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naive Bayes algorithms). The proposed system was intended to help novice or untrained staff learn and experiment more effectively, as well as aid medical professionals in identifying the disease at an early stage. The 400 records in the dataset used for this study included 15 attributes, and the data was pre-processed to lower noise, incompleteness, and inconsistencies. An accuracy of 95.6% was attained on average by the proposed system, and the highest individual accuracy was recorded by Random Forest, at 98%. The dataset used in the study was limited to 400 records and when compared to other algorithms, Naive Bayes produced lower accuracy.

Ramakrishna and Karthikeyan (2023) proposed an Artificial Neural Network-based diagnostic model that uses the Updated Chimp optimization algorithm (UChOA) to detect and predict dengue virus infection. The study used an Updated Chimp Optimization Algorithm-Artificial Neural Network (UChOA-ANN) based

diagnostic model to effectively identify dengue-affected blood samples. The ideal weight parameters for an ANN were chosen using UChOA to enhance its performance. According to the findings, the suggested diagnostic model had reached its highest levels of accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity at 94%, 96%, and 92%, respectively. In terms of sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, PPV, NPV, FPR, FNR, and FDR, the suggested diagnostic model has performed better than alternative techniques for identifying blood samples affected by dengue. The study's limitation was the need for lengthy clinical exams to provide an accurate diagnosis.

2.4 Knowledge Gap

The existing study discussed in this thesis employed AHP-based models to support the diagnosis of febrile diseases. While this method offered a structured decision-making framework, it was limited to patients over the age of 17 and lacked interpretability of the diagnostic results. This limitation reduces its usefulness in various clinical settings where transparent and explainable outcomes are essential for both healthcare providers and patients. Furthermore, the broader body of related literature reviewed has demonstrated the application of machine learning, XAI, or LLMs in various healthcare settings. However, none of these studies have used an integrated framework that combines machine learning for prediction, XAI for interpretability, and LLMs for better reasoning and explanation in diagnosing febrile diseases. This lack of integration highlights a significant gap, as the complexity and overlapping symptoms of febrile illnesses require not only accurate predictions but also transparent, explainable, and context-aware diagnostic support systems. Addressing this gap is essential for advancing healthcare technology by creating reliable and interpretable diagnostic models that can be used across diverse patient populations, ultimately enhancing trust, adoption, and outcomes in diagnosing febrile diseases.

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 Method Adopted in the Study

The study adopted Agile Development and Data-Driven methods to ensure the creation of a robust and user-friendly diagnostic system. Agile development was chosen because it is user-centric, supports incremental delivery, communication, and collaboration, and is well known for its flexibility and adaptability in system development. Data-driven methodologies were selected because they support evidence-based decision-making and improvement through continuous data collection and analysis for constant enhancement and validation of the study's diagnostic model. Machine learning (ML), Explainable AI (XAI), and Natural Language Processing (NLP) are the specific data-driven methods used in this study. The ML method was used to develop a diagnostic app from trained models on labeled data, which consists of patients' symptoms and diseases, to diagnose tropical diseases. The XAI method used was Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME). LIME visualizations were utilized to provide a more understandable, trustworthy, and transparent ML model that will facilitate the adoption of the enhanced diagnostic system in healthcare. The NLP method known as Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) was also utilized to provide contextual explanations of diagnostic information, thus further explaining the diagnostic outcomes in natural language. The Unified Modeling Language (UML) tools were used in this study to aid in the modeling, designing, and communication of the enhanced diagnostic system. These UML tools helped produce a reliable, effective, and user-focused system by guaranteeing an Agile framework and a structured yet adaptable approach to creating a machine learning-based diagnostic app.

3.2 Analysis of the Existing System

The existing system is Febra Diagnostica (Obot et al, 2023a). It uses analytic hierarchy process (AHP)-based MCDA models to diagnose and treat eleven tropical febrile diseases. The Canadian New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF) funded the study, which promotes high-risk/high-reward, transformative, and world-leading

international research. The app was the outcome of extensive research by a group of computer scientists, doctors, nurses, and community health workers from Nigeria, Canada, the United States of America, and the United Kingdom. Febra app is one of the first medical diagnosis applications that uses the MCDA model, based on the mining of the experiential knowledge of physicians who are experts in the diagnosis of tropical diseases, and real-life patient data, which was used in testing the models for accuracy and precision.

Agile software development methodology was used in the development of the application, emphasizing iterative user involvement. The specific objectives of the study were to: a) obtain experiential knowledge of medical experts in the diagnosis of febrile diseases; b) apply software engineering methodology in the design of an app for differential diagnosis of febrile diseases by CHWs; c) develop and validate an AHP-based MCDA model for the differential diagnosis and d) develop functional graphic user interfaces in collaboration with the CHWs who are the eventual users of the app. The architecture of the system included diagnosis and treatment, medical experts, patients, a diagnostic system with its sub-components (AHP diagnostic engine, decision support filters), a user interface, and a knowledge base. The AHP diagnostic engines differentiate between the symptoms of febrile illnesses and help identify the suspected illnesses based on the patient's symptoms and risk factors, allowing for the most appropriate course of treatment to be suggested. The system computed the occurrence of each febrile disease from the aggregate diagnostic factor index (ADFI) based on the linguistic score of its symptoms and the weighted Eigenvector generated from the AHP process. The outcome of the study was to help CHWs and less experienced physicians, in the differential diagnosis of tropical febrile diseases and also to increase access as well as early and accurate diagnosis of these diseases by providing the ability for CHWs to carry out basic patient consultation and diagnosis, thus reducing mortality rates.

3.2.1 Architecture of the Existing System

The architecture of the existing system comprises the medical experts in the domain of diagnosis of febrile diseases; patients; a user interface; a knowledge base that contains extracted experiential knowledge from the medical expert; and a diagnostic

system with its sub-components (decision support filters and AHP diagnostic engine). The decision support filters employ the knowledge base's contents to mimic the actions of a skilled physician, utilizing the AHP diagnostic engines to identify the relevant individual febrile disease model(s) for additional examination. The linear consensus models in the AHP diagnostic engines determine which disease the decision support filters should trigger. The AHP diagnostic models comprise eleven (11) engines for diagnosing eleven tropical febrile diseases namely: malaria, enteric fever, HIV and AIDS, upper urinary tract infection, lower urinary tract infection, upper respiratory tract infection, lower upper respiratory tract infection, tuberculosis, dengue fever, yellow fever, and lassa fever. The diagnostic engines help differentiate between the symptoms of febrile illnesses and make it easier to identify the suspected illness based on the patient's symptoms and risk factors to recommend the best course of action. To make timely and accurate healthcare decisions regarding medical advice and treatment, the CHW can also view the system's predicted diagnosis on the user interface as presented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Architecture of the Existing System
Source: Obot et al. (2023a)

3.2.2 Constraints of the Existing System

- i. **Limited Age Range:** Only patients older than seventeen (17) were considered by the existing system. A significant portion of the population was left out by this restriction, particularly children who are susceptible to these febrile illnesses. The system's applicability and usefulness are thus limited because it cannot be used to diagnose these diseases in younger patients.
- ii. **Lack of Interpretability and Explainability:** Physicians and medical experts find it difficult to comprehend the reasoning behind diagnostic results due to the limited insight into how conclusions are reached in the AHP-based diagnostic models. This "black-box" nature undermines trust because medical experts find it challenging to understand and validate the decision-making process. Consequently, the lack of transparent and data-driven explanations hampers acceptance and integration into clinical workflows, as practitioners require clear, evidence-based justifications to confidently rely on any diagnostic tool.

3.3 Analysis of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

The enhanced diagnostic system is a mobile-based application designed with a user-friendly interface to aid healthcare workers in diagnosing febrile diseases, particularly in resource-scarce environments. This system integrates ML, XAI, and LLM techniques to enhance explainability, transparency, and user trust. The key features and operation of the system include:

- i. **ML-Based Disease Diagnosis:** The system operates by analyzing patient symptoms using a trained ML model (Random Forest). Once a healthcare worker inputs patient symptoms, the system uses this algorithm to generate a provisional diagnosis by predicting the most likely febrile disease based on the symptom patterns.
- ii. **XAI Integration for Enhanced Transparency:** After generating a diagnosis, the system utilizes an XAI method (LIME) to break down and explain how the ML model arrived at its decision. This process provides healthcare workers with an easy-to-understand explanation of the factors that influenced

the diagnosis, allowing them to see which symptoms contributed most to the result. This transparency helps the healthcare worker assess the credibility of the diagnosis in real time.

iii. **Natural Language Interpretation via LLM (GPT):** To further enhance the interpretability of the diagnosis, the system employs GPT to translate complex technical outputs into plain language. The LLM summarizes the diagnosis and XAI explanations into a natural language report that healthcare workers can easily understand and share with patients, improving communication and decision-making during patient consultations.

iv. **User Roles and Interaction Flow:**

Healthcare Worker: The healthcare worker logs in to the system and can register new patients, access medical histories, and update patient records. During consultations, they input patient symptoms, vital signs, and medical history, which the system uses to generate a diagnosis. The healthcare worker can review both the diagnosis and its explanation, using this information to inform their medical decisions.

Patient: Patients can log in after being registered by a healthcare worker. They can view their summarized medical history, update personal records, and request more detailed information. This access empowers patients to manage their health information.

Admin: The system admin manages user accounts, configures system settings, monitors the overall performance, and ensures data backups and log management to maintain system integrity and security.

v. **Mobile App Interaction:** Through a mobile application, healthcare workers can access the system's diagnostic tools and patient records from remote locations. They can input patient symptoms and receive real-time feedback, which is especially useful in areas with limited healthcare infrastructure. The app's interface allows healthcare workers to navigate easily, input data using sliders for symptom severity, and view results instantly, making the system practical in low-resource settings.

vi. **Provisional Diagnosis Process:** Upon receiving symptom data, the system computes a provisional diagnosis by comparing the patient's inputs with the

trained ML model's internal representations. This diagnosis is then sent back to the healthcare worker for further review, who may use it alongside their clinical judgment to decide on treatment or further tests.

- vii. **Front-End (Mobile Application):** The mobile application serves as the primary interface for healthcare workers and patients, each with distinct roles. For healthcare workers, the system presents a tailored dashboard where they can register new patients, view and update medical history, record symptoms, and access diagnostic results. Patients interact with the system via a simplified interface, where they can update personal information, request medical history, and view diagnostic summaries. The system operates by allowing users to input symptoms using intuitive sliders, enabling quick data entry. Once symptoms are submitted, the interface provides real-time feedback, presenting provisional diagnoses and visual explanations in an easy-to-read format, streamlining the diagnosis workflow.
- viii. **Back-End (ML, XAI, and LLM Processing):** The system's back-end manages the flow of data between the mobile application and the ML model. When symptoms are entered by a healthcare worker or patient, the system sends this input to the RF model, which processes the data to generate a diagnosis. The LIME tool then analyzes the model's predictions to generate visual explanations, helping the healthcare worker understand how the system arrived at its conclusions. The GPT further processes this output to provide natural language explanations, converting complex diagnostic results into simple, understandable summaries. This operation ensures that healthcare professionals can comprehend the results with ease, improving trust and usability.
- ix. **Database and Storage:** The system stores all data (patient records, medical history, symptom inputs, diagnostic results, and system logs) in a secure, cloud-based database. The operation of the database is designed to ensure the efficient retrieval and updating of records in real time, allowing healthcare workers to access patient information instantly. Additionally, the system is configured to automatically back up data at scheduled intervals, ensuring that patient information is protected from accidental loss or system failure. When

new data is entered or modified, it is immediately saved to the cloud, keeping the system up-to-date and synchronized across all users.

- x. **Security and User Management:** The security and user management of the diagnostic system are enforced through a combination of multi-factor authentication (MFA), role-based access control (RBAC), and encryption. Users (patients, healthcare workers, and admins) access the system via a mobile app, with MFA ensuring that only authorized individuals can log in. RBAC further restricts access based on user roles: patients can only view and edit their personal records, healthcare workers manage patient data and diagnoses, and admins oversee system functions. All communication between the app and the cloud-based web service (hosted on PythonAnywhere) is secured with Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS)/Transport Layer Security (TLS) encryption, and sensitive data stored in the MySQL database is protected using AES-256 encryption. Regular backups and audit logs are maintained to ensure data integrity and monitor system activity for security and compliance.

3.3.1 Justification of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

The enhanced diagnostic system addresses the limitations of the existing system by significantly expanding the age range of patients it can diagnose as well as improving interpretability and transparency.

The enhanced diagnostic system expands its diagnostic capabilities to include patients from 4 years of age and above, in contrast to the existing system, which is limited to diagnosing patients over the age of 17. This broader age range allows a more inclusive diagnosis, which benefits a greater proportion of the population, and improves early diagnoses and treatment outcomes.

Healthcare providers find it challenging to comprehend and trust the diagnostic process due to the existing system's dependence on the Analytic Hierarchy Process, which lacks interpretability. However, the enhanced diagnostic system makes use of ML techniques to improve the precision of diagnoses. It also integrates XAI and LLMs techniques to offer comprehensible explanations of the diagnostic results.

Through these explanations, medical professionals are better able to build trust by understanding the underlying causes of each diagnosis.

The enhanced diagnostic system is a more efficient and reliable tool for febrile disease diagnoses because of its dual improvements in age inclusivity and diagnostic clarity.

3.4 System Model

The enhanced diagnostic system accepts patient personal data, symptoms, and vitals through a mobile device. The local and cloud storage holds the patient data and models' outputs. The ML model processes the patient's symptoms to diagnose the febrile disease or diseases, the XAI model interprets the results of the ML model while the LLM processes the patient's symptoms, and the XAI explanations to generate natural language explanations for easier decision-making as presented in Figure 3.2. This user-friendly application guarantees accessibility and offers clear explanations with the combination of these models to capture comprehensive diagnostic indicators. This system outperforms the current AHP-based system and extends applicability to a wider range of age groups by providing a scalable, interpretable diagnostic tool. The enhanced diagnostic system architecture; the high-level input design; the high-level process design, the high-level output design, and the database design are presented to provide an overview of the whole system.

Figure 3.2: Enhanced Diagnostic System Model

3.4.1 Architecture of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

In the enhanced diagnostic system, the components of the system and their interrelationships are structured. The components comprise medical experts from which patient data were collected, data Preprocessing, diagnostic system, model evaluation, healthcare provider, the patient, the mobile device, and the cloud storage, as illustrated in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Architecture of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

3.4.1.1 Mobile Device

The Android-based mobile device serves as the interface between healthcare providers, patients, admin, and the diagnostic system. The mobile device is used by healthcare providers to input patient data such as personal information, patient vitals, and symptoms and receive output such as provisional diagnosis, patient medical record patient history overview, vital signs summary, user management report, and recommendations to healthcare providers as shown in Figure 3.4. The mobile device provides a user-friendly interface for users to enter information, and access the cloud-based system, and serves as the access point for the diagnostic and decision support functionalities.

Figure 3.4: Mobile device of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

3.4.1.2 Decision Filter

The decision filter mimics a skilled physician's reasoning by appropriately grouping patient vitals and symptoms for diagnostic decisions. The decision filter identifies critical symptoms and ensures that all relevant factors have been considered before finalizing a diagnosis. The input data into the decision filter are personal information, vitals, and symptoms, while the output data are diagnoses and additional recommendations. A flow chart of the decision filter is presented in Figure 3.5, which presents the steps followed by the filter to send appropriate information to the database as well as the diagnostic system for decision-making.

3.4.1.3 Diagnosis and Recommended Treatment

The diagnosis and recommended treatment component provides healthcare workers with the patient's diagnosis from the diagnostic system, which comprises the RF diagnosis, LIME interpretation, further explanations by the GPT engine, and recommended treatment. This component holds the diagnostic results from the diagnostic system, patient vitals, and additional recommendations from the decision filter. The recommendation is aligned with medical guidelines and is tailored based on the patient's history.

Figure 3.5: A flowchart of the decision filter

3.4.1.4 Cloud Storage

The cloud storage holds patient data, model data, diagnostic results, and other system records. It ensures that patient data is stored securely and can be accessed as needed. The application programming interface (API) is the bridge between the enhanced diagnostic app and the cloud architecture, allowing the app to send and retrieve data from the cloud storage, invoke ML models, and receive diagnostic results. The API handles secure data transmission, ensuring privacy and compliance with regulations as shown in Figure 3.6. The API forwards personal information, vitals, and symptoms to the cloud storage service which are saved securely and organized into different tables depending on the type. After the model completes the diagnosis, the evaluation metrics and the diagnostic results are also sent to the cloud storage via the API to keep track of versions and for future reference.

Figure 3.6: Diagram of the cloud storage

3.4.1.5 Patient

The patient is the source of all medical data, such as symptoms, vitals, and health records. Patients provide symptoms, vitals, and medical history to a healthcare worker for entry into the system using a mobile device. The patient has limited functions, including editing their personal record, viewing medical history summary, and requesting detailed medical records from the healthcare worker. The patient played a key role as one of the end users who provided essential feedback on the system's usability, accessibility, and relevance. Although not directly involved in the development process, patients participated in user interviews, usability testing, and

feedback sessions after system iterations. Their input helped the team understand how the system meets real-world requirements such as ease of use. Their continuous feedback loop is crucial in building a user-centric system that is intuitive and beneficial for the target audience.

3.4.1.6 Healthcare Worker

The healthcare worker interacts directly with the system to input personal information, patient history, and examination, including temperature, blood pressure, respiratory rate, height, weight, and symptoms from the patient through the user-friendly interface of the app. The healthcare worker can then interpret and act on the diagnostic results and recommendations from the app for decision-making. The healthcare worker served as a key user and stakeholder who provided valuable insights into the clinical workflows and practical application of the system. They collaborated with the development team to define user stories, ensuring that the system accurately reflects the real-world tasks and challenges they encounter in patient care. The healthcare worker helped validate features such as data input processes, diagnosis generation, and recommendations by offering feedback on their efficiency and usability. During sprint reviews and testing phases, they assess whether the system supports effective and accurate decision-making in a healthcare setting. Their involvement ensured the system was both clinically functional and intuitive for everyday use, bridging the gap between technical development and practical healthcare needs.

3.4.1.7 Medical Experts

The medical experts are experienced physicians in tropical febrile diseases from secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities (both public and private) who collected the patients' data from patients with febrile diseases during their clinic days. The medical experts assisted in developing the data collection instrument, identifying key symptoms, and helping define the medical rules that guide the system. They provided valuable insights and initial knowledge for the system development. Their primary responsibility was to provide expert insights into medical practices, patient care, and healthcare workflows, ensuring that the system accurately reflects real-world clinical requirements. They collaborated closely with the system developer to define user

stories, validate system requirements, and provide feedback during sprint reviews. The medical expert helped in refining diagnostic algorithms, interpreting clinical data, and ensuring that the system's outputs, such as diagnoses and recommendations, align with medical standards. They also participate in testing phases to validate that the system's functionality supports accurate, practical, and usable healthcare outcomes. By working iteratively within the agile framework, the medical expert ensures the system remains patient-centric and clinically relevant.

3.4.1.8 Data Collection

The dataset was collected from a study conducted by a group of computer scientists, doctors, nurses, and community health workers from Nigeria, Canada, the United States of America, and the United Kingdom to develop a multi-disease, multi-symptom soft-computing system for early differential diagnosis of tropical diseases by frontline health workers. This study was funded by the New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF), which promotes high-risk/high-reward, transformative, and world-leading international research, and was approved in June 2020 with application number 102232. The research involved human participants and was evaluated and granted approval by the Human Research Ethics Board (HREB) of Mount Royal University in Calgary, Alberta, Canada, and ethical clearance of the study was given by the Institutional Health Research Ethical Committee (IHREC) at the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The approval to use the dataset in this study was received from the Institute of Health Research and Development, University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Nigeria. The dataset contains 4870 patient records comprising demographic data, patient symptoms, risk factors, suspected diagnoses, further investigation, and confirmed diagnoses (UNIUYO and MRU, 2024). Data exploration was needed once the data had been collected to examine the dataset's structure, types of data, size, and features. It also involved computing basic statistics for numerical data to spot trends, patterns, and outliers. The dataset showed that 4605 patient records were collected during the rainy season, 40 during harmattan, and 225 during the dry season. Table 3.1 presents the descriptive statistics of patients in the dataset, indicating that there were 2175 male and 2695 female patients.

Table 3.1 Descriptive statistics of male and female patients in the dataset

Age Range	Male	Female	Pregnant Women	No	Nursing Mothers	No
< 5years	534	419	1 st trimester	139	0-3 months	27
5 years to 12 years	346	323	2 nd trimester	184	4-6 months	35
13years to 19 years	150	213	3 rd trimester	86	7-9 months	28
20 years to 64 years	1012	1605			Over 9 months	63
65 years and above	133	135				
Total	2175	2695	Total	409	Total	153

The data exploration further showed the number of pregnant patients from the first to third trimester and patients who were nursing mothers and their respective months in the dataset. The dataset contained fifty (50) symptoms and eleven (11) suspected and confirmed diagnoses which are highlighted in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Patient Symptoms and Diseases in the Dataset

SN	Symptom/Disease	Abbreviation	SN	Symptom/Disease	Abbreviation
1	Abdominal pains	ABDPN	33	Muscle and body pain	MSCBDYPN
2	Back pain	BCKPN	34	Mouth ulcer	MUTUCR
3	Bitter taste in mouth	BITAIM	35	Nausea	NUS
4	Bleeding	BLDN	36	Night sweats	NGTSWT
5	Bloody urine	BLDYURN	37	Pain behind the eyes	PNBHEYE
6	Catarrh	CTRH	38	Upper back pain (loin)	UPBCKPN
7	Chest indraw	CHSIND	39	Painful urination	PNFLURNTN
8	Chest pain	CHSPN	40	Peritonitis	PERTN
9	Chills and Rigors	CHLNRI	41	Red eyes	REDEYE
10	Cloudy urine	CLDYURN	42	Red eyes, face, tongue	REDEYEFCTNG
11	Constipation	CNST	43	Sensitivity to light	SENLHT
12	Cough (initial dry)	CGHDRY	44	Shock	SHK
13	Diarrhea	DRH	45	Skin rash	SKNRSH
14	Difficulty breathing	DIFBRT	46	Sore throat	SRTRT
15	Dizziness	DIZ	47	Suprapubic pains	SPPBPN
16	Dry cough	DRYCGH	48	Urinary frequency	URNFQC
17	Fatigue	FTG	49	Vomiting	VMT
18	Fever	FVR	50	Wheezing	WHZ

19	High persistent fever	HGPSFVR	51	Malaria	MAL
20	High-grade fever	HGGDFVR	52	Typhoid fever	ENFVR
21	Stepwise rise fever	SWRFVR	53	HIV and AIDS	HVAD
22	Sudden onset fever	SUDONFVR	54	Upper urinary tract infection	UPUTI
23	Low-grade fever	LWGDFVR	55	Lower urinary tract infection	LWUTI
24	Foul breath	FOLBRT	56	Upper respiratory tract infection	URTI
25	Body itching	BDYICH	57	Lower respiratory tract infection	LRTI
26	Generalized body pain	GENBDYPN	58	Tuberculosis	TB
27	Generalized rashes	GENRSH	59	Lassa fever	LASFVR
28	Headaches	HDACH	60	Yellow fever	YELFVR
29	Intestinal bleeding and perforation	INTBLEPRF	61	Dengue fever	DENFVR
30	Joint swelling	JNTSWL			
31	Lethargy	LTG			
32	Lymph node swelling	LMPNSWL			

The patient's symptoms were presented on a five-point scale (1=absent; 2=mild; 3=moderate; 4=severe; 5=very severe) and the diagnoses on a six-point scale (1=absent; 2=very low; 3=low; 4=moderate; 5=high; 6=very high) along with the physician's level of confidence (a numerical rating scale from 1 to 10) for every symptom and disease. The sample patient dataset is presented in Table 3.3.

3.4.1.9 Data Preprocessing

Data processing is a crucial phase that entails feature selection, feature scaling, and data cleaning. Expunging records with missing features, irrelevant data, and columns that were not needed as part of the data-cleaning process. During the data cleaning process, records of patients under the age of five (5) were removed from the data because these patients could not accurately express certain symptoms, and the data collection instrument used did not make provision for certain symptoms of patients

under the age of 5. All the columns containing the confidence level selected by the physicians were deleted from the dataset since the confidence level will not be needed during the machine learning modeling process. The suspected diagnoses columns recorded by the physician were also removed from the dataset, leaving the dataset with the symptoms and confirmed diagnoses after further investigations. The haemorrhagic fevers (Lassa, yellow, and dengue fever) and their symptoms were also removed because these diseases were not considered in this study. After cleaning, the dataset was reduced to 3914 records with 32 symptoms and 8 confirmed diagnoses as presented in Table 3.4. The list of symptoms and diseases with their abbreviations is presented in Table 3.5.

Table 3.3: The Sample Patient Dataset

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	N	P	R	T	V	X	DJ	DL	DN	DP	DR	DT	DV	DX	
1	PATCON	STCON	PHICOD	PHYEXP	PHICLF	PATCOD	SEACON	PATAGE	PATSEX	PRGSTA	PATNUSV	ABDPN	BCKPN	BITAIM	BLDN	BLDYRN	CTRH	CHSIND	MAL	ENVR	HVAD	UPUTI	LWUTI	URTI	LRTI	TB
2	1	3	IM/0	5	2	IM/09/0	1	5	1	1	1	4	4	4	1	1	3	3	6	6	1	1	4	5	6	1
3	1	3	IM/09	12	1	IM/09/0	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/01	3	6	1	1	1	2	3	2	1	1	3	1	6	6	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/02	3	27	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/04	3	30	2	1	1	3	1	3	1	2	3	1	4	1	2	5	5	1	4	1
7	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/05	3	30	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	4	1	3	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	1	1	AK/06	5	1,2	AK/06/06	3	40	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	4	5	5
9	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/07	3	31	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	6	4	4	5	4	5
10	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/08	3	20	2	1	5	2	1	4	1	2	3	1	4	1	1	2	1	4	4	1
11	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/09	3	6	2	1	1	4	4	1	1	4	3	1	3	4	1	5	4	1	2	1
12	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06	3	6	2	1	1	4	4	2	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	2	3	4	2
13	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/11	3	36	2	3	3	2	3	2	1	2	3	1	4	1	1	1	4	5	5	1
14	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/12	3	23	1	2	5	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	4	2	1	3	1	1	1	1
15	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/13	3	38	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	4	1	6	2	4	5	5	4
16	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/14	3	62	1	1	1	3	3	3	4	3	2	1	3	1	1	1	5	5	1	1
17	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/15	3	41	2	4	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	3	3	1	1	4	3	1
18	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/16	3	3	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	4	4	1	1	1	4	4	1
19	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/18	3	58	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	3	1	3	4	3	5	3	4	5	2
20	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/18	1	45	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	5	3	3	4
21	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/19	1	5	2	1	1	4	2	1	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	4	1
22	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/20	1	29	2	3	5	1	3	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	1
23	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/21	1	60	2	1	1	4	2	2	2	1	2	1	3	6	1	1	1	1	1	1
24	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/22	1	47	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	4	4	1	2	3	6	3	5	2	2	5
25	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/23	1	5	2	2	5	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	5	5	1	5	4
26	1	1	AK/06	5	2	AK/06/24	1	52	2	1	1	5	1	1	3	2	2	1	2	5	2	5	5	5	5	2

Table 3.4 Pre-processed Data

	ABDPN	BITAIM	BLDYURN	CTRH	CHSIND	CHSPN	CHLNRI	CNST	CGHRY	DIFBRT	...	VMT	WHZ	MAL	ENFVR	HVAD	UPUTI	LWUTI	URTI	LRTI	TB
0	4	4	1	3	3	4	4	3	2	3	...	4	4	6	6	1	2	2	4	5	1
1	2	2	1	3	1	1	2	1	2	1	...	2	1	6	1	1	1	1	4	1	1
2	1	3	1	2	1	2	5	3	1	1	...	1	1	1	6	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	3	2	3	1	3	1	1	2	1	...	4	1	4	1	2	1	5	1	4	1
4	3	1	4	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	...	3	1	1	6	1	1	1	1	1	1
...
3909	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3910	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3911	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3912	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
3913	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

3914 rows x 40 columns

Table 3.5. Patient Symptoms and Diseases used in the Study

	Symptom/Disease	Abbreviation		Symptom/Disease	Abbreviation
1	Abdominal pains	ABDPN	20	Headaches	HDACH
2	Bitter taste in Mouth	BITAIM	21	Lethargy	LTG
3	Bloody urine	BLDYURN	22	Lymph node swelling	LMPNDSWL
4	Catarrh	CTRH	23	Muscle and body pain	MSCBDYPN
5	Chest Indraw	CHSIND	24	Mouth ulcer	MUTUCR
6	Chest pain	CHSPN	25	Nausea	NUS
7	Chills and Rigors	CHLNRI	26	Night sweats	NGTSWT
8	Constipation	CNST	27	Painful urination	PNFLURNTN
9	Cough (initial dry)	CGHRY	28	Sore throat	SRTRT
10	Difficulty breathing	DIFBRT	29	Suprapubic pains	SPPBPN
11	Dry cough	DRYCGH	30	Urinary frequency	URNFQC

12	Fatigue	FTG	31	Vomiting	VMT
13	Fever	FVR	32	Wheezing	WHZ
14	High-grade fever	HGGDFVR	33	Malaria	MAL
15	Stepwise rise fever	SWRFVR	34	Typhoid fever	ENFVR
16	Low-grade fever	LWGDFVR	35	HIV and AIDS	HVAD
17	Foul breath	FOLBRT	36	Urinary tract infection	UTI
18	Generalized body pain	GENBDYPN	37	Respiratory tract infection	RTI
19	Generalized rashes	GENRSH	38	Tuberculosis	TB

To further reduce the number of confirmed diseases to what was captured in the scope of this study (six diseases), upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) and lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI), as well as upper urinary tract infection (UPUTI) and lower urinary tract infection (LWUTI), were merged into respiratory tract infection (RTI) and urinary tract infection (UTI) respectively. Max operation also known as max function was applied to combine the two sets of severity levels into a single value. Taking the maximum value from two or more related measurements, the max operation combines severity scales with emphasis on the highest severity recorded across various metrics. Given that U and L are the severity levels of upper and lower urinary tract infections respectively, the Max Operation $M(U, L)$ can be expressed as:

$$M(U, L) = \max(U, L) \quad (3.1)$$

Where U represents the first input to the max operation while L represents the second input to the max operation. The max function returns the maximum value between U and L . This operation ensures that the combined severity level accurately represents the worst-case scenario from the two columns. When the goal is to determine which medical condition is the most severe, the Max Operation is a reliable way to combine severity scales, and the dataset after applying the Max Operation is presented in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6 Pre-processed dataset after max operation

	ABDPN	BITAIM	BLDYURN	CTRH	CHSIND	CHSPN	CHLNRI	CNST	CGHDY	DIFBRT	...	SPPBPN	URNFQC	VMT	WHZ	MAL	ENFVR	HVAD	UTI	RTI	TB
0	4	4	1	3	3	4	4	3	2	3	...	2	1	4	4	6	6	1	2	5	1
1	2	2	1	3	1	1	2	1	2	1	...	1	1	2	1	6	1	1	1	4	1
2	1	3	1	2	1	2	5	3	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	1	6	1	1	1	1
3	3	3	2	3	1	3	1	1	2	1	...	4	4	4	1	4	1	2	5	4	1
4	3	1	4	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	...	4	3	3	1	1	6	1	1	1	1
...
3909	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
3910	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
3911	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
3912	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1
3913	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1

3914 rows x 38 columns

Custom mapping was utilized to map the disease severity Absent (1) to binary 0 and very-low to very-severe (2 to 6) to binary 1 as presented in Table 3.7. A lambda function mapping the disease severity to 0 and 1 is employed, with *condition 0 if x == 1 else 1*. This approach of mapping the diseases prepares the dataset, ensuring that the disease severity is represented in a simplified, binary manner for effective machine learning model training.

Table 3.7 Pre-processed dataset after custom mapping

	ABDPN	BITAIM	BLDYURN	CTRH	CHSIND	CHSPN	CHLNRI	CNST	CGHDY	DIFBRT	...	SPPBPN	URNFQC	VMT	WHZ	MAL	ENFVR	HVAD	UTI	RTI	TB
0	4	4	1	3	3	4	4	3	2	3	...	2	1	4	4	1	1	0	1	1	0
1	2	2	1	3	1	1	2	1	2	1	...	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
2	1	3	1	2	1	2	5	3	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
3	3	3	2	3	1	3	1	1	2	1	...	4	4	4	1	1	0	1	1	1	0
4	3	1	4	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	...	4	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
...
3909	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
3910	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
3911	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
3912	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
3913	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	...	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0

3914 rows x 38 columns

3.4.1.10 Diagnostic System

This is the core engine where the actual diagnosis takes place. It comprises the ML, XAI, and LLM models, which are further explained in detail. The ML model (RF Model) is trained on pre-processed data to diagnose diseases based on the patterns of symptoms. The XAI(LIME) component explains the reasoning behind the model's diagnosis, making the results interpretable by healthcare professionals. In contrast, the LLM model (GPT) further refines the diagnosis, provides context, and suggests explanations or questions for deeper insight into the patient's condition. The diagnostic system takes input data (symptoms) and passes it through ML models to diagnose the disease. XAI explains the diagnosis, and LLMs provide additional explanations or further diagnostic suggestions.

In this study, three machine learning algorithms, namely random forest, extreme gradient boost, and multi-layer perceptron, were considered, which are explained below. The best-performing model, which was the random forest, was adopted for the diagnostic system development.

- i. **Random Forest (RF)** model used in this study takes advantage of the power of ensemble learning to deliver robust diagnoses by considering multiple decision trees. This RF model improves the diagnostic results of febrile diseases by combining the diagnoses from all trees, using several symptoms as input features. The RF model has several advantages such as its simplicity and ability to yield excellent results even without hyperparameter tuning. It builds several decision trees on various identical nodes using the patient data comprising the symptoms and diseases and the combination of the decisions of multiple decision trees as shown in Figure 3.7 to arrive at a solution which is the mean of all the decision trees.

Figure 3.7 Random Forest algorithm schematic diagram

The RF model was adopted as the main engine of this study for multi-disease diagnosis of febrile diseases. This RF model in Equation (3.2) was adopted from a consistency analysis study by Biau et al. (2012) which outlines the formulation of tree splits and their optimization in high-dimensional spaces. For each input x (representing a patient's symptoms), the goal is to diagnose a disease $\hat{y} = \hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \hat{y}_3, \hat{y}_4, \hat{y}_5, \hat{y}_6$ where $\hat{y}_i \in \{0,1\}$ indicates whether the i^{th} disease is present.

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n T_j(x) \quad (3.2)$$

where:

\hat{y}_i is the predicted label for the i^{th} disease.

$T_j(x)$ is the prediction from the j^{th} decision tree for input x .

n is the total number of trees in the forest.

In this multi-label classification, each tree will make a diagnosis for all six diseases, and the final output is the average diagnosis across all trees, which can be thresholded to determine the presence (1) or absence (0) of each disease.

- ii. **Extreme gradient boost (XGBoost)** was selected for this study because it is an ensemble technique and an advanced gradient boosting implementation that is portable, flexible, and efficient, making it a suitable option for disease diagnosis. XGBoost constructs classification trees one

at a time, using the residuals from each tree to train the next, and the schematic diagram of the computational process is shown in Figure 3.8. XGBoost makes use of regularisation techniques to improve model generalization and gradient-boosted decision trees as its foundation. It adds weak learners (decision trees) to the ensemble one after the other in a stepwise manner, with each new learner concentrating on fixing the mistakes made by the previous ones. During training, it minimizes a predetermined loss function using the gradient descent optimization technique.

Figure 3.8 Extreme gradient boosting algorithm schematic diagram

The XGBoost model in Equation (3.3) and (3.4) were adopted from a study by Chen and Guestrin (2016) which utilized gradient boosting to maximize prediction accuracy while controlling regularization.

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(x) \quad (3.3)$$

where:

\hat{y}_i is the predicted score for the i^{th} disease.

K is the number of boosting rounds (trees).

$f_k(x)$ is the contribution of the K^{th} tree in predicting the probability of disease i

Since this work is a multi-label classification task, the loss function is the combination of binary cross-entropy for each disease as presented in Equation (3.4). The symptoms are represented by the input feature space and the model generates six probability scores, each of which indicates the likelihood of a specific disease.

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^6 \sum_{j=1}^n (y_{ij} \log(\hat{y}_{ij}) + (1 - y_{ij}) \log(1 - \hat{y}_{ij})) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k) \quad (3.4)$$

where:

y_{ij} is the true label (0 or 1) for the i^{th} disease in the j^{th} patient.

\hat{y}_{ij} is the predicted probability of disease i in patient j .

$\Omega(f_k)$ is the regularization term for the tree f_k

- iii. **Multi-layered perceptron (MLP)** was selected for this study because it is an effective tool for disease diagnosis due to its versatility in managing various data types, capacity to learn from high-dimensional datasets, and ability to model complex relationships. When combined with appropriate training techniques and interpretability methods, MLPs can offer reliable and practical insights for medical diagnosis. It is a feedforward artificial neural network with multiple layers, comprising an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer as shown in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9 Multi-layered perceptron architecture

The MLP mathematical model in Equation (3.5) was adopted from a study on the formalism of the general mathematical expression of MLP neural networks by Hounmenou et al. (2021). The model comprises an input layer representing patient features(symptoms), multiple hidden layers, and an output layer with six neurons (one for each disease). Each neuron performs a weighted sum of inputs followed by a non-linear activation function ϕ and uses backpropagation to minimize a loss function.

$$h_j = \phi\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ij}x_i + b_j\right) \quad (3.5)$$

where:

h_j is the predicted probability for the j^{th} disease.

w_{ij} and b_j are the weight matrix and bias vector for the final layer

x_i is the i^{th} input symptom,

n is the number of input symptoms.

- iv. Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME)** provide interpretability locally by using a more straightforward model to approximate the behaviour of the model around a particular diagnosis. When diagnosing diseases where patient cases may differ greatly from one another, LIME is extremely helpful when generating explanations by aiding healthcare workers in comprehending why a model diagnosed a disease for a particular patient considering their unique symptoms. This localized explanation improves the diagnostic model's accuracy and reliability by helping to spot any anomalies or mistakes in the diagnosis. LIME is model-agnostic and can be used with a variety of ML models, offering versatility and wide applicability in a range of diagnostic scenarios. The LIME model in Equation (3.6) utilized in this study was adopted from a study by Saini and Prasad (2021) which proposed a novel explainable AI method to provide locally interpretable model agnostic explanations. The goal of LIME is to identify an interpretable model g that roughly corresponds to the complex model f around a given instance x .

$$L = \operatorname{argmin}_g L(f, g, \pi_x + \Omega(g)) \quad (3.6)$$

Where $L(f, g, \pi_x)$ is the loss function that measures how well the interpretable model g approximates the complex model f around the instance x . It typically considers a weighted least squares loss. π_x is a proximity measure that assigns higher weights to samples closer to x , emphasizing local behaviour. $\Omega(g)$ is a regularization term that penalizes the complexity of the interpretable model g , ensuring that it remains simple.

- v. **Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT)** greatly improves the diagnosis of febrile diseases by utilizing its strong natural language processing capabilities to evaluate and comprehend intricate medical data. When combined with an ML model, it improves the efficiency of disease diagnosis by providing thorough explanations and justifications for its recommendations, which ultimately lead to better patient outcomes. It leverages the transformer architecture which is the foundational model in natural language processing due to its ability to handle sequential data effectively. The GPT models in Equations (3.7) and (3.8) were adopted from Luo et al. (2022) and Lee (2023). The task is for GPT to generate human-readable explanations based on the predicted labels and probabilities from the ML models. The input to the GPT will be a structured prompt containing the patient's symptoms and ML model results indicating the likelihood of each disease. The goal of GPT is to generate an explanation for each predicted disease based on its probability score and the associated symptoms, incorporating medical knowledge. The GPT model will generate text conditioned on the structured input (ML predictions + symptoms). GPT predicts the next token in a sequence based on previous tokens. The sequence in this study includes: symptoms of the patient, predicted disease probabilities from ML models, and the request for explanation. For a sequence $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_N$ the model generates the next token x_{N+1} based on the probability:

$$P(x_{n+1}|x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_N) = \text{softmax}(W_0 z_{N+1}) \quad (3.7)$$

where z_{n+1} is the hidden representation at position $N + 1$.

GPT uses self-attention to capture relationships between the symptoms and the predicted disease probabilities:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (3.8)$$

where:

$Q = W_Q h$ are the queries

$K = W_K h$ are the keys

$V = W_V h$ are the values

h is the hidden state from the previous layer

W_Q , W_K , and W_V are learnable weight matrices

d_k is the dimension of the keys

Here, Q, K, and V represent the symptoms, predicted probabilities, and other relevant medical information. This allows GPT to contextualize why a certain disease was predicted, based on the input features. The prompt that is fed into GPT will be structured as a concatenation of the patient's symptoms, the disease predictions with their probabilities from the ML model, and instruction to generate an explanation. Given this prompt, GPT will use its learned medical knowledge and the context provided by the predictions to generate an interpretative explanation. For each disease, GPT will provide an explanation based on the diagnoses and symptoms.

The mathematical formulations of RF, XGBoost, and MLP provide the foundation for predictive modelling, and RF was selected as the main engine of the study while the LIME equation enhances interpretability. Including these equations in this work contextualizes their applicability to the specific problem of diagnosing febrile diseases. This research demonstrates a novel method for using GPT to generate natural language explanations of model predictions, enhancing the transparency and interpretability of machine learning models in healthcare.

3.4.1.11 Mathematical Model

The mathematical model presented in this section is independent of the specific ML, XAI, and LLM techniques. Therefore, any ML algorithm, XAI technique, and LLM can be implemented using this model.

- i. Machine Learning Model: The ML algorithm in Equation (3.9) predicts the disease \hat{y} based on input features (symptoms) $X = x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{32}$

$$\hat{y} = f_{ML}(X) = f_{ML}(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{32}) \quad (3.9)$$

where:

$X = x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{32}$ represents the input vector of 32 symptoms.

\hat{y} is the predicted disease for each possible disease.

The output of this model can be expressed as Equation (3.10):

$$O_{ML}(X) = \{P(d_1|X), P(d_2|X), \dots, P(d_k|X)\} \quad (3.10)$$

where:

O_{ML} is the output of the machine learning model

$P(d_i|X)$ is the probability of disease d_i given the symptoms X

k is the total number of diseases (in our case, $k=6$).

- ii. Explainable AI Model: The XAI model analyses how each symptom contributes to the diagnosed disease. The output in Equation (3.11) is an explanation of the diagnosis, which is importance scores for each symptom.

$$O_{XAI}(X, \hat{y}) = [c_1(X, \hat{y}), c_2(X, \hat{y}), \dots, c_{32}(X, \hat{y})] \quad (3.11)$$

where:

$O_{XAI}(X, \hat{y})$ is the output of the explanation of the diagnosis

$c_i(X, \hat{y})$ is the contribution of symptom x_i in diagnosing \hat{y}

- iii. Large Language Model: The LLM in Equation (3.12) interprets both the ML model's diagnosis and the XAI explanation and generates a natural language description

$$O_{LLM}(X) = f_{LLM}(O_{ML}(X), O_{XAI}(X, \hat{y})) \quad (3.12)$$

where $O_{LLM}(X)$ is the LLM's output that uses the ML output $O_{ML}(X)$ and the explainability output $O_{XAI}(X, \hat{y})$ to form a coherent explanation in natural language, providing healthcare workers with a clear interpretation of both the diagnosis and the reasoning behind it.

The outputs of the ML, XAI, and LLM models in Equations (3.10), (3.11), and (3.12), respectively, are combined into a single model in Equation (3.13), which can work with any ML, XAI, or LLM technique.

$$D(X) = O_{LLM}(O_{ML}(X), O_{XAI}(X, O_{ML}(X))) \quad (3.13)$$

where:

$D(X)$ is the diagnostic system interpretation in natural language.

$O_{LLM}(O_{ML}(X), O_{XAI}(X))$ is any LLM that takes the output $O_{ML}(X)$ from the ML model and the explanation $O_{XAI}(X)$ from the XAI model to generate a natural language interpretation $D(X)$.

$O_{ML}(X)$ is any ML algorithm that takes symptoms X and diagnose the disease \hat{y} .

$O_{XAI}(X, \hat{y})$ is any XAI method that explains the diagnosis \hat{y} by analysing the symptoms X and providing interpretability in terms of the contributions of each symptom.

3.4.1.12 Model Evaluation

The performance of the ML model was assessed using Recall, Precision, and F1 Score because they ensure that the model's diagnoses are accurate and reliable. Recall is important for diagnosing diseases because it shows how well the model can identify patients who truly have the condition, and a high recall rate guarantees that the majority of patients are diagnosed with the disease correctly. Precision is significant because it indicates how accurately the model made positive diagnoses, and a high precision indicates that the majority of patients diagnosed have the condition. The F1 score offers a more thorough assessment of the model's

performance by combining Precision and Recall into a single metric. When a model has a high F1-score, it is considered reliable for diagnosing diseases because it has high Precision and high Recall.

Recall: Recall measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive observations to all the observations in the actual class. It indicates how well the model can identify positive samples. Recall is important when the cost of false negatives is high, such as in medical screenings, where missing a positive case (false negative) can be critical.

$$Recall = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \quad (3.14)$$

Precision: Precision measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positives. It reflects the accuracy of positive predictions. Precision is crucial when the cost of false positives is high. For example, in medical diagnoses, a false positive could lead to unnecessary treatments.

$$Precision = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}} \quad (3.14)$$

F1 Score: The F1 Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It provides a balance between precision and recall, particularly useful for imbalanced datasets. F1 Score is useful when you need to balance precision and recall, especially in cases where you have an uneven class distribution.

$$F1 \text{ Score} = 2 * \left(\frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \right) \quad (3.15)$$

3.4.2. High-Level Input Design of the Enhanced Diagnostics System

The high-level input design of the system accepts input parameters through the touchscreen of a tablet or smartphone into the febrile disease diagnostic system graphic user interface (GUI). The high-level inputs are categorized into personal information, patient vitals, and symptoms as shown in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.10. High-level input design of the proposed system

The personal information category captures the vital demographic data of patients and healthcare workers while the patient vitals category captures patients' vitals such as blood pressure, temperature, etc entered through the system graphic user interface (GUI). The symptoms category captures patients' symptoms using a slider feature depicting the severity of each symptom. Table 3.8 presents the input parameters, data type, format, and mode of capture for the high-level input design.

Table 3.8. High-level input parameters

Input parameter	Data type	Format	Mode of capture
Personal Information			
Date of Birth (DOB)	Date	DD-MM-YYYY	Date picker interface to select the date
Gender	Categorical	Predefined categories	Dropdown menu
Name	Text	Natural language (plain text)	Text input field for first name, middle name (optional), and last name
Address	String	Text	Text input field with separate lines for street address, city, and state
Mobile phone	String	Numeric	Numeric input field with format validation to ensure proper phone number structure

Email	String	Text	Text input field with validation to ensure proper email format
National Identity Number	String	Numeric	Numeric input field with format validation to ensure proper NIN structure
Patient Vitals			
Temperature	Float	Numeric with one decimal place	Manual entry in a numeric input field
Blood Pressure	Integer	Separate systolic and diastolic values	Manual entry fields for systolic and diastolic values
Heart Rate	Integer	Numeric	Manual entry in a numeric input field
Respiratory Rate	Integer	Numeric	Manual entry in a numeric input field
Weight	Float	Numeric with one or two decimal places	Manual entry in a numeric input field
Height	Float	Numeric with one or two decimal places	Manual entry in a numeric input field
Symptom Severity			
Symptom	Ordinal (categorical)	Predefined categories (e.g. Absent, mild, moderate, severe, very severe)	Slider to indicate severity on a scale (e.g., 1-5).
Additional Symptoms	Text	Natural language (plain text)	Text input field where healthcare providers can type in symptoms

3.4.3. High-Level Process Design of the Enhanced Diagnostics System

The high-level process design of the system comprises several components that represent the interactions and relationships between the actors and the use cases in the proposed system. Figure 3.11 shows the Use-CASE diagram detailing the different use cases and the Actors in the system. The use case diagram is grouped into three sections (System administrator, patient clinical information, and patient assessment). The system administrator's functions ensure an efficient and seamless operation of the system, which include configuring system settings, managing user accounts and permissions, monitoring system performance, handling data backups and recovery, and managing and analyzing system logs. The patient clinical

information section handles editing patient personal records and viewing the summary of a patient's medical history by both the patient and the healthcare provider. The patient can also request a detailed medical history from the healthcare provider. The patient assessment section includes obtaining a patient's vital signs by measuring the essential physiological parameters, a physical examination, which involves a detailed assessment of the patient's body to look for anomalies or indications of illness, and history taking which is when the healthcare worker gathers comprehensive information about the patient's medical history, symptoms, and lifestyle. The provisional diagnosis is the initial diagnosis made by the system, which is subject to further investigation by the healthcare worker. In a use case diagram, "Suggest Treatment" extends "Provisional Diagnosis," signifying that proposing a treatment is an additional step that depends on the outcome and completion of the provisional diagnosis.

Figure 3.11. USE-CASE Diagram of the Diagnostic System

The class diagram in Figure 3.12 describes the structure of a system and shows the system's operations, classes, attributes, and relationships among objects. Figure 3.13 displays an extensive activity diagram that shows the actions of all the actors, and to distinguish between the roles of each actor and the flow of the action, each actor's actions are shown in a distinct swimlane.

Figure 3.12. Class Diagram of the Diagnostic System

Figure 3.13. Activity Diagram of the Diagnostic System

The sequence diagram of the enhanced diagnostic system details how operations are carried out and captures the interactions between the objects. Figure 3.14 shows the interactions between the actors (Healthcare Worker, Patient, Admin, System) and the system for different tasks performed within the system.

Figure 3.14. Sequence diagram of the Diagnostic System

3.4.4. High-Level Output Design of the Enhanced Diagnostics System

The high-level output of the system describes the output function of the febrile diagnostic system providing effective documentation and accessibility of all pertinent information. The high-level output comprises the vital signs summary, patient history overview, provisional diagnosis report, explainable output, patient medical record, request for detailed medical history, user management report, and backup and restore confirmation as shown in Figure 3.15. Vital signs summary provides a concise summary of the patient's vitals, such as temperature, blood pressure, and heart rate while the patient history overview shows the patient's past medical history, including previous diagnoses. The Provisional diagnosis report shows the predicted disease diagnosis, and the symptoms responsible for the diseases while the explainable output gives a visual representation of feature importance as well as a clear explanation of why the system made the diagnosis. Patient medical

record provides a comprehensive view of current and previous medical records. The request for detailed medical history is an automatically generated report when the patient requests a copy of their medical records, showing history in a user-friendly format. User Management Report provides a dashboard summary of users in the system, showing active, suspended, or pending accounts while backup and restore confirmation gives a report indicating successful or failed backup and restore operations. To ensure clarity and precision in the design and implementation of the proposed system, Table 3.9 offers a comprehensive view of the output requirements for each category along with a detailed description.

Figure 3.15. High-level output design context diagram

Table 3.9. High-level output parameters

Category	Output Parameters	Data Type	Format	Mode of Output
Provisional Diagnosis Report	Diagnosis ID, Patient ID, Symptoms, Vitals etc.	String, Date	Text, Date	Text, PDF, Electronic Record
Patient Medical Record	Patient ID, Name, Symptoms, Vitals, Diagnoses, etc.	String, List<Date>	Text, Date, List	Text, PDF, Electronic Record
Patient History Overview	Patient ID, Name, Vital, etc.	String, List<Number>	Text, CSV, List	Text, CSV, PDF, System Dashboard
Vital Signs Summary	Vital ID, Patient ID, etc.	String, List<Number>, DateTime	Text, DateTime	Text, PDF, Electronic Record
Request for Detailed Medical History	Patient ID, Request ID, etc.	String, DateTime	Text, DateTime	Text, PDF, Electronic Record
Explainable Output	Diagnosis ID, Patient ID, Symptoms, etc.	String, Date	Text, Date	Text, PDF, Electronic Record
User Management Report	User ID, Name, etc.	String, DateTime	Text, DateTime	Text, PDF, Electronic Record
Backup and Restore Confirmation	Backup/ Restore ID, Admin ID, etc.	String, DateTime	Text, DateTime	Text, PDF, Electronic Record

3.5. Database Design of the Enhanced Diagnostics System

The database design for the backend storage of the system is MySQL, a widely used open-source relational database management system (RDBMS). MySQL provides offline functionality and stores all data locally, and also a cloud database for online storage, backup, and real-time synchronization. The system has a mechanism for synchronization that guarantees data availability and consistency by coordinating the local storage with the cloud whenever an internet connection is available. It also has a mechanism for resolving conflicts that arise during synchronization, which guarantees data integrity. The database design is structured to handle patient registration, medical history, vitals, and diagnosis reports. The database is designed

to store all necessary data about the system with scalability, security, and efficiency while adhering to ACID principles to ensure reliable and consistent data handling. The conceptual data model is shown in Figure 3.16 which provides a high-level overview of the database, focusing on the main entities and their relationships.

Figure 3.16: Conceptual Data Model

The logical data model is shown in Figure 3.17, which depicts the database's Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD). The E-R diagram comprises six tables; patient, healthcare provider, symptom, patient_symptoms, vital, and diagnosis, representing the primary functions. The purpose of this model is to define the logical structure of the database, the entities, and the relationships between them. The logical data model defines all the attributes and their details, such as specific data types, and data length, and defines the relationships more explicitly.

Figure 3.17: Logical Data Model

The Physical data model describes how the data will be physically stored in the database in Figure 3.18. The physical data model represents the actual design blueprint of a relational database. It represents how data should be structured, presenting table names, attributes with data types, with primary and foreign key relationships. The Patient Table has several attributes, and each patient can have one or more diagnoses (a one-to-many relationship with the diagnosis table). The PatientID acts as a Foreign Key in both the Diagnosis and Vitals tables. The personal information and symptoms of the patient are recorded and linked to a healthcare provider during diagnosis. The Healthcare provider table has its attributes and the healthcare provider performs diagnoses and collects patient data (personal information, symptoms, and vitals) each healthcare worker can only perform one

diagnosis at a time, creating a one-to-one relationship between the Healthcare provider and each diagnosis. The HealthcareProviderID is a Foreign Key in the Diagnosis table, and they also have the authority to approve symptoms before they are considered for diagnosis. The Diagnosis Table has its attributes, and each diagnosis is linked to one patient (via the PatientID foreign key) and one healthcare provider (via the HealthcareProviderID foreign key). A patient can have multiple diagnoses, but each diagnosis is carried out by only one healthcare provider at a time. The diagnosis table records the detailed findings of the healthcare worker, using symptoms and other patient data for the final diagnosis. The Vitals table stores the various vital signs collected from the patient (e.g., temperature, blood pressure, heart rate), and the PatientID is a foreign key in the Vitals table, indicating that one patient can have multiple vitals recorded (a one-to-many relationship). These vitals are essential for supporting diagnosis and are reviewed by healthcare workers for decision-making. The Symptoms Table stores all possible symptoms that can be used for diagnosis. Symptoms approved by a healthcare provider in the system are linked to a diagnosis and stored on PatientSymptoms table. This ensures that only relevant symptoms are included. Multiple symptoms can be used for each diagnosis (a many-to-many relationship between Diagnosis and Symptoms).

Figure 3.18: Physical Data Model

3.6. Security Mechanism of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

The high-level security design is to ensure that the primary concern of the diagnostic system hosted on PythonAnywhere with MySQL for cloud storage is safeguarding patient data and ensuring secure interactions between different users (patient, healthcare worker, and admin). The overview of how security in the system is maintained is presented in Figure 3.18.

- i. **Authentication and Authorization:** Multi-factor Authentication (MFA) ensures that all users (patients, healthcare workers, and admins) securely log into the system. Role-based Access Control (RBAC) was used to define the permissions for each user role: A patient can log in via MFA,

view and edit their personal details, and view their summary of medical history. They cannot access sensitive medical data or other patient records. A healthcare worker logs into the system, registers patients, inputs patient data (vitals, symptoms), edits patients' records, and receives provisional diagnostic results from the system. The interaction is secure with encryption and role-based permissions. The Admin oversees the system's operations, manages access controls, performs backups, and monitors system logs for any security breaches.

- ii. **Data Encryption:** The system uses In-transit Encryption which ensures that all communication between the diagnostic app and the server is encrypted using Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS)/Transport Layer Security (TLS) to protect data from eavesdropping. The At-rest Encryption ensures that data stored in the MySQL database, including patient records and diagnosis results, is encrypted using Advanced Encryption Standard (AES-256), ensuring protection even if the database is compromised.
- iii. **Cloud Security:** The system was hosted on PythonAnywhere, which provides additional security features like firewalls to block unauthorized access and Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) protection to safeguard against attacks. Also, regular backups of the database are securely stored in the cloud with encryption to ensure data recovery in case of failure or corruption.
- iv. **Audit Logs and Monitoring:** All interactions within the diagnostic system, such as patient record updates, healthcare worker activities, and admin actions, are logged in audit logs. This provides traceability and ensures that unauthorized actions can be detected. An Intrusion Detection System (IDS) continuously monitors the system for suspicious activity, such as unauthorized access attempts or abnormal data traffic, to ensure prompt response to potential threats.

Figure 3.18: Security Design of the Enhanced Diagnostic System

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Choice of Implementation Platform

The system was implemented using Google Colaboratory (Google Colab), Visual Studio Code (VS Code), and PythonAnywhere. Google Colab is an improved version of Jupyter Notebook and an online tool that provides free access to a Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) and Tensor Processing Unit (TPU) for building machine learning and deep learning models. VS Code is an open-source, lightweight, and robust source code editor that facilitates rapid coding initiation and supports multiple extensions. PythonAnywhere is an online web hosting service and integrated development environment (IDE) built on the Python programming language. Figma is a collaborative platform that facilitates the creation of visually appealing and intuitive user interfaces.

4.2 Justification of the Implementation Platform

Google Colab is a product of Google that offers a free cloud-based platform for users to write and run Python code in a group setting. It provides GPU and TPU resources accessibility, which makes data analysis and machine learning easier. Google Drive is where Colab notebooks are kept and readily shared for in-the-moment collaboration. This cloud-based infrastructure offers free access to potent processing resources for training and testing intricate machine learning models, such as Multi-layer Perceptron, XGBoost, and Random Forest. Colab is a great platform for experimenting with algorithms, creating diagnostics, and interpreting results with tools like LIME for explainability because of its smooth integration with Python and well-known machine learning libraries and packages like Scikit-learn, NumPy, Pandas, Matplotlib, and TensorFlow. Furthermore, Google Drive's capacity to store sizable datasets and facilitate collaboration offers flexibility in the development process.

Visual Studio Code was developed by Microsoft as a cross-platform open-source code editor that works with Linux, macOS, and Windows. With its powerful and highly configurable Integrated Development Environment (IDE), VS Code enhances development and offers developers a comprehensive platform to write, test, and optimize code thanks to its support for extensions and debugging tools, which enable seamless integration with version control systems. Its extensive plugin library enhances Python development functionality, making it an indispensable tool for writing production-ready code. Its interface facilitates the integration of remote development features and seamless deployment connectivity with PythonAnywhere. The VS code platform made it possible to integrate API clients right into the IDE, which made it easier for ChatGPT, LIME explanations, and ML models to communicate with one another.

Flet offers an intuitive framework for developing interactive desktop, mobile, and web applications with Python, which is why it was selected for mobile app development. It was the best option because of its ease of use and smooth integration with other Python libraries, like GPT for natural language processing, LIME for explainability, and Random Forest (RF) for machine learning. Furthermore, Flet's cross-platform compatibility made sure that the application could function consistently on various devices, giving patients and healthcare professionals flexibility. Constrained resource environments could also benefit from the framework's ability to render UI components quickly and with little overhead, making it a good choice for creating lightweight and responsive applications.

The system UI/UX design was built using Figma since it provides a strong, team-based platform for designing user interfaces that are both logical and aesthetically pleasing. Because of its real-time collaboration features, developers and designers could collaborate easily to make sure the app's design was intuitive for patients and healthcare workers alike. The app's workflow was thoroughly tested and refined due to Figma's flexibility in creating interactive prototypes. This made sure that crucial features like patient registration, viewing medical histories, and receiving diagnostic feedback were both easily accessible and navigable. This approach ensured a

polished and efficient user experience, which is critical for an app intended for use in medical settings.

PythonAnywhere is an online integrated development environment (IDE) and web hosting service built on the Python programming language. It was founded in 2012 by Giles Thomas and Robert Smithson and offers a code editor with syntax highlighting as well as in-browser access to server-based Python and Bash command-line interfaces. Because PythonAnywhere makes hosting Python-based web applications so simple, it was chosen as the deployment platform. It is a cloud-based platform that allows access to databases like MySQL and supports the scalability needed for the deployment of mobile apps. PythonAnywhere facilitates seamless transitions from the development environment to real-world applications by allowing continuous deployment and testing. It guarantees that the application can operate effectively on a range of mobile devices with little reliance on client-side hardware. The server-side code for LIME and the RF model was hosted by PythonAnywhere so that the model could be used to diagnose diseases, and LIME was able to interpret the predictions made by the model. PythonAnywhere served as the middleman for API calls to ChatGPT, by processing incoming queries from the mobile app, sending ChatGPT the ML and LIME results for additional clarification, and then returning the answers to the mobile interface. The MySQL-based infrastructure for handling patient data and diagnostic results was handled by PythonAnywhere, ensuring safely storing and retrieving diagnostic results, medical histories, and patient records. The platform made sure that the backend logic and the mobile app could access the MySQL database, allowing for seamless data transfer and persistent storage across the app's various functionalities.

MySQL is a widely used relational database management system and is renowned for its open-source nature and scalability. Due to its strong security features, which include encryption, role-based access control, and user authentication, MySQL is appropriate for managing sensitive health data by the laws governing the privacy of medical data. MySQL interfaces with the Python backend and runs GPT, LIME, and RF with ease, making data transfer between the models and the database seamless. The versatility of MySQL in managing dynamic queries and storing different kinds

of data makes it a great option for this application's data management requirements. It supports database scaling, which guarantees that the application can accommodate growing workloads without compromising performance as it expands and serves a larger user base.

4.3 System Requirements

The enhanced diagnostic system requires explicit software and hardware specifications to operate effectively. These requirements are highlighted in subsections 4.31 and 4.32.

4.3.1 Hardware Requirements

The hardware requirements for the smooth operation and optimal performance of the diagnostic system include the following.

1. **Central Processing Unit (CPU):** A quad-core processor (2.0 GHz or higher) is required for efficient execution of the application, especially when handling LIME explanations and Random Forest computations.
2. **Random Access Memory (RAM):** A minimum of 4GB RAM is required to ensure smooth multitasking and prevent lag during diagnosis.
3. **Storage:** An Android device with at least 16GB of internal storage is recommended for optimal functionality.
4. **Battery:** Since the app may be used in resource-limited settings, a device with a minimum 3000mAh battery is required to ensure extended usage.
5. **Display:** A screen size of at least 5 inches with a 720p (1280 × 720 pixels) resolution is required for clear visualization because lower resolution device may reduce the clarity of diagnostic results.
6. **Network Connectivity:** The app relies on cloud-based services, including the ChatGPT API and backend processing. Therefore, a stable 4G or Wi-Fi connection is required.
7. **Operating System:** It is recommended to run the app on a device with Android 9.0 (Pie) or higher for smooth operation.

4.3.2 Software Requirements

The enhanced diagnostic system requires an Android OS to run, and to run it on a Microsoft Windows device, an Android emulator such as BlueStacks 5, which supports Android 8.0 (Oreo).

1. Android: A minimum of Version 8.0 (Oreo) is required, but for good performance, Android 10.

4.4 System Testing

The mobile app was tested to ensure it works properly, satisfies user requirements, and performs dependably in real-world scenarios using Top-Down and Bottom-Up testing approaches.

Bottom-Up Testing: The bottom-up approach started with testing individual components before integrating them into larger modules. This method ensured that foundational issues were identified and resolved early. Each component was tested separately to verify its correctness before integration. The Random Forest model was evaluated to confirm accurate disease diagnosis. The LIME explainability feature was tested to ensure it generated valid and interpretable explanations. The ChatGPT API integration was checked for proper response formatting and retrieval. The database operations were tested to confirm patient data could be added, modified, and retrieved correctly. Once individual components were validated, they were gradually integrated and tested together.

Top-Down Testing: The top-down approach focused on assessing the system as a whole before delving into individual components. This ensured that the app met user expectations and functioned seamlessly. The complete system was tested from the user's perspective to validate workflows such as patient registration, history-taking, diagnosis generation, and medical record management. Performance tests were conducted under different conditions to assess system responsiveness, including concurrent user access and real-time interactions with the ChatGPT API and ML model. Security testing ensured proper authentication, access control, and secure storage of patient data. Usability testing was performed to confirm that healthcare

professionals and patients could navigate the app easily. Feedback from users was collected to validate the interpretability and usefulness of the explanations provided by the ML model and LIME.

4.5 Results and Discussion

The study achieved the following results:

1. The tropical febrile disease dataset was acquired.
2. A Disease Diagnostic Model (DDM) was developed.
3. The DDM was trained and tested.
4. A Model Interpretability Framework (MIF) was integrated.
5. The integrated diagnostic model was implemented and evaluated.

1. **Acquisition of a Tropical Febrile Disease Dataset:** The dataset was approved for use by the Institute of Health Research and Development, University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Nigeria, and proved instrumental in the development and validation of the diagnostic system. The dataset contains detailed records from 4,870 patients, encompassing demographic information, 50 symptoms, associated risk factors, suspected diagnoses, further investigations, and confirmed diagnoses for eleven tropical febrile diseases. The descriptive statistics of the collected dataset which comprises the age range of the patients, the diseases, the number of confirmed diagnoses, patients with comorbidities, and the number of comorbidities are presented in Table 4.1. The dataset was 100% complete with no missing values and a duplicate check also ensured that no redundant patient records were found as patient entry was distinct with unique identifiers as presented in Appendix A. This acquisition met the research's objectives and underscored the importance of high-quality, ethically sourced datasets in AI-driven healthcare applications.

Table 4.1 Descriptive statistics of the dataset

Age Range	Male	Female	Total
< 5years	534	419	953
5 years to 12 years	346	323	669
13years to 19 years	150	213	363
20 years to 64 years	1012	1605	2617
65 years and above	133	135	268
Total			4870
Diseases	No. of Confirmed Diagnosis		
Malaria	3350		
Typhoid Fever	1244		
HIV/AIDS	447		
Upper RTI	1386		
Lower RTI	913		
Upper UTI	658		
Lower UTI	854		
Tuberculosis	410		
Yellow Fever	28		
Lassa Fever	32		
Dengue Fever	46		
Comorbidity	No. of Comorbidity		
0 disease	535		
1 disease	1727		
2 diseases	1399		
3 diseases	623		
4 diseases	282		
5 diseases	124		
6 diseases	99		
7 diseases	35		
8 diseases	35		
9 diseases	6		
10 diseases	2		
11 diseases	3		
Total	4870		

2. Development of a Disease Diagnostic Model (DDM) using the Random Forest algorithm: This objective was achieved through machine learning modeling. This approach identified an optimal model that effectively diagnosed febrile diseases based on the dataset. The model was developed to align with the mathematical framework for diagnosing febrile diseases, as defined by equation 4.1. This equation represents the relationship between

input features (symptoms) and disease outcomes, independent of the specific ML model being used. The developed DDM was designed to ensure robust generalization and serve as a framework, ensuring that predictions from different algorithms adhered to a standardized relationship between inputs and outputs. This mathematical independence allows flexibility in switching or combining models, thus enhancing the system's adaptability.

$$O_{ML}(X) = \{P(d_1|X), P(d_2|X), \dots, P(d_k|X)\} \quad (4.1)$$

where:

O_{ML} is the output of the ML model

$P(d_i|X)$ is the probability of disease d_i given the symptoms X

k is the total number of diseases (in our case, $k=6$).

3. Training and Testing of the DDM using an 80/20 split of the febrile disease dataset: The febrile disease dataset was split into training and testing subsets to ensure robust evaluation, using an 80/20 ratio. The training set, comprising 80% of the dataset, was used to train the models, while the remaining 20% served as the testing set to evaluate generalization. This split was chosen to maintain a balance between training sufficiency and unbiased performance evaluation. Hyperparameter tuning was executed through Grid search cross-validation (GridSearchCV) with 5-fold cross-validation (CV=5) to maximize the model's performance. The training data is divided into five equal subsets, or folds, for cross-validation. Four folds were used to train the model, and the final fold was used for testing. To guarantee that every observation in the training data was used for validation, this process was repeated five times, using a different fold as the test set each time. Cross-validation is a useful technique for evaluating the robustness of the model and lowering the likelihood of overfitting. By averaging the performance across all folds, it also aids in identifying the most ideal hyperparameters. GridSearchCV was used to tune the hyperparameters for each model to find the combination that delivers the best performance. Hyperparameter tuning greatly affects the model's accuracy and efficiency and it is applied to maximize the model's

performance by regulating how it learns from the data. For Random Forest (RF), the `n_estimators` parameter, which controls the number of trees in the forest, was tested with values [100, 200, 300], and `max_depth`, which defines the maximum depth of each tree, was set to [None, 10, 20]. For the Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), three hyperparameters were tuned: the `hidden_layer_sizes` (number of neurons in each layer) with values [(100,), (50, 50), (50, 25, 10)], the activation function (responsible for transforming input data within the neural network) with ['relu', 'tanh', 'logistic'], and the regularization term `alpha` with [0.0001, 0.001, 0.01]. Lastly, for XGBoost, the `n_estimators` parameter was tuned with [100, 200, 300] and `max_depth` with [3, 5, 7].

The training performance of the ML models in Table 4.2 and Figure 4.1 show significant differences in predictive power. MLP achieved moderate performance, with an overall AUC-ROC of 0.78 and F1-scores ranging from 0.56 (HIV/AIDS) to 0.90 (Malaria), indicating its struggles with recall, particularly for HIV/AIDS (0.42) and Enteric Fever (0.54). XGBoost demonstrated significantly higher precision and recall across all diseases, achieving an AUC-ROC of 0.97 and near-perfect F1-scores (≥ 0.95), making it a highly reliable classifier. Random Forest outperformed both models, achieving perfect precision for most diseases, high recall (≥ 0.97), and an AUC-ROC of 0.99, suggesting an almost flawless training performance with minimal misclassifications. While all three algorithms demonstrated the capability to model the complex relationships on the test dataset, Random Forest emerged as the best-performing model due to its balance between high predictive results and computational efficiency. XGBoost demonstrated strong results but required intensive tuning, whereas MLP showed limitations in recall and F1 scores for certain diseases, indicating potential constraints in handling imbalanced data within the dataset. Across all models, Random Forest algorithm emerged as the best-performing model and achieved the highest diagnostic performance across most diseases with an f1-score of 88% for malaria, 60% for enteric fever, 51% for HIV and AIDS, 72% for urinary tract infection, 72% for respiratory tract infection, and 60% for tuberculosis

followed by XGBoost (87%, 60%, 48%, 70%, 72%, and 65%) and the MLP (85%, 51%, 46%, 70%, 69%, 64%) model as presented in Table 4.3 and Figure 4.2.

Table 4.2. ML Diagnostic Models Training Performance

		MAL	ENFVR	HVAD	UTI	RTI	TB
MLP	Precision	0.88	0.73	0.84	0.85	0.79	0.87
	Recall	0.91	0.54	0.42	0.67	0.74	0.59
	F1-score	0.90	0.62	0.56	0.75	0.76	0.70
	AUC-ROC	0.78					
XGBOOST	Precision	0.98	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Recall	0.98	0.92	0.91	0.93	0.97	1.00
	F1-score	0.98	0.95	0.95	0.96	0.99	1.00
	AUC-ROC	0.97					
RF	Precision	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Recall	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.99	1.00
	F1-score	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.00
	AUC-ROC	0.99					

Figure 4.1. Model Training Performance

Table 4.3. ML Diagnostic Models Test Performance

		MAL	ENFVR	HVAD	UTI	RTI	TB
MLP	Precision	0.84	0.65	0.75	0.77	0.75	0.59
	Recall	0.87	0.42	0.34	0.65	0.63	0.59
	F1-score	0.85	0.51	0.46	0.70	0.69	0.64
	AUC-ROC	0.74					
XGBOOST	Precision	0.84	0.64	0.62	0.77	0.77	0.72
	Recall	0.90	0.56	0.40	0.63	0.68	0.60
	F1-score	0.87	0.60	0.48	0.70	0.72	0.65
	AUC-ROC	0.76					
RF	Precision	0.85	0.69	0.75	0.80	0.77	0.77
	Recall	0.91	0.53	0.39	0.65	0.68	0.49
	F1-score	0.88	0.60	0.51	0.72	0.72	0.60
	AUC-ROC	0.75					

Figure 4.2. Model Test Performance

- Integration of a Model Interpretability Framework (MIF): To address the critical need for transparency and explainability in disease diagnosis, a Model Interpretability Framework (MIF) was integrated with the diagnostic system. The Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) framework and large language model (ChatGPT) were selected for their ability to provide

intuitive visual and textual explanations of model decisions. LIME was applied to the Random Forest model, offering insights into how specific symptoms contributed to diagnostic predictions. LIME aids in understanding how the models make decisions for individual cases by approximating the model locally with an interpretable substitute model and by applying LIME to the test subset, this study was able to identify key symptoms that influenced the model's diagnoses for specific instances as shown in Fig. 4.3 to Fig. 4.5 for the three models. The length of the bars indicates how much each symptom contributed to the final diagnosis. The symptoms on the left push the diagnosis into the negative class, which is the absence of a disease, while the symptoms on the right push the diagnosis into the positive class, which is the presence of disease. This integration was essential in addressing a key limitation of traditional machine learning models: their "black-box" nature. By enabling clinicians and healthcare providers to understand the reasoning behind predictions, the system enhances trust, promotes adoption, and aids in informed decision-making.

Figure 4.3. MLP model LIME diagram

Figure 4.4. XGBoost model LIME diagram

Figure 4.5. RF model LIME diagram

The ChatGPT was used to generate natural language interpretations of complex diagnostic outputs. This was easily accessible because the development environment was built on a Python platform. The sample prompt takes the list of diagnosed diseases and patient symptoms with their contributions to the diagnoses from the LIME model as shown in Appendix E. The generated prompt was assigned to a variable and converted to JSON format before being sent to the ChatGPT API as a request.

5. Implementation and Evaluation of the Integrated Diagnostic Model: The integrated diagnostic model was implemented using Python in a development environment combining Google Colaboratory, Visual Studio Code, and

PythonAnywhere, with a MySQL database for data storage. The model was evaluated using performance metrics such as precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC. The Random Forest-based diagnostic system consistently outperformed the other models, achieving high precision and recall for diseases like malaria and urinary tract infections while maintaining robust performance across different diseases. Including LIME and ChatGPT as the MIF enhanced the model by ensuring interpretability. Clinicians provided positive feedback on the clarity and usability of the interpretative outputs, reinforcing the practical value of the system. These results demonstrate that the integration of machine learning, XAI, and user-centric design can create diagnostic tools that are both accurate and interpretable, paving the way for improved healthcare outcomes in tropical regions. The integrated diagnostic system was implemented and the result of the explainable diagnosis page is presented in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6. Explainable Diagnosis Page

In evaluating the Enhanced Diagnostic System, a structured questionnaire was distributed to ten doctors to collect patient symptoms and confirmed disease diagnoses after laboratory tests. The collected patient information was then used to test the system. The questionnaire and results are presented in Appendices H and I. Out of the 99 patient cases tested, the system correctly predicted 72 confirmed cases, while 26 cases were misclassified, and one case was completely missed. The system demonstrated the highest detection rates for Malaria and HIV/AIDS, correctly identifying all cases with no false positives. However, Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) and Respiratory Tract Infection (RTI) had moderate detection rates, while Typhoid Fever and Tuberculosis had the lowest detection

rates, indicating challenges in distinguishing these diseases. Additionally, false positives were most frequent in Typhoid Fever, Malaria, Tuberculosis, and Respiratory Tract Infection, likely due to symptom overlap among these diseases, leading to misclassifications. These findings suggest that while the system performs well for certain diseases, further refinements are needed to improve its accuracy, particularly for diseases with overlapping clinical presentations.

4.6 Documentation

The four phases of the system development which comprises the design, development, testing, and deployment are outlined in this section.

4.6.1 The Design Phase

This phase outlines the methodology which was adopted in this research work. The data-driven and Agile methodologies were adopted for the design of the enhanced febrile disease diagnostic system to ensure adaptability, accuracy, and continuous improvement. The system was able to utilize real patient data because of the data-driven approach, which ensures that diagnostic models are based on real patterns, and relationships, which results in more accurate and trustworthy disease diagnoses. Meanwhile, the Agile's iterative and flexible framework facilitated rapid prototyping, continuous feedback from healthcare workers, and regular updates to the system. This ensured that user needs and technological advancements could be promptly incorporated, enhancing the system's relevance and responsiveness to evolving healthcare requirements. The created solution made use of the limitations in the existing system to create new features that would improve the proposed system. The proposed system was then compared with the existing one which could only diagnose patients above 17 years) and lacked explainability which undermines medical experts' trust in the system. These limitations were the rationale for investing time and resources in developing the new system. The high-level input design of the system shows how users can input parameters through the mobile device into the diagnostic system GUI. The high-level functionalities of the system components that enhanced the application are highlighted in the system architecture and the high-level process design shows:

- i. The Use-case diagram detailing the different use cases and the Actors in the diagnostic system.
- ii. The class diagram which describes the structure of a system and presents the system's operations, classes, attributes, and relationships among objects.
- iii. An extensive activity diagram that displays each actor's actions along with their respective roles and the action's flow, with each actor's actions displayed in its swimlane.
- iv. A sequence diagram detailing how operations are carried out, capturing the interactions between the objects.

The designed system is expected to provide the needed output for the users by describing the output function of the system and providing effective documentation and accessibility of all pertinent information. The database design which is the backend storage of the system provides offline functionality for storing all data locally, and also a cloud database for online storage. The designed system also incorporated a security design that handles security threats to the system

4.6.2 The Development Phase

This phase is characterized by the creation of the necessary models and the writing of the codes to implement the intended system with the aid of development tools, frameworks, libraries, and packages.

PythonAnywhere, VS Code, and Google Colab were used in the system's development. The random forest model was developed using Google Colab and integrated with LIME, and VS Code provided a complete platform for writing, testing, and optimizing code. The Random Forest model, LIME explanations, and ChatGPT were able to communicate with each other more easily because the VS code platform allowed API clients to be integrated directly into the IDE. The PythonAnywhere is an online integrated development environment (IDE) that enables the hosting of Python-based web applications. MySQL database runs GPT, LIME, and RF with ease and interfaces with the Python backend, facilitating smooth data transfer between the models and the database.

4.6.3 The Testing Phase

In this phase, numerous tests were performed on the code throughout the development phase to ensure its functionality, reliability, and user-friendliness. To ensure that individual parts, like user interfaces and algorithms for illness diagnosis, function as intended, unit testing was carried out. Integration testing guarantees that these parts work together harmoniously inside the application. Agile relies heavily on user acceptance testing (UAT), wherein input from patients and healthcare providers is continuously collected to make sure the app satisfies their needs. Performance testing examines the app's responsiveness and speed, particularly in environments with limited resources, while regression testing confirms that new updates or iterations do not adversely affect current features. Iterative testing can be used to improve the app over time.

4.6.4 The Deployment Phase

This phase involves ensuring that the fully tested and functional app is available for use by the user and includes setting up the necessary infrastructure, such as cloud servers, databases, and user interfaces, ensuring the app is accessible to both healthcare professionals and patients. Deployment is done incrementally in Agile, with features being rolled out in stages, allowing for quick feedback and adjustments. Additionally, user training, system monitoring, and maintenance plans are established to ensure smooth operation and support after deployment.

4.7. System Setup and User Manual

The system user manual presents the features of the application and how the user interacts with the application. The system is designed with a user-friendly user interface that allows users to interact with the system through the touchscreen of their mobile devices. The app was built and packaged into an Android Package (APK) format using the development platform (VS Code) and the APK file could easily be run on any Android device. After successful installation, the healthcare worker can create an account using the form in Figure 4.7. After creating an account, the system admin would have to verify the details of the healthcare worker before the password can be sent to the healthcare worker's email address to be used for logging into the

system. The healthcare worker uses his or her email address and password to log into the system through Figure 4.8.

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for creating an account. The title is "Create an account" with a subtitle "Already have an account? [Login](#)". Below the title are five input fields: "Email address", "Full Name", "Sex", "Password" (with an eye icon for visibility), and "Confirm Password" (with an eye icon). A red "Register" button is positioned below the fields. At the bottom, there is a disclaimer: "By clicking Create account you agree to Recognizes [Terms of use](#) and [Private Policy](#)".

Figure 4.7. Healthcare Worker Signup

The screenshot shows the login screen for the "Febrile Disease Diagnosis System". The title is "Febrile Disease Diagnosis System" with a subtitle "Welcome back, you've been missed!". Below the title are two input fields: "Email address" and "Password". A red "Continue" button is located below the password field. At the bottom, there is a link: "Not a member [Register now](#)". The top status bar shows the time 11:32, signal strength, and 28% battery.

Figure 4.8. User Login

After successfully logging into the system, the Healthcare worker is presented with a user-friendly dashboard in Figure 4.9. Through the dashboard, the healthcare worker can register new patients (Figure 4.10) and view the list of registered patients (Figure 4.11).

Figure 4.9. Healthcare Dashboard

Figure 4.10. Patient Registration Page

After a successful patient registration, the healthcare worker can navigate to the patient's dashboard (Figure 4.12) automatically or by searching and clicking on the patient's name from the patient list. In the patient's dashboard, history taking and examination (Figure 4.13) and view the past medical history of patients. After a successful history taking and examination, the mobile app presents provisional diagnoses, listing all likely diseases that the patient has with a LIME chart and ChatGPT explanation of the diagnoses as shown in Figure 4.14.

Figure 4.11. Patient List

Figure 4.12. Patient Dashboard

Figure 4.13. History Taking and Examination Figure 4.14. Explainable Diagnosis
Page

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

The enhanced diagnostic system developed in this study represents a significant advancement in improving the diagnosis of tropical febrile diseases, particularly in resource-limited settings. By leveraging the Random Forest model as the core diagnostic algorithm and integrating Explainable AI (LIME) and Large Language Models (ChatGPT), the system overcomes key limitations of traditional models, such as interpretability constraints and exclusion of younger patients. Unlike the existing models, which lack transparency in explaining their diagnostic rationale and impose an age restriction of 17 years and above, our model provides detailed, case-specific justifications for its predictions. Through LIME, the system highlights symptom contributions to disease classification, while ChatGPT translates these insights into user-friendly explanations, making the decision-making process comprehensible to both medical professionals and non-expert users.

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of combining Machine Learning, Explainable AI, and LLMs to enhance healthcare diagnostics. The system not only predicts the presence of malaria, HIV/AIDS, enteric fever, UTI, RTI, and tuberculosis but also interprets its decisions by identifying symptom relevance and model confidence for each disease. This interpretability ensures that healthcare providers can validate AI-driven insights and refine their clinical decision-making. Furthermore, implementing the system with a scalable MySQL database and flexible coding platforms (Google Colab and PythonAnywhere) enhances accessibility and adaptability to diverse clinical environments. By adopting an agile, data-driven methodology, this study demonstrates that iterative development leads to effective, region-specific diagnostic solutions. Ultimately, this system represents a crucial step toward AI-driven healthcare tools that empower clinicians, improve diagnostic accuracy, and enhance patient outcomes in tropical regions.

5.2. Recommendations

Several recommendations are made for primary, secondary and tertiary stakeholder, so that the diagnostic system can be fully utilized to enhance disease detection, optimize patient care, and improve overall healthcare efficiency.

5.2.1 Primary Stakeholders

Medical Professionals: Medical professionals should actively engage in continuous education programs on AI-assisted diagnostics to stay updated with advancements in the field. They should also provide regular feedback on AI-generated diagnoses to enhance model accuracy and reliability. Additionally, leveraging AI-driven explanations can improve doctor-patient communication, ensuring patients better understand their conditions and treatment recommendations.

Healthcare Organizations: Healthcare organizations should facilitate AI training for staff through workshops and training sessions to optimize the use of AI diagnostics. They should invest in seamlessly integrating the diagnostic system into existing hospital management and Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems while establishing internal policies to monitor AI performance, track errors, and ensure regulatory compliance. Additionally, upgrading healthcare IT infrastructure to support real-time AI diagnostics, cloud computing, and data storage is essential for maximizing the system's effectiveness.

5.2.2 Secondary Stakeholders

Healthcare Administrators: Healthcare administrators should develop clear AI adoption policies to guide the integration of AI diagnostics into healthcare systems while ensuring ethical use through governance frameworks that promote fairness and transparency. Securing funding through grants and investments is crucial for expanding AI adoption in both public and private healthcare facilities. Additionally, fostering collaboration with technology providers and research institutions will help enhance and continuously improve the AI diagnostic system.

Medical Researchers: Medical researchers should leverage AI-driven insights to analyze disease patterns, enhance epidemiological studies, and improve predictive

modeling. To ensure reliability, they must conduct independent clinical trials to validate AI accuracy and suggest refinements. Publishing research findings in scientific journals and conferences will contribute to the broader knowledge base, while advocating for open data sharing can facilitate responsible access to anonymized datasets, further improving AI training and performance.

Healthcare Technology Developers: Healthcare technology developers should focus on enhancing system usability by creating an intuitive user interface for seamless navigation by both professionals and patients. Continuous optimization of AI models using real-world data will improve diagnostic accuracy, while ensuring interoperability with existing healthcare software and medical devices will enhance integration. Additionally, robust cybersecurity measures, including strong encryption and data protection, must be implemented to safeguard patient information.

Public Health Officials: Public health officials should utilize AI for early disease surveillance to detect outbreaks promptly and enhance response strategies. Standardizing AI implementation through national frameworks will ensure consistent quality and accuracy in diagnostics. Integrating AI into national health strategies will improve disease prevention and management, while public awareness campaigns should educate communities on the benefits of AI-assisted healthcare.

Insurance Providers: Insurance providers should integrate AI diagnostics into health plans to ensure coverage for AI-driven assessments. Utilizing AI-generated reports can streamline claims processing, enabling faster approvals. AI-powered risk assessment models can help personalize insurance coverage based on individual health risks, while offering incentives for preventive healthcare can encourage early disease detection and proactive health management.

5.2.3 Tertiary Stakeholders

Healthcare Educators: Healthcare educators should integrate AI diagnostics into medical training by updating curricula to reflect modern advancements. Offering AI certification programs can equip students and professionals with specialized knowledge, while hands-on clinical simulations and case studies will enhance practical experience in AI-assisted diagnostics.

Healthcare IT Professionals: Healthcare IT professionals should ensure the AI diagnostic system remains functional, secure, and up to date while implementing strict data protection policies to comply with health regulations. Additionally, they should develop scalable AI solutions capable of handling growing patient demands without performance issues.

Medical Device Manufacturers: Medical device manufacturers should design AI-compatible diagnostic tools, innovate AI-powered equipment to enhance accuracy and usability, and integrate real-time data processing capabilities for faster disease detection.

Pharmaceutical Companies: Pharmaceutical companies should leverage AI to optimize drug discovery, personalize treatment plans based on patient data, and invest in AI-driven clinical research to enhance drug efficacy and patient outcomes.

5.3. Contributions to Knowledge

This research makes several important contributions to the field of healthcare technology and AI diagnostics.

- i. This research introduces an enhanced diagnostic system, leveraging Machine Learning, Explainable AI, and Large Language Models to improve transparency and interpretability. By selecting Random Forest as the primary diagnostic model and integrating it with LIME and ChatGPT, this study demonstrates the practical value of using XAI to enhance clinician understanding of machine-driven diagnostics.
- ii. By utilizing accessible and scalable tools like Google Colab, VS Code, and PythonAnywhere, this study illustrates a viable model for implementing advanced diagnostics in low-resource environments, which could inspire further innovations in the development of healthcare applications suited to under-resourced settings.

5.4. Suggestions for Further Study

- i. Future research should explore the adoption of the methodology and techniques used in this study for diagnosing other diseases beyond febrile

illnesses. Expanding its application to other chronic conditions could enhance AI-driven diagnostic capabilities across multiple medical fields.

- ii. Further studies could investigate the integration of additional Large Language Models with specialized medical training to improve interpretability and ensure domain-specific accuracy. This would enhance the system's ability to generate precise, explainable diagnoses tailored to complex medical cases.

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APPENDIX A: FEBRILE DISEASE PATIENT DATASET

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	
1	PATCC	STCON	PHYCG	PHYEX	PHYOL	PATCC	SEACG	PATAG	PATSE	PRGST	PATNU	ABDPN	ABDPN	BCKPN	BCKPN	BITAM	BITAM	BLDN	BLDN	BLDYU	BLD
4846	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/90	1	9	1	1	1	1	9	1	9	4	9	1	9	1	
4847	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/91	1	6	2	1	1	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	
4848	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/92	1	44	1	1	1	4	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	
4849	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/93	1	26	2	1	1	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	
4850	1	1	AK/16	15	3, 2	AK/16/048	1	18	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4851	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/04	1	12	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4852	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	45	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4853	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	6	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4854	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	51	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	
4855	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	29	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4856	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	29	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4857	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	38	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4858	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	44	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4859	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	40	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4860	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	50	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4861	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/05	1	14	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4862	1	1	AK/16	15	3	AK/16/06	1	25	2	1	5	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4863	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/08	1	44	1	1	1	4	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4864	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/08	1	26	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4865	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/08	1	6	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	
4866	1	1	AK/13	10	3	AK/13/08	1	41	1	1	1	1	10	2	10	3	10	1	10	1	
4867	1	4	RV/03	7	3	RV/03/001	3	45	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4868	1	4	RV/03	7	3	RV/03/002	3	26	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4869	1	4	RV/03	7	3	RV/03/003	3	25	2	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4870	1	4	RV/03	7	2	RV/03/004	3	41	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	
4871	1	4	RV/03	7	2	RV/03/005	3	45	1	1	1	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	

	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD	AE	AF	AG	AH	AI	AJ	AK	AL	AM	AN	AO		
1	CTRH	CTRH	CHSIN	CHSIN	CHSPN	CHSPN	CHLNR	CHLNR	CLDYU	CLDYU	CNST	CNST	CGHDR	CGHDR	DRH	DRH	DIFBR	DIFBR	DIZ	DIZ	CC	DRY
4846	3	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	4	9
4847	3	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	2	9
4848	1	9	1	9	1	9	4	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	3	9
4849	4	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	3	9
4850	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4851	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4852	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4853	1	10	1	10	1	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4854	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4855	1	10	1	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4856	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4857	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
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4859	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4860	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4861	1	10	2	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4862	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4863	1	10	1	10	3	10	3	10	3	10	2	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	3	10
4864	3	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	2	10	3	10	3	10
4865	3	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	3	10
4866	3	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	3	10	1	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	4	10
4867	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4868	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4869	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4870	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4871	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10

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	AP	AQ	AR	AS	AT	AU	AV	AW	AX	AY	AZ	BA	B6	BC	BD	BE	BF	BG	BH	BI	BDY	
1	DRYCG	DRYCG	DRYCG	DRYCG	FTG	FTG_C	FVR	FVR_C	HGPSF	HGPSF	HGGDF	HGGDF	SWRF	SWRF	SUDON	SUDON	LWGD	LWGD	FOLBR	FOLBR	BDY	
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4847	1	9	1	9	3	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9
4848	1	9	1	9	3	9	3	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	2	9
4849	1	9	1	9	4	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	2	9	2	9
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4858	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10
4859	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10
4860	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10
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4862	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4863	3	10	3	10	3	10	3	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4864	1	10	1	10	4	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	2	10	2	10
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4869	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4870	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4871	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10

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	BJ	BK	BL	BM	BN	BO	BP	BQ	BR	BS	BT	BU	BV	BW	BX	BY	BZ	CA	CB	CC	CC	C
1	BDYIC	BDYIC	GENBD	GENBD	GENRS	GENRS	HDACH	HDACH	INTBLE	INTBLE	JNTSW	JNTSW	LTG	LTG_C	LMPNI	LMPNI	MSCBI	MSCBI	MUTUC	MUTUC	NUS	
4846	2	9	2	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9
4847	1	9	3	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9
4848	2	9	3	9	1	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	3	9	3	9	3	9	1	9	1	9
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4859	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10
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4861	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
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4870	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4871	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10

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	CD	CE	CF	CG	CH	CI	CJ	CK	CL	CM	CN	CO	CP	CQ	CR	CS	CT	CU	CV	CW	CK
1	NUS	NUS_C	NGTSV	NGTSV	PNBHE	PNBHE	UPBCK	UPBCK	PNFLU	PNFLU	PERTN	PERTN	REDEY	REDEY	REDEY	REDEY	SENLH	SENLH	SHK	SHK_C	SKM
4846	1	3	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9
4847	2	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1
4848	2	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	4	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1
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4855	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1
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4859	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1
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4867	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1
4868	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1
4869	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1
4870	1	10	4	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1
4871	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1

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	CX	CY	CZ	DA	DB	DC	DD	DE	DF	DG	DH	DI	DJ	DK	DL	DM	DN	DO	DP	DQ	DR	
1	SKNRS	SKNRS	SRTRT	SRTRT	SPPBP	SPPBP	URNFO	URNFO	VMT	VMT_C	WHZ	WHZ_C	MAL	MAL_C	ENFVR	ENFVR	HVAD	HVAD	UPUTI	UPUTI	LWJ	
4846	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	5	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	2	9
4847	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	5	9	1	8	1	9	1	9	1	8
4848	1	9	1	9	4	9	3	9	1	9	1	9	3	8	5	8	4	8	5	8	5	8
4849	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	5	9	4	8	2	8	5	8	5	8
4850	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	4	10	3	10	2	10	2	10
4851	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	2	10	2	10	2	10	2	10
4852	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	3	10	2	10	2	10	2	10
4853	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4854	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	3	10	3	10	2	10	2	10
4855	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	2	10	2	10	3	10	3	10
4856	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4857	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4858	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	4	10	4	10	4	10	4	10
4859	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	4	10	3	10	5	10	5	10
4860	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4861	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4862	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4863	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	4	6	5	8	4	6	4	6	4	6
4864	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	2	10	1	10	4	6	4	6	2	3	1	1	1	1
4865	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	7	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3
4866	1	10	1	10	3	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	4	6	4	6	1	1	5	9	9	9
4867	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4868	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4869	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10
4870	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10
4871	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10

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	DR	DS	DT	DU	DV	DW	DX	DY	DZ	EA	EB	EC	ED	EE	EF	EG	EH	EI	EJ	EK	EL
1	LWUTI	LWUTI	URTI	URTI	LRTI	LRTI	TB	TB	LASFV	LASFV	YELFV	YELFV	DENFV	DENFV	MAL	MAL	ENFVR	ENFVR	HVAD	HVAD	UPU
4846	2	9	2	9	2	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	6	10	1	9	1	9	1
4847	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	6	10	1	10	1	9	1
4848	5	8	2	8	2	8	1	9	1	8	1	8	1	9	4	9	5	9	2	9	1
4849	3	8	2	8	2	8	1	8	1	8	1	8	1	8	6	10	2	9	2	9	1
4850	2	10	2	10	2	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	2	10	4	10	1
4851	2	10	2	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1
4852	2	10	2	10	2	10	2	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1
4853	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	6	10	1	10	1	10	1
4854	2	10	2	10	2	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1
4855	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	3	10	1	10	1
4856	1	10	3	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	3	10	1	10	1
4857	1	10	3	10	3	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	4	10	4	10	1
4858	4	10	4	10	4	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	5	10	1	10	1
4859	5	10	3	10	3	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	2	10	4	10	1	10	1
4860	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1
4861	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1
4862	1	10	3	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1
4863	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	4	6	6	9	2	3	1
4864	1	1	4	6	4	6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	8	1	1	1	1	1
4865	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1	1	1	1	1
4866	5	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	6	1	1	1	1	1
4867	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1
4868	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1
4869	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1
4870	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1
4871	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	5	10	1	10	1	10	1

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	EL	EM	EN	EO	EP	EQ	ER	ES	ET	EU	EV	EW	EX	EY	EZ	FA	FB	FC	FD	FE	FF	
1	UPUTI	UPUTI	LWUTI	LWUTI	URTI	URTI	TB	TB	LASFV	LASFV	YELFV	YELFV	DENFV	DENFV	CONF							
4846	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9						
4847	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9						
4848	6	9	6	9	2	9	2	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9						
4849	2	9	2	9	2	9	2	9	1	9	1	9	1	9	1	9						
4850	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4851	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4852	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4853	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4854	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4855	3	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4856	1	10	1	10	4	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4857	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	3	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4858	2	9	2	9	1	9	1	9	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4859	4	10	4	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4860	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4861	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4862	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4863	5	7	5	7	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4864	2	2	2	8	5	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						
4865	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						
4866	5	9	5	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						
4867	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4868	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4869	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4870	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						
4871	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10						

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APPENDIX B: RANDOM FOREST AND LIME CODE

```
pip install lime
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, accuracy_score, roc_auc_score,
confusion_matrix
#from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
#from xgboost import XGBClassifier
from sklearn.multioutput import MultiOutputClassifier
import pandas as pd
from google.colab import drive
import numpy as np
import lime.lime_tabular
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Mount Google Drive
drive.mount('/content/drive')
# Load the dataset
df = pd.read_csv('/content/drive/My Drive/Colab Notebooks/NFRF
ML/FD6D.csv')
#Using DataFrame.drop() method.
df2=df.drop(df.columns[0], axis=1)

X = df2.iloc[:, :32].values
Y = df2.iloc[:, 32:].values
# Function to evaluate classifiers
def evaluate(y_true, y_pred):
    print("Performance Evaluation:")
    print(classification_report(y_true, y_pred))
    print("Accuracy:", accuracy_score(y_true, y_pred))
    auc_score = roc_auc_score(y_true, y_pred, average='macro')
    print("AUC-ROC:", auc_score)
    #print("\nConfusion Matrix:")
    #print(confusion_matrix(y_true, y_pred))

# Split the dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size=0.2,
random_state=42)

# Define classifiers
rf = RandomForestClassifier()
# Create multi-output classifiers
multi_rf = MultiOutputClassifier(rf)

# Define parameter grids for grid search
```

```

param_grid_rf = {'estimator__n_estimators': [100, 200, 300],
'estimator__max_depth': [None, 10, 20]}

# Perform grid search for each classifier
rf_grid = GridSearchCV(multi_rf, param_grid_rf, cv=3, scoring='accuracy')

# Fit the classifiers to the baseline dataset
rf_grid.fit(X_train, y_train)
# Make predictions on the baseline dataset
rf_pred = rf_grid.best_estimator_.predict(X_test)

# Print evaluation metrics for the baseline dataset
print("Performance Evaluation for Baseline Dataset:")
print("\nRandom Forest:")
evaluate(y_test, rf_pred)

# LIME explanation plot
explainer = lime.lime_tabular.LimeTabularExplainer(
    X_train,
    feature_names=df2.columns[:32],
    class_names=['MAL', 'ENFVR', 'HVAD', 'UTI', 'RTI', 'TB'],
    discretize_continuous=True
)
i = np.random.randint(0, X_test.shape[0])

# Create a wrapper function for predict_proba to handle multi-output
def predict_proba_wrapper(x):
    predictions = rf_grid.best_estimator_.predict_proba(x)
    # predictions is a list of arrays, so we need to combine them into a single 2D
    array
    return np.column_stack(predictions)
exp = explainer.explain_instance(X_test[i], predict_proba_wrapper,
num_features=32)
# Extract feature importances for the selected instance
importance_df = pd.DataFrame(exp.as_list(), columns=['Feature', 'Importance'])
# Plot LIME explanation
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
sns.barplot(x='Importance', y='Feature', data=importance_df, palette='viridis')
plt.title('LIME Feature Importances')
plt.xlabel('Importance Score')
plt.ylabel('Feature')
plt.show()

```

APPENDIX C: XGBOOST AND LIME CODE

```
pip install lime
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, accuracy_score, roc_auc_score
from xgboost import XGBClassifier
from sklearn.multioutput import MultiOutputClassifier
import pandas as pd
from google.colab import drive
import numpy as np
import lime.lime_tabular
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
# Mount Google Drive
drive.mount('/content/drive')

# Load the dataset
df = pd.read_csv('/content/drive/My Drive/Colab Notebooks/NFRF
ML/FD6D.csv')
#Using DataFrame.drop() method.
df2=df.drop(df.columns[0], axis=1)

X = df2.iloc[:, :32].values
Y = df2.iloc[:, 32:].values
# Function to evaluate classifiers
def evaluate(y_true, y_pred):
    print("Performance Evaluation:")
    print(classification_report(y_true, y_pred))
    print("Accuracy:", accuracy_score(y_true, y_pred))
    auc_score = roc_auc_score(y_true, y_pred, average='macro')
    print("AUC-ROC:", auc_score)
    #print("LogLoss",log_loss)
    #print(confusion_matrix(y_true, y_pred))

# Split the dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size=0.2,
random_state=42)

# Define classifiers
xgb = XGBClassifier()

# Create multi-output classifiers
multi_xgb = MultiOutputClassifier(xgb)

# Define parameter grids for grid search
```

```

param_grid_xgb = {'estimator__n_estimators': [100, 200, 300],
                  'estimator__max_depth': [3, 5, 7]}
# Perform grid search for each classifier
xgb_grid = GridSearchCV(multi_xgb, param_grid_xgb, cv=3, scoring='accuracy')

# Fit the classifiers to the baseline dataset
xgb_grid.fit(X_train, y_train)
# Make predictions on the baseline dataset
xgb_pred = xgb_grid.best_estimator_.predict(X_test)

print("\nExtreme Gradient Boosting:")
evaluate(y_test, xgb_pred)

# LIME explanation plot
explainer = lime.lime_tabular.LimeTabularExplainer(
    X_train,
    feature_names=df2.columns[:32],
    class_names=['MAL', 'ENFVR', 'HVAD', 'UTI', 'RTI', 'TB'],
    discretize_continuous=True
)

i = np.random.randint(0, X_test.shape[0])

# Create a wrapper function for predict_proba to handle multi-output
def predict_proba_wrapper(x):
    predictions = xgb_grid.best_estimator_.predict_proba(x)
    # predictions is a list of arrays, so we need to combine them into a single 2D
    array
    return np.column_stack(predictions)
exp = explainer.explain_instance(X_test[i], predict_proba_wrapper,
                                num_features=32)
# Extract feature importances for the selected instance
importance_df = pd.DataFrame(exp.as_list(), columns=['Feature', 'Importance'])
# Plot LIME explanation
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
sns.barplot(x='Importance', y='Feature', data=importance_df, palette='viridis')
plt.title('LIME Feature Importances')
plt.xlabel('Importance Score')
plt.ylabel('Feature')
plt.show()

```

APPENDIX D: MLP AND LIME CODE

```
pip install lime
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, accuracy_score, roc_auc_score
from sklearn.neural_network import MLPClassifier
import pandas as pd
from google.colab import drive
import numpy as np
import lime.lime_tabular
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
# Mount Google Drive
drive.mount('/content/drive')

# Load the dataset
df = pd.read_csv('/content/drive/My Drive/Colab Notebooks/NFRF
ML/FD6D.csv')
#Using DataFrame.drop() method.
df2=df.drop(df.columns[0], axis=1)
X = df2.iloc[:, :32].values
Y = df2.iloc[:, 32:].values

# Function to evaluate classifiers
def evaluate(y_true, y_pred):
    print("Performance Evaluation:")
    print(classification_report(y_true, y_pred))
    print("Accuracy:", accuracy_score(y_true, y_pred))
    auc_score = roc_auc_score(y_true, y_pred, average='macro')
    print("AUC-ROC:", auc_score)
# Split the dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size=0.2,
random_state=42)

# Define MLP classifier
mlp = MLPClassifier()

# Define parameter grids for grid search
param_grid_mlp = {
    'hidden_layer_sizes': [(100,), (50, 50), (50, 25, 10)], # Example configurations
for hidden layers
    'activation': ['relu', 'tanh', 'logistic'], # Activation functions
    'alpha': [0.0001, 0.001, 0.01], # L2 penalty (regularization term) parameter
}
# Perform grid search for MLP classifier
mlp_grid = GridSearchCV(mlp, param_grid_mlp, cv=3, scoring='accuracy')
```

```

# Fit the MLP classifier to the training data
mlp_grid.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions on the test data using the best estimator found by grid search
mlp_pred = mlp_grid.best_estimator_.predict(X_test)

# Print evaluation metrics for the test data
print("Performance Evaluation for Test Dataset:")
evaluate(y_test, mlp_pred)

# LIME explanation plot
explainer = lime.lime_tabular.LimeTabularExplainer(
    X_train,
    feature_names=df2.columns[:32],
    class_names=['MAL', 'ENFVR', 'HVAD', 'UTI', 'RTI', 'TB'],
    discretize_continuous=True
)
# Select a random instance
i = np.random.randint(0, X_test.shape[0])

# Create a wrapper function for predict_proba to handle a single output
def predict_proba_wrapper_single_output(x):
    predictions = mlp_grid.best_estimator_.predict_proba(x)
    return predictions
exp = explainer.explain_instance(X_test[i], predict_proba_wrapper_single_output,
num_features=32)
# Extract feature importances for the selected instance
importance_df = pd.DataFrame(exp.as_list(), columns=['Feature', 'Importance'])
# Plot LIME explanation
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
sns.barplot(x='Importance', y='Feature', data=importance_df, palette='viridis')
plt.title('LIME Feature Importances')
plt.xlabel('Importance Score')
plt.ylabel('Feature')
plt.show()

```

APPENDIX E: SAMPLE PROMPT OF ML AND XAI RESULTS

Explain the LIME results below (disease or diseases and significant symptoms) to a physician with not more than 150 words:

Predictions ['Typhoid Fever Likely', 'HIV/AIDS Likely', 'Urinary Tract Infection Likely', 'Respiratory Tract Infection Likely', 'Tuberculosis Likely']

LIME Explanation;

BITTER TASTE IN MOUTH <= 1.00; -0.16758919765052108

Painful Urination > 1.00; -0.06605868111597245

Suprapubic_Pain > 1.00; -0.06550467141471979

Difficulty Breathing <= 1.00; 0.06071678705925383

Wheezing <= 1.00; 0.0590462921972035

Headache <= 1.00; -0.05826547312462451

CHILLS AND RIGORS <= 1.00; -0.05630271637802242

CHEST INDRAW <= 1.00; 0.04070095788472542

Generalized Body Pain > 3.00; 0.03974979336103006

1.00 < CATARRH <= 2.00; 0.03816070620416529

Urinary_Frequency > 1.00; -0.03770207672685268

ABDOMINAL PAIN > 3.00; -0.033902377938511155

2.00 < Fever <= 3.00; 0.032999053123995245

1.00 < Muscle and Body Pain <= 3.00; 0.03295097711760973

HGGDFever > 3.00; 0.032768000129691194

BLOODY URINE > 1.00; -0.029955841393233477

Cough (Initial Dry) <= 1.00; 0.026364166193042264

CHEST PAIN <= 1.00; 0.02354889167461192

Sore_Throat > 1.00; -0.021402483028506374

Lymph Node Swelling > 1.00; -0.0202552321969518

Vomiting > 2.00; 0.019057721531348118

Lethargy > 2.00; -0.017371438160508137

Mouth Ulcer > 1.00; -0.015856144250446513

Fatigue > 3.00; -0.015122895567807396

Generalized Rash <= 1.00; 0.014081682731125898

Foul Breath <= 1.00; 0.01260963643914623

1.00 < LWGDFever <= 3.00; 0.012187835432654306

CONSTIPATION <= 1.00; -0.012145436356090885

Night Sweat > 1.00; -0.010556292961671602

SWRFever > 2.00; -0.007451681601225083

Nausea > 2.00; -0.00406587833157149

Dry Cough > 1.00; -0.003064108573649665

APPENDIX F: ENHANCED DIAGNOSTIC SYSTEM CODE LISTING

```
# MAIN.PY
import flet as ft
from view import routes
from utility import LoadingView, default_theme, AlertControl, overlay

def metadata(page: ft.Page):
    page.title = "Work"
    page.theme_mode = 'Light'
    page.window.width = 320

def set_theme(page):
    save_colors = default_theme
    if not page.client_storage.get("theme_color"):
        page.client_storage.set('theme_color', save_colors)
    else:
        save_colors = page.client_storage.get("theme_color")
    page.theme = ft.Theme(
        color_scheme= ft.ColorScheme(
            primary= save_colors['accent'],
            primary_container= save_colors['container'],
            surface= save_colors['background'],
            on_surface= save_colors['text'],
            on_surface_variant= save_colors['text'],
        ),
    )

def add_overlays(page):
    page.overlay.append(ft.SnackBar(ft.Text("love"), duration= 2000))
    page.overlay.append(LoadingView())
    page.overlay.append(AlertControl())

def main(page: ft.Page): # add security
    metadata(page)
    add_overlays(page)
    set_theme(page)
    def route_change(e: ft.RouteChangeEvent) -> None:
        role = page.session.get('role')
        if page.session.get('authentication') is None:
            page.route = "/error" if page.route not in ['/', '/register'] else page.route
            role = None
        current_view = [i for i in page.views if page.route == i.route]
        if any(current_view): page.views.remove(current_view[0])
        if page.route in ['/dash', '/']: page.views.clear()
        main_route : dict = routes['global' if not role else role]
        page.views.append((
            main_route[page.route]
            if page.route in list(main_route.keys())
            else routes['global']['/']
        ))
        page.update()

def view_pop(e: ft.ViewPopEvent) -> None:
    page.views.pop()
```

```

top_view: ft.View = page.views.pop()
page.go(top_view.route)

page.on_route_change = route_change
page.on_view_pop = view_pop
page.go(page.route)
ft.app(main)

## Global views
# LOGIN
import fllet as ft
from utility import *

def validate(data: dict, page: ft.Page):
    overlays = overlay(page)
    overlays.loadingview.open(True, src="/Fast delivery.gif" ,text= 'Logging In') # change to a
decorator
    result = connect_backend(data=data, page=page)
    if result:
        result['data'].pop('password')
        page.session.set('authentication', result['data'])
        page.session.set('role', result['role'])
        page.go('/dash')
        errormessage(page, f"Success: {result['message']}")
    overlays.loadingview.open(False)

class LoginView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/",
            padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 30, vertical= 40),
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
        )

    self.form = FormField(
        controls=[
            customTextField(
                "Email address",
                type= 'email',
                data= 'email',
            ),
            customTextField(
                "Password",
                type= 'password',
                data= 'password',
            ),
            ft.Text("Recovery password", weight= BOLD, text_align= ft.TextAlign.END),
            ft.ElevatedButton(
                "Continue",
                expand= True,
                bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
                color= "white",
                style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
                    padding= 20,

```

```

        overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(
            0.5, CONTAINER_COLOR
        ),
    ),
    on_click= lambda _ : self.form.validate(
        lambda e: validate(e, self.page),
        data= {
            'email': 'attaikingsley@gmail.com',
            'password': 'phd@123456',
        },
    ),
),
],
spacing= 10,
expand= 5,
padding= 12,
)

self.controls = [
    ft.Column([
        ft.Column([
            ft.Text("Febrile Disease Diagnosis System", size= 25, text_align=
ft.TextAlign.CENTER, weight= BOLD),
            ft.Text("Welcome back, you've been missed!", weight= BOLD, text_align=
ft.TextAlign.CENTER),
        ],
        spacing= 50,
        horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
    ),
    ft.Container(expand= True),
    self.form,
    ft.Container(expand= True),
    ft.Text(
        weight= BOLD,
        spans= [
            ft.TextSpan("Not a member "),
            Link("Register now", color= ACCENT2_COLOR, onclick= lambda:
self.page.go('/register'))
        ]
    ),
], expand= True,
horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
)
]

```

REGISTER

```

import flet as ft
from utility import *

```

```

def validate(data: dict, page: ft.Page):
    overlays = overlay(page)
    overlays.loadingview.open(True, src="/Fast delivery.gif" ,text= 'Registering') # change to a
decorator # should test
    result = connect_backend(data=data, page=page, url_code= "register")
    if result:
        page.go('/')

```

```

    errormessage(page, f"Success: {result['message']}")
overlays.loadingview.open(False)

```

```

class RegisterView(ft.View): # add confirm password
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route="/register",
            padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 30, vertical= 40),
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
        )

        self.form = FormField(
            controls=[
                customTextField(
                    "Email address",
                    type= 'email',
                    data= 'email',
                ),
                customTextField(
                    "Full Name",
                    type= "full_name",
                    data= f'fname',
                ),
                ft.DropDown(
                    width=200,
                    label= "Sex",
                    options=[
                        ft.dropdown.Option("Male"),
                        ft.dropdown.Option("Female"),
                        # ft.dropdown.Option("Other"),
                    ],
                    data= "sex"
                ),
                customTextField(
                    "Phone Number",
                    type= 'phone_number',
                    data= 'mobile_number',
                ),
                customTextField(
                    "Password",
                    type= 'password',
                    data= 'password',
                ),
                customTextField( # create a new type confirm password
                    "Confirm Password",
                    type= 'password',
                    data= 'password',
                ),
                ft.Text("Recovery password", weight= BOLD, text_align= ft.TextAlign.END),
                ft.ElevatedButton(
                    "Continue",
                    expand= True,
                    bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
                    color= "white",
                    style= ft.ButtonStyle(

```

```

        shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
        padding= 20,
        overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(
            0.5, CONTAINER_COLOR
        ),
    ),
    on_click= lambda _: self.form.validate(
        lambda e: validate(e, self.page),
    ),
),
],
spacing= 10,
expand= 5,
padding= 12,
)

self.controls = [
    ft.Column([
        ft.Column([
            ft.Text("Create an account", size= 25, text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER, weight=
BOLD),
            ft.Text(
                # weight= BOLD,
                spans= [
                    ft.TextSpan("Already have an account? "),
                    Link("Login", color= ACCENT2_COLOR, onclick= lambda: self.page.go('/'))
                ]
            ),
        ],
        # spacing= 50,
        horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
    ),
    # ft.Container(expand= True),
    self.form,
    # ft.Container(expand= True),
    ft.Text(
        # weight= BOLD,
        spans= [
            ft.TextSpan("By clicking Create account you agree to Recognizes. "),
            Link("Terms of use", color= ACCENT2_COLOR),
            ft.TextSpan(" and "),
            Link("Private Policy", color= ACCENT2_COLOR),
        ],
        text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER
    ),
    ], expand= True,
    horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
    # alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN
)
]

def did_mount(self):
    return super().did_mount()

```

```

## HCW Views
# DASHBOARD

```

```

import flet as ft
from utility import *

class customMenuButton(ft.Container):
    def __init__(self, value, src, onclick= None, expand=None):
        super(self).__init__(
            bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
            padding= 10,
            border_radius= 10,
            on_click= onclick,
            expand= expand,
            on_hover= self.onhover,
        )
        self.content = ft.Column([
            ft.Image(
                src,
                width= 48,
                fit= ft.ImageFit.FIT_WIDTH,
            ),
            ft.Text(
                value,
                color= TEXT_COLOR,
                size= 11,
                weight= BOLD,
            ),
        ],
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER
        )

    def onhover(self, e):
        if e.data == 'true':
            # e.control.border= ft.border.all(1, TEXT_COLOR)
            e.control.scale = 1.05

        else:
            # e.control.border= None
            e.control.scale = 1

        self.update()

class DashboardView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super(self).__init__(
            route= "/dash",
            padding= 0,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN,
            bgcolor= BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            appbar= ft.AppBar(
                title= ft.Text("Dashboard", weight= BOLD, color= TEXT_COLOR),
                center_title= True,
                automatically_imply_leading= False,
                # elevation_on_scroll= 0,
                force_material_transparency= True,
            ),
        )

```

```

    # navigation_bar= customHCWNavbar(0)
)
self.NName = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
self.Name = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
self.Id = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
self.body = [
    # ft.Text("Dashboard", size= 20, weight= BOLD),
    ft.Column([
        ft.Container(
            ft.Row([
                ft.Container(
                    ft.Text(
                        'AP',
                        size= 20,
                        color= 'white',
                        ref= self.NName,
                        width= 30,
                        height= 30,
                        text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
                    ),
                    bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
                    # padding= 5,
                    alignment= ft.alignment.center,
                    border_radius= 50,
                    width= 40,
                    height= 40,
                ),
                ft.Column([
                    ft.Text(
                        'Ajuga Peterben', #add name
                        weight= BOLD,
                        ref= self.Name,
                        color= TEXT_COLOR,
                    ),
                    ft.Text(
                        'Health Care Worker',
                        color= TEXT_COLOR,
                        weight= BOLD,
                        size= 11,
                    ),
                ], spacing= 0),
            ],
            bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
            padding= 10,
            border_radius= 10,
        ),
    ],
    ft.Column([
        ft.Text(
            "Quick Menu",
            style= ft.TextStyle(
                decoration= ft.TextDecoration.UNDERLINE,
                decoration_color= TEXT_COLOR
            ),
            weight= BOLD,
            color= TEXT_COLOR
        )
    ]
)

```

```

),
ft.Row(
  controls= [
    customMenuButton(
      'Patient List',
      './patient.svg',
      lambda _: self.page.go('/Plist'),
      expand= 1,
    ),
    customMenuButton(
      'Register',
      './add.svg',
      lambda _: self.page.go('/reg'),
      expand= True
    ),
    customMenuButton(
      'Appointments',
      './twenty-two-calendar.svg',
      lambda _: self.page.go('/Happoint'),
      expand= 1,
    ),
  ],
),
ft.Row(
  controls=[
    customMenuButton(
      'Help',
      './help.svg',
      expand= True,
      onclick= lambda _: self.page.go('/help'),
    ),
    customMenuButton(
      'Settings',
      './settings.svg',
      expand= True,
      onclick= lambda _: self.page.go('/settings'),
    ),
    customMenuButton(
      'Log Out',
      './exit.svg',
      lambda _: logout(self.page),
      expand= True,
    ),
  ],
  # alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN
),
],
spacing= 10,
),
ft.Column(
  controls= [
    ft.Text(
      "Extra Features",
      style= ft.TextStyle(
        decoration= ft.TextDecoration.UNDERLINE,
        decoration_color= TEXT_COLOR

```

```

    ),
    weight= BOLD,
    color= TEXT_COLOR,
),
ft.Row([
    ft.Container(
        ft.Row([
            ft.Text(
                'Patient Requests',
                weight= BOLD,
                color= TEXT_COLOR,
            ),
            ft.Container(
                bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
                border_radius= 100,
                width= 8,
                height= 8,
                border= ft.border.all(1, ACCENT2_COLOR)
            ),
        ]),
        bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
        padding= 10,
        border_radius= 10,
        expand= True,
        on_click= lambda _ : self.page.go('/HPreq'),
    )
],
),
ft.Row([
    ft.Container(
        ft.Column([
            ft.Text(
                'Febral Chat',
                weight= BOLD,
                color= TEXT_COLOR,
            ),
            ft.Text(
                'Ask any febral questions.',
                size= 11,
                color= TEXT_COLOR
            ),
        ]),
        spacing= 0,
    ),
    bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
    padding= 10,
    border_radius= 10,
    expand= True,
    on_click= lambda _ : self.page.go('/chat'),
)
]),
],
spacing= 10,
),
ft.Row([
    ft.ElevatedButton(

```

```

        "View Personal Bio",
        expand= True,
        bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
        color= "white",
        style= ft.ButtonStyle(
            shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
            padding= 20
        ),
        on_click= lambda e: self.page.go('/bio')
    )
]),
]

self.controls = [
    ft.Container(
        ft.Column(
            self.body,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            expand= True,
        ),
        padding= ft.padding.symmetric(20, 40),
        bgcolor= BACKGROUND_COLOR,
    )
]

```

```

def did_mount(self):
    # self.controls[0].controls[0].height = self.page.height
    data = self.page.session.get('authentication')
    if data == None: data = {'name': 'Attai Kingsley'}
    self.Name.current.value = ".join(data['name']).title()
    NName = [i[0] for i in data['name'].split(' ')]
    if len(NName) > 2:
        NName = NName[:1]
    elif len(NName) == 1:
        NName *= 2
    self.NName.current.value = ".join(NName).upper()
    self.update()
    return super().did_mount()

```

DIAGOSIS.PY

```

import flet as ft
from utility import *

```

```

class Symptoms(ft.Container):
    def __init__(self, data, num, value= 1):
        super().__init__()
        self.IDs = data['n_name']
        sym = data['name']
        self.slider_value = ft.Ref[ft.Slider]()
        self. Ids = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
        self.content = ft.Column([
            ft.Row(
                controls=[
                    ft.Text(
                        f'{num}.',

```

```

        weight= BOLD,
        ref= self._Ids,
    ),
    ft.Container(
        content=ft.Text(
            f'How severe is the {sym}?',
            weight= BOLD,
        ),
        expand= True,
    ),
],
vertical_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.START
),
ft.Stack([
    ft.Column([
        ft.Container(
            ft.Row([
                ft.Text(f" {i+1} ")
                for i in range(5)
            ], alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN),
            padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 25),
        ),
    ], alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.END, height= 55),
    ft.Slider(
        value= value,
        divisions= 4,
        label= "{value}",
        min= 1,
        max= 5,
        active_color= ACCENT2_COLOR,
        ref= self.slider_value,
    ),
],
)
),
spacing= 0,
)

```

```

def assign_value(self, value):
    self.slider_value.current.value = value
    self.update()

```

```

@property
def slidervalue(self):
    return self.slider_value.current.value

```

```

@property
def record(self):
    return self.IDs, int(self.slider_value.current.value)

```

```

class DiagnosisView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/Dign",
            padding= 20,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,

```

```

        bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
    )
    self.symptoms_severity_dict = {}
    self.symptoms_list = ft.ListView(
        [],
        spacing= 20,
        padding= 10,
    )
    self.next_but = ft.ElevatedButton(
        "Next(0/6)",
        expand= True,
        bgcolor= "teal",
        color= "white",
        style= ft.ButtonStyle(
            shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
            padding= 20,
        ),
        on_click= lambda e: self.next_page(),
    )
    self.back_but = ft.ElevatedButton(
        'Exit',#"Back",
        # expand= 2,
        bgcolor= 'red',
        color= "white",
        style= ft.ButtonStyle(
            shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
            padding= 20
        ),
        on_click= lambda e: self.prev_page(),
    )
    self.controls = [
        ft.Text("History Taking & Examination", size= 18, weight= BOLD, text_align=
ft.TextAlign.CENTER),
        ft.Divider(1,1, ACCENT2_COLOR),
        ft.Container(
            self.symptoms_list,
            bgcolor= "white",
            padding= 10,
            expand= True,
            border_radius= 10
        ),
        ft.Row(
            controls= [
                self.back_but,
                self.next_but,
            ],
        ),
    ]

def next_page(self):
    self.back_but.text = f'Back'
    self.update()
    self.load_slider()
    if (self.current_page + 1) != self.maxpage:
        self.current_page += 1
        self.update_page(self.symptoms)

```

```

if (self.current_page + 1) == self.maxpage:
    self.next_but.text = f'Finish({self.current_page+1}/{self.maxpage})'
    self.update()
    self.update_slider(lambda e: e in self.symptoms_severity_dict)
else:
    self.overlays.loadingview.open(True)
    orderlist = ['ABDPN', 'BITAIM', 'BLDYURN', 'CTRH', 'CHSIND',
                'CHSPN', 'CHLNRIG', 'CNST', 'CGHDRV', 'DIFBRT',
                'DRYCGH', 'FTG', 'FVR', 'HGGDFVR', 'SWRFVR',
                'LWGDVFR', 'FOLBRT', 'GENBDYPN', 'GENRSH',
                'HDACH', 'LTG', 'LMPNDSWL', 'MSCBDYPN', 'MUTUCR',
                'NUS', 'NGTSWT', 'PNFLURNTN', 'SRTRT', 'SPPBPN',
                'URNFQC', 'VMT', 'WHZ']
    p_id = self.page.session.get('Current Patient')['patient_id']
    symp = [self.symptoms_severity_dict[i] for i in orderlist]

    data = {
        "patient_id": p_id,
        "symptoms": symp,
    }
    result = connect_predict(data=data, page=self.page)
    # time.sleep(0.5)
    self.overlays.loadingview.open(False)
    if result != None:
        self.page.session.set('diagnosis_result', result)
        self.page.go('/result')
    else:
        errormessage(self.page, 'Failed to diagnose: Check network')

def load_slider(self):
    for i in self.symptoms_list.controls:
        k, v = i.record
        self.symptoms_severity_dict[k] = v

def update_slider(self, condition= None):
    if condition == None: condition = lambda _: True
    for i in self.symptoms_list.controls:
        k, _ = i.record
        if condition(k):
            i.assign_value(self.symptoms_severity_dict[
                k
            ])

def prev_page(self):
    self.load_slider()
    if (self.current_page) != 0:
        self.current_page -= 1
    if (self.current_page) == 0:
        self.back_but.text = f'Exit'
        self.update()
    self.update_page(self.symptoms)
    for i in self.symptoms_list.controls:
        k, _ = i.record
        i.assign_value(self.symptoms_severity_dict[
            k
        ])

```

```

else:
    self.page.go("/Pdash")

def did_mount(self):
    self.overlays = overlay(self.page)
    if self.page.session.contains_key("sessiontime"):
        session_timer = self.page.session.get("sessiontime")
    else:
        session_timer = SessionManager(5)
        self.page.session.set("sessiontime", session_timer)
    if not session_timer.is_session_active():
        session_timer.start_session()
    self.overlays.loadingview.open(True, src="/medical-report.svg", text= 'Fetching
Symptoms')
    self.symptoms = connect_backend(page=self.page, url_code= '/get_symptoms')
    if self.symptoms:
        self.symptoms= self.symptoms['data']
        num_sym = len(self.symptoms)
        self.pages = 6
        self.current_page = 0
        self.maxpage = num_sym // self.pages if num_sym % self.pages == 0 else (num_sym //
self.pages)+1
        self.update_page(self.symptoms)
    else:
        self.page.go("/Pdash")
        self.overlays.loadingview.open(False)
    else:
        self.symptoms = saveload_cahce(self.page, "sympytoms", default= [])
        if self.symptoms:
            num_sym = len(self.symptoms)
            self.pages = 6
            self.current_page = 0
            self.maxpage = num_sym // self.pages if num_sym % self.pages == 0 else (num_sym //
self.pages)+1
            self.update_page(self.symptoms)
        else:
            self.page.go("/Pdash")
    saveload_cahce(self.page, "sympytoms", self.symptoms)
    return super().did_mount()

def update_page(self, symptoms):
    start, end = self.current_page*self.pages, (self.current_page+1)*self.pages
    self.symptoms_list.controls.clear()
    if (self.current_page+1)== self.maxpage:
        symptoms = symptoms[start: ]
    else:
        symptoms = symptoms[start:end]
    for n, i in enumerate(symptoms):
        self.symptoms_list.controls.append(
            Symptoms(i, (n+1) + (self.current_page*self.pages))
        )
    self.next_but.text = f'Next( {self.current_page+1} / {self.maxpage} )'
    self.update()
    self.symptoms_list.scroll_to(
        0,
    )

```

```

# HELP

import fltk as ft
from utility import *

class HelpView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/help",
            padding= 20,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN,
        )
        color = CONTAINER_COLOR
        self.userguide_control = ft.ListView([

            ],expand= True )
        # get all the patientdata
        self.controls = [
            ft.Row(
                controls=[
                    ft.IconButton(
                        ft.Icons.CLOSE,
                        on_click= lambda _: self.page.go('/dash'),
                        icon_color= color,
                        style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                            overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, color)
                        )
                    ),
                    ft.Text(
                        'User Guide',
                        expand= True,
                        weight= BOLD
                    ),
                ]
            ),
            self.userguide_control,
        ]

    def did_mount(self):
        # patients = connect_backend(page=self.page, url_code= '/get_patient')['message']
        # for i in patients:
        #     self.controls.append(
        #         ft.ElevatedButton(
        #             f" {i['first_name']} {i['last_name']}",
        #             on_click= lambda _: self.login_patient(i)
        #         )
        #     )
        # self.update()
        return super().did_mount()

    def login_patient(self, patient_info):
        self.page.session.set('Current Patient', patient_info)

```

```

self.page.go("/Pdash")

# MEDCHAT.PY

import flet as ft
from utility import *

class PromptTiles(ft.ElevatedButton):
    def __init__(self, content=None, on_click=None, text=None, icon=None, color=
ACCENT2_COLOR, **kwargs):
        super().__init__(
            text=text,
            icon=icon,
            content=content,
            style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(10),
                bgcolor= ft.Colors.TRANSPARENT,
                elevation= False,
                side= ft.BorderSide(1, color),
                color= color,
                overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, color),
            ),
            on_click=on_click,
            **kwargs,
        )

class ChatView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/chat",
            padding= 20,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor= BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            # scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN,
            # vertical_alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN
        )
        color = CONTAINER_COLOR
        drawer = ft.NavigationDrawer(
            # on_dismiss=handle_dismissal,
            on_change=self.handle_change,
            controls=[
                ft.Container(
                    content=ft.Row(
                        controls=[
                            ft.Text("History", weight= ft.FontWeight.BOLD),
                            ft.IconButton(
                                ft.Icons.NEW_LABEL,
                            ),
                        ],
                        alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN
                    ),
                    margin= 10
                ),
                ft.Divider(thickness=2),
                ft.NavigationDrawerDestination( # might change to something different

```

```

        label="Why are doctors constantly",
    ),
    ft.NavigationDrawerDestination(
        label="The importance of sex ed",
    ),
],
)
chat_side = ft.Column(
    controls=[
        ft.Container(
            content=ft.Column(
                controls=[
                    ft.TextField(
                        hint_text= "Ask MedGPT",
                        multiline= True,
                        # border_radius=20,
                        dense= True,
                        border= ft.InputBorder.NONE,
                        # bgcolor= ft.Colors.TRANSPARENT,
                    ),
                    ft.Row(
                        controls=[
                            ft.Text("0/1000", color= TEXT_COLOR, size= 12),
                            ft.ElevatedButton(
                                content= ft.Icon(
                                    ft.Icons.SUBDIRECTORY_ARROW_RIGHT,
                                    color= "white",
                                    size= 15
                                ),
                                style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                                    bgcolor=ACCENT2_COLOR,
                                    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(10),
                                    padding= 10
                                )
                            )
                        ],
                        alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.END
                    )
                ],
            ),
        ],
        bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
        padding= 10,
        border_radius= 10,
    ),
    ft.Text(
        "The Gpt can make mistakes. Check important info.",
        size= 12,
    )
],
)
middle_part = ft.Column( # improve look
    controls=[
        ft.Text(
            "How can i help?",
            size= 25,
            weight= ft.FontWeight.BOLD,

```

```

    ),
    ft.Text(
        "Use one of the most common prompts below or use your own to begin."
    ),
    ft.Row(
        controls=[
            PromptTiles(
                text= "What is medgpt?"
            ),
            PromptTiles(
                text= "Why are drug not effective on certain diseases?"
            ),
            PromptTiles(
                text= "What is febra?"
            ),
            PromptTiles(
                text= "The role of Ai in diagnosis?"
            )
        ],
        wrap= True
    )
]
)
# get all the patientdata
self.controls = [
    ft.Row(
        controls=[
            ft.IconButton(
                ft.Icons.BOOK,
                on_click=lambda e: self.page.open(drawer)
            ),
            ft.Text("MedGpt"),
            ft.IconButton(
                ft.Icons.CLOSE,
                on_click=lambda e: self.page.go('/dash')
            ),
        ],
        alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN
    ),
    # ft.Container(expand=True),
    ft.Column( # might change to back
        controls=[
            middle_part,
            chat_side,
        ],
        # alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.CENTER,
        expand= True,
        scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN
    ),
    # ft.Container(expand=True),
]

def did_mount(self):
    return super().did_mount()

def handle_change(self, e):

```

```

self.page.add(ft.Text(f"Selected Index changed: {e.selected_index}"))
# page.close(drawer) # close the drawer after execution

```

```

# REGISTRATION.PY

```

```

import flet as ft
from utility import *
# from datetime import datetime

```

```

def validate(data: dict, page: ft.Page):
    # data = {'patient_last_name': 'ebong', 'patient_first_name': 'chukwu', 'patient_dob':
datetime.strptime('09/06/2000', r"%m/%d/%Y").isoformat(), 'patient_email': '2000@gmail.com',
'patient_mobile_no': '08767594456', 'patient_address': 'bitch', 'patient_gender': 'female',
'nok_phone': '08767594456', 'nok_name': 'bitch gooo', 'nok_address': 'bitch'}
    result = connect_backend(data=data, page=page, url_code='add_patient')
    if result:
        page.session.set('Current Patient', result['data'])
        page.go('/Pdash')
        errormessage(page, f"Success: {result['message']}")

```

```

class RegistrationView(ft.View):

```

```

    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/reg",
            padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 25, vertical= 40),
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            navigation_bar= customHCWNavbar(2),
            # appbar= ft.AppBar(),
        )

```

```

self.form = FormField([
    ft.Text("Patient (Details)", weight= BOLD),
    customTextField(
        "last name".title(),
        data= f'last_name',
    ),
    customTextField(
        "first name".title(),
        data= f'first_name',
    ),
    customTextField("MM/DD/YYYY", type= 'date', data= 'dob'), # add custom
    customTextField(
        "Email Address",
        type= 'email',
        data= f'email',
    ),
    customTextField(
        "Phone Number",
        type= 'phone_number',
        data= f'mobile_number',
    ),
    customTextField(
        "Home Address",
        validate= lambda e: (

```

```

        f"Please enter a valid Address"
        if not e
            else None
    ),
    data= f'address',
),
ft.RadioGroup(
    value= 0,
    content=ft.Row([
        ft.Radio(label='male', value= 0),
        ft.Radio(label='female', value= 1),
        ft.Radio(label='other', value= 2)
    ]),
    data= 'gender'
),
ft.Text("Next of kin", weight= BOLD),
customTextField(
    "Next of kin (Phone Number)",
    type= 'phone_number',
    data= f'nok_phone',
),
customTextField(
    "Next of kin (Full Name)",
    validate= lambda e: (
        f"Please enter a valid Name"
        if not e or len(e) < 6
        else None
    ),
    data= f'nok_name',
),
customTextField(
    "Next of kin (Home Address)",
    validate= lambda e: (
        f"Please enter a valid Address"
        if not e
        else None
    ),
    data= f'nok_address',
),
ft.ElevatedButton(
    "Register",
    expand= True,
    bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
    color= "white",
    style= ft.ButtonStyle(
        shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
        padding= 20
    ),
    on_click= lambda _: self.form.validate(
        lambda e: validate(e, self.page)
    ),
)
],
expand= True,
spacing= 10,
padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 15)

```

```

)

self.controls = [
    ft.Column([
        ft.Text("Patient Registration", size= 20, weight= BOLD),
        self.form,
        ft.Text(
            size= 11,
            spans= [
                ft.TextSpan("By clicking Create account you agree to Recognizes\n"),
                Link("Terms of use", color= ACCENT2_COLOR),
                ft.TextSpan(" and "),
                Link("Private Policy", color= ACCENT2_COLOR)
            ],
            text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
        ),
    ],
    expand= True,
    horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
    spacing= 10,
)
]

```

```

# RESULT.PY
import fllet as ft
from utility import *

class ResultView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/result",
            padding= 40,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
        )
        self.prediction_ref = ft.Ref[ft.Row]()
        self.img_ref = ft.Ref[ft.Image]()
        self.explanation_ref = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
        self.controls = [
            #Interpretable
            ft.Text("Explainable Diagnosis Results", size= 18, weight= BOLD, text_align=
ft.TextAlign.CENTER),
            ft.Divider(height= 1, color= ft.Colors.ON_SURFACE),
            ft.ListView([
                ft.Column([
                    ft.Text(
                        'Provisional Diagnoses:',
                        weight= BOLD,
                    ),
                    ft.Row(
                        controls=[
                            self.tags(i)
                            for i in ['Typhoid Fever Likely', 'HIV/AIDS Likely', 'Urinary Tract Infection
Likely',
                                'Respiratory Tract Infection Likely', 'Tuberculosis Likely']
                        ],
                        wrap= True,
                        ref= self.prediction_ref,
                        visible= False,
                    ),
                ], spacing= 0),
            ft.Container(
                ft.Column([
                    ft.Image("./plot.png", ref= self.img_ref)
                ], spacing= 0),
                bgcolor= 'White',
                padding= 10,
                border_radius= 10,
                expand= True
            ),
            ft.Container(
                ft.Column([
                    ft.Text(
                        size= 10,
                        ref= self.explanation_ref,
                        text_align= ft.TextAlign.JUSTIFY
                    ),
                ], spacing= 0),

```

```

        bgcolor= 'White',
        padding= 10,
        border_radius= 10,
        expand= True
    ),
], spacing= 10, expand= True),
ft.Row([
    ft.ElevatedButton(
        "Return Home", # Done
        expand= True,
        bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
        color= "white",
        style= ft.ButtonStyle(
            shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
            padding= 20
        ),
        on_click= lambda e: self.page.go('/dash')
    )
]),
]

def tags(self, value):
    return ft.Container(
        ft.Text(value, color= ACCENT2_COLOR)
    ,
        bgcolor= 'white',
        border= ft.border.all(1, ACCENT2_COLOR),
        padding= 10,
        border_radius= 5,
    )

def did_mount(self): # shift this to the loading page
    self.results = self.page.session.get('diagnosis_result')
    predictions = self.results['predictions']
    img_path = self.results['img_path']
    explanation = self.results['explanation']
    self.prediction_ref.current.controls.clear()
    if not len(predictions):
        self.prediction_ref.current.controls.append(ft.Text("No Disease"))
        explanation = "No disease"
    else:
        for i in predictions: # create none
            self.prediction_ref.current.controls.append(self.tags(i))
    self.prediction_ref.current.visible = True
    self.update()
    self.explanation_ref.current.value = explanation
    self.img_ref.current.src = img_path
    patient = self.page.session.get('Current Patient')
    hcw = self.page.session.get('authentication')
    data = {
        "patient_id": patient["patient_id"],
        "diagnosed_at": datetime.datetime.now().isoformat(),
        "hc_provider_id": hcw["hc_provider_id"],
        "details": f"Predicton: {predictions}\n\nExplanation: {explanation}",
        "recommendation": "See a doctor" if len(predictions) else 'You\'re fine'
    }
}

```

```

print(data)
# connect_backend(self.page, data, "add_diagnosis")
return super().did_mount()

```

```
# SETTINGS.PY
```

```

import flet as ft
from utility import *

```

```

class SettingsView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route="/settings",
            spacing=10,
            bgcolor=BACKGROUND_COLOR,
        )

    self.base_color_picker = ft.Row(
        controls=[
            ft.Container(
                content=ft.Row(
                    controls=[
                        ft.Container(
                            bgcolor=i[j],
                            border_radius=90,
                            expand=True,
                        )
                        for j in ['background', 'accent', 'text']
                    ],
                    spacing=0,
                ),
                width=20,
                height=20,
                border=ft.border.all(4, ft.Colors.SURFACE_TINT),
                border_radius=90,
                on_hover=self.onhover,
                on_click=self.change_color,
                data=i,
            )
            for i in THEMES_LIST
        ],
    )

    self.theme_options = ft.Dropdown(
        value="English",
        options=[
            ft.dropdown.Option(i)
            for i in ["Mandarin Chinese", "Spanish", "English", "Hindi",
                "Bengali", "Portuguese, Russian, Japanese",
                "Yue Chinese", "Vietnamese, Turkish, Wu Chinese",
                "Marathi", "Telugu, Western Punjabi, Korean",
                "Tamil", "Egyptian Arabic, Standard German, French",
                "Urdu", "Javanese, Italian, Iranian Persian",
                "Gujarati, Hausa, Bhojpuri", "Levantine Arabic",
                "Southern Min"
            ]
        ],
    )

```

```

        dense= True,
        prefix_icon= ft.Icons.LANGUAGE,
        focused_border_color= TEXT_COLOR,
        border_radius= 15,
    )
    self.setting_view = ft.ListView(
        controls= [
            ft.Text('Appearance', weight= BOLD, size= 18, color= TEXT_COLOR),
            ft.Text('Change how the UI looks and feels in the app.', color= TEXT_COLOR),
            ft.Divider(1,1, color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.2, TEXT_COLOR)),
            ft.Text('Theme-Colors', weight= BOLD, color= TEXT_COLOR),
            ft.Text('Update your dashboard with a new style.', size= 13, color= TEXT_COLOR),
            ft.Column(
                controls=[
                    self.base_color_picker,
                ]
            ),
            ft.Divider(1,1, color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.2, TEXT_COLOR)),
            ft.Text('Language', weight= BOLD, color= TEXT_COLOR),
            ft.Text('Change the language.', size= 13, color= TEXT_COLOR),
            self.theme_options,
        ],
        expand= True,
        padding= 20,
        spacing= 10,
    )
    self.controls = [
        ft.Row(
            controls=[
                ft.IconButton(
                    ft.Icons.CLOSE,
                    on_click= lambda _: self.page.go('/dash'),
                    icon_color= TEXT_COLOR,
                    style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                        overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, TEXT_COLOR),
                    )
                ),
                ft.Text(
                    'Settings',
                    expand= True,
                    weight= BOLD,
                    color= TEXT_COLOR
                ),
            ],
        ),
        self.setting_view,
    ]

```

```

def onhover(self, e):
    if e.data == 'false':
        e.control.border= ft.border.all(4, ft.Colors.SURFACE_TINT)
        e.control.scale = 1
    else:
        e.control.border= ft.border.all(1, ft.Colors.SURFACE_TINT)
        e.control.scale = 1.2
    self.update()

```

```

def did_mount(self):
    self.update()
    return super().did_mount()

def change_color(self, e):
    save_colors = e.control.data
    self.page.theme.color_scheme= ft.ColorScheme(
        primary= save_colors['accent'],
        primary_container= save_colors['container'],
        surface= save_colors['background'],
        on_surface= save_colors['text'],
        on_surface_variant= save_colors['text'],
    )
    self.page.client_storage.set('theme_color', save_colors)
    self.page.update()

# BIO.PY
import flet as ft
from utility import *

class ProfileTile(ft.Column):
    def __init__(self, title, content, ref, **kwargs):
        self.title = title
        self.content = content
        super().__init__(
            controls= [
                self.title,
                self.content,
            ],
            ref= ref,
            **kwargs
        )

    def update_content(self, value):
        self.content.value = value
        self.update()

    @property
    def _value(self):
        return self.content.value

class BioView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/bio",
            spacing= 10,
            bgcolor= BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN,
            padding= 20
        )

        self.base_color_picker = ft.Row(
            controls=[
                ft.Container(
                    content=ft.Row(

```

```

        controls=[
            ft.Container(
                bgcolor=i[j],
                border_radius= 90,
                expand= True,
            )
            for j in ['background', 'accent', 'text']
        ],
        spacing= 0,
    ),
    width= 20,
    height= 20,
    border= ft.border.all(4, ft.Colors.SURFACE_TINT),
    border_radius= 90,
    on_hover= self.onhover,
    on_click= self.change_color,
    data= i,
)
for i in THEMES_LIST
],
)
self.theme_options = ft.Dropdown(
    value= "English",
    options=[
        ft.dropdown.Option(i)
        for i in ["Mandarin Chinese", "Spanish", "English", "Hindi",
            "Bengali", "Portuguese, Russian, Japanese",
            "Yue Chinese", "Vietnamese, Turkish, Wu Chinese",
            "Marathi", "Telugu, Western Punjabi, Korean",
            "Tamil", "Egyptian Arabic, Standard German, French",
            "Urdu", "Javanese, Italian, Iranian Persian",
            "Gujarati, Hausa, Bhojpuri", "Levantine Arabic",
            "Southern Min"
        ]
    ],
    dense= True,
    prefix_icon= ft.Icons.LANGUAGE,
    focused_border_color= TEXT_COLOR,
    border_radius= 15,
)
self.setting_view = ft.ListView(
    controls= [
        ft.Text('Appearance', weight= BOLD, size= 18, color= TEXT_COLOR),
        ft.Text('Change how the UI looks and feels in the app.', color= TEXT_COLOR),
        ft.Divider(1,1, color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.2, TEXT_COLOR)),
        ft.Text('Theme-Colors', weight= BOLD, color= TEXT_COLOR),
        ft.Text('Update your dashboard with a new style.', size= 13, color= TEXT_COLOR),
        ft.Column(
            controls=[
                self.base_color_picker,
            ]
        ),
        ft.Divider(1,1, color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.2, TEXT_COLOR)),
        ft.Text('Language', weight= BOLD, color= TEXT_COLOR),
        ft.Text('Change the language.', size= 13, color= TEXT_COLOR),
        self.theme_options,
    ],
)

```

```

    ],
    expand= True,
    padding= 20,
    spacing= 10,
)

self.id_ref = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
self.nname_ref = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
self.name_ref = ft.Ref[ProfileTile]()
self.email_ref = ft.Ref[ProfileTile]()
self.number_ref = ft.Ref[ProfileTile]()
self.sex_ref = ft.Ref[ProfileTile]()

self.controls = [
    ft.Column(
        controls=[
            ft.Row(
                controls=[
                    ft.IconButton(
                        ft.Icons.CLOSE,
                        on_click= lambda _: self.page.go('/dash'),
                        icon_color= TEXT_COLOR,
                        style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                            overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, TEXT_COLOR),
                        )
                    ),
                    ft.Text(
                        # 'Bio',
                        "Personal Information",
                        # expand= True,
                        # weight= BOLD,
                        # color= TEXT_COLOR
                    ),
                    ft.Container(
                        content= ft.Text("HCW", color= ACCENT2_COLOR),
                        bgcolor= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, ACCENT2_COLOR),
                        border= ft.border.all(1, ACCENT2_COLOR),
                        border_radius= 5,
                        padding= 5
                    ),
                ],
                alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN,
            ),
        ],
    ),
    ft.Row(
        controls=[
            ft.Column(
                controls= [
                    ft.Container(
                        content=ft.Container(
                            content= ft.Text(
                                "AD",
                                size= 40,
                                weight= ft.FontWeight.BOLD,
                                color= 'White',

```

```

        ref= self.nname_ref
    ),
    alignment= ft.alignment.center,
    bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
    width= 90,
    height= 90,
    border_radius= 200
),
border= ft.border.all(2, ACCENT2_COLOR),
border_radius= 200,
padding= 3,
),
ft.Text(
    "Aks-0000023",
    ref= self.id_ref,
)
],
# expand= True,
),
],
alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.CENTER
),
ft.Text("Personal Info", weight= ft.FontWeight.W_500),
ProfileTile(
    ft.Text("Name"),
    ft.TextField(
        hint_text= "Enter your name",
        prefix_icon= ft.Icons.PERSON
    ),
    ref= self.name_ref
),
ProfileTile(
    ft.Text("Email address"),
    ft.TextField(
        hint_text= "Enter your email address",
        prefix_icon= ft.Icons.EMAIL
    ),
    ref= self.email_ref
),
ProfileTile(
    ft.Text("Phone number"),
    ft.TextField(
        hint_text= "Enter your phone number",
        prefix_icon= ft.Icons.PHONE
    ),
    ref= self.number_ref
),
ProfileTile(
    ft.Text("Gender"),
    ft.Dropdown(
        # width=200,
        label= "Sex",
        icon= ft.Icons.PERSON_PIN,
        options=[
            ft.dropdown.Option("Male"),
            ft.dropdown.Option("Female"),

```

```

        ],
        data= "sex"
    ),
    ref= self.sex_ref
),
ft.Row(
    controls=[
        ft.ElevatedButton( # add edit logic
            "Save changes",
            expand= True,
            bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
            color= "white",
            style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
                padding= 20,
                overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(
                    0.5, "white"
                )
            ),
            # on_click= lambda _: self.form.bypassed_validate(
            #     lambda e: validate(e, self.page),
            #     data= {
            #         'email': 'attaikingsley@gmail.com',
            #         'password': 'phd@123456',
            #     },
            #     # nobypass= True,
            # ),
        ],
    ),
]
),
]

def onhover(self, e):
    if e.data == 'false':
        e.control.border= ft.border.all(4, ft.Colors.SURFACE_TINT)
        e.control.scale = 1
    else:
        e.control.border= ft.border.all(1, ft.Colors.SURFACE_TINT)
        e.control.scale = 1.2
    self.update()

def did_mount(self): # add cache
    info = self.page.session.get('authentication')
    self.id_ref.current.value = f"Aks-{{int(info['hc_provider_id']):06d}}"
    NName = [i[0] for i in info['name'].split(' ')]
    if len(NName) > 2:
        NName = NName[:1]
    elif len(NName) == 1:
        NName *= 2
    self.nname_ref.current.value = ".join(NName).upper()
    self.name_ref.current.update_content(info["name"])
    self.email_ref.current.update_content(info["email"])
    self.number_ref.current.update_content(info["mobile_number"])
    self.sex_ref.current.update_content(info["sex"])
    self.update()
    return super().did_mount()

```

```

def change_color(self, e):
    save_colors = e.control.data
    self.page.theme.color_scheme= ft.ColorScheme(
        primary= save_colors['accent'],
        primary_container= save_colors['container'],
        surface= save_colors['background'],
        on_surface= save_colors['text'],
        on_surface_variant= save_colors['text'],
    )
    self.page.client_storage.set('theme_color', save_colors)
    self.page.update()

# APPOINTMENT.PY
import fllet as ft
from utility import *

class AppointmentListControl(ft.ListView):
    def __init__(self, head_text:str, inbtw_text:str, onclick= None):
        super().__init__(
            expand= True,
            spacing= 10,
            padding= 10,
        )
        self.onclick = onclick
        self.__items = []
        self.header = ft.Text(
            head_text, # 'Request for access to full medical history'
            weight= BOLD,
            size= 12,
            expand= True,
        )
        self.inbtw = ft.Text(
            inbtw_text,
            weight= BOLD,
            size= 12,
            expand= True,
        )

    def base_item(self, i):
        item = ft.ElevatedButton(
            content= ft.Row(
                controls=[
                    ft.Column(
                        controls=[
                            ft.Text(
                                i['name'],
                                color= TEXT_COLOR,
                                size= 10,
                            ),
                            ft.Text(
                                i['type'],
                                color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.8, TEXT_COLOR),
                                size= 10,
                            ),
                            ft.Text(

```

```

        i['date'].strftime(r"%a, %b %d %Y, %I:%M %p"),
        color= TEXT_COLOR,
        size= 10,
    ),
    ],
    spacing= 0,
),
# ft.Icon(ft.Icons.EMAIL, color= TEXT_COLOR),
]
),
data= i,
on_click= self.onclick,
style= ft.ButtonStyle(
    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(5),
    padding= 10,
    bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
    overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, BACKGROUND_COLOR),
),
clip_behavior= ft.ClipBehavior.HARD_EDGE,
)
return item

def special_item(self, i):
    item = ft.ElevatedButton(
        content= ft.Column(
            controls=[
                ft.Row(
                    controls=[
                        ft.Image(
                            './calendar.svg',
                            # height= 50,
                            width= 50,
                            color= TEXT_COLOR,
                            color_blend_mode= ft.BlendMode.MODULATE,
                        ),
                        ft.Column(
                            controls=[
                                ft.Text(
                                    i['name'],
                                    color= TEXT_COLOR,
                                    size= 10,
                                ),
                                ft.Text(
                                    i['type'],
                                    color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.8, TEXT_COLOR),
                                    size= 10,
                                ),
                                ft.Text(
                                    i['date'].strftime(r"%a, %b %d %Y, %I:%M %p"),
                                    color= TEXT_COLOR,
                                    size= 10,
                                ),
                            ],
                            spacing= 0,
                        ),
                    ],
                    spacing= 0,
                ),
            ],
        ),
    )

```

```

    ),
    ft.Row(
        controls=[
            ft.ElevatedButton(
                'Copy Phonenummer',
                icon= ft.Icons.COPY,
                expand= True,
                style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                    padding= 0,
                    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(5),
                    bgcolor= TEXT_COLOR,
                    color= BACKGROUND_COLOR,
                ),
                height= 30,
            ),
        ],
    ),
],
),
data= i,
on_click= self.onclick,
style= ft.ButtonStyle(
    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(10),
    padding= 10,
    bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
    overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, BACKGROUND_COLOR)
),
clip_behavior= ft.ClipBehavior.HARD_EDGE,
)
return item

```

```

def append(self, item):
    _length_of_items = len(self.__items)
    head_item = self.special_item(item)
    item = self.base_item(item)
    if _length_of_items == 0:
        self.controls = [
            self.header,
            head_item,
        ]
    elif _length_of_items == 1:
        self.controls.extend([
            self.inbtw,
            item,
        ])
    else:
        self.controls.append(item)
        self.__items.append(item)
        self.update()

def search(self, query: str):
    if query != "":
        self.controls = [item for item in self.__items if item.data['date'] == query]
    else:
        self.clear()
        self.update()

```

```

def clear(self):
    self.controls.clear()
    _length_of_items = len(self.__items)
    if _length_of_items == 1:
        self.controls = [self.header, self.__items[0]]
    elif _length_of_items > 1:
        self.controls = [
            self.header,
            self.special_item(self.__items[0].data),
            self.inbtw,
            *self.__items[1:]
        ]
    self.update()

def remove(self, __id):
    self.__items = [item for item in self.__items if __id != item.id] # use id of the
    self.clear()

class HCWAppointmentsView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route="/Happoint",
            padding= 20,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            navigation_bar= customHCWNavbar(3),
            floating_action_button= ft.FloatingActionButton(
                icon= ft.Icons.ADD,
                on_click= lambda e: self.page.go('/Pappoint'),
            ),
            # appbar= ft.AppBar(),
        )
        self._body_controls = AppointmentListControl(
            'Next Appointment',
            'Upcoming Appointments',
            onclick= self.onclick,
        )
        self.calendersearch = CalenderSearchcontrol(on_change=self.onsearch)
        page_padding = None
        self.controls = [
            ft.Container(
                content=ft.Row(
                    controls=[
                        # ft.IconButton(
                        #     ft.Icons.CHEVRON_LEFT,
                        #     on_click= lambda _: self.page.go('/dash'),
                        #     icon_color= color,
                        #     style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                        #         overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, color)
                        #     )
                        # ),
                        # ),
                        ft.Text(
                            'Follow up appointments',
                            # expand= True,
                            weight= BOLD,

```

```

        size= 17,
        text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
    ),
    # ft.Container(width= 15),
],
alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.CENTER,
# expand= True,
),
padding= page_padding,
),
ft.Container(
    content= self.calendersearch,
    padding= page_padding
),
self._body_controls,
]

```

```

def did_mount(self):
    self.overlay = overlay(self.page)
    dt_obj = datetime.datetime.strptime("Sat, Sep 7 2024", r"%a, %b %d %Y")
    items = [{
        'date': dt_obj,
        'id': "AKS-00002",
        'request_id': '000002',
        'name': 'Ajuga Peterben',
        'type': "Check up",
    }]*10
    # self.user =
    # patients = connect_backend(page=self.page, url_code= '/get_patient')['message']
    for i in items:
        self._body_controls.append(
            i
        )
    self.messages = self._body_controls.controls.copy()
    self.update()
    return super().did_mount()

```

```

def onclick(self, e):
    self.control_excess()
    # print(e.control.data) # implement e.data
    alertcontrol: AlertControl = self.overlay.alertcontrol
    alertcontrol.change_view(
        controls=[
            ft.Text(
                "Ajuga Peterben",
                weight= BOLD,
            ),
            ft.Column(
                controls=[
                    ft.Text(
                        "Time",
                        weight= BOLD,
                    ),
                    ft.Text("24 Aug, 3:30 pm"),
                ],
                spacing= 0,
            )
        ]
    )

```



```

    alertcontrol.excess = self.control_excess

def control_excess(self, value= False):
    self.navigation_bar.visible = value
    self.floating_action_button.visible = value
    self.update()

def onsearch(self):
    date = self.calendersearch.date
    if date:
        self._body_controls.search(date)
    else:
        self._body_controls.clear()
    self.update()

def will_unmount(self):
    self.overlay.alertcontrol.excess = None
    return super().will_unmount()

# HCWPATIENTREQUEST.PY
import fllet as fl
from utility import *

class HCWPatientRequestView(fl.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/HPreq",
            padding= 20,
            horizontal_alignment= fl.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
        )
        color = TEXT_COLOR
        self.calendersearch = CalenderSearchcontrol(on_change=self.onsearch)
        page_padding = None #fl.padding.only(right= 15)
        self._body_controls = fl.ListView(
            controls= [

                ],
            expand= True,
            spacing= 10,
            padding= page_padding,
        )
        self.controls = [
            fl.Container(
                content=fl.Row(
                    controls=[
                        fl.IconButton(
                            fl.Icons.CHEVRON_LEFT,
                            on_click= lambda _: self.page.go('/dash'),
                            icon_color= color,
                            style= fl.ButtonStyle(
                                overlay_color= fl.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, color)
                            )
                        ),
                        fl.Text(
                            'Request Notification',

```

```

        # expand= True,
        weight= BOLD,
        size= 17,
        text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
    ),
    ft.Container(width= 15),
],
alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.SPACE_BETWEEN,
# expand= True,
),
padding= page_padding,
),
ft.Container(
    content= self.calendersearch,
    padding= page_padding
),
ft.Container(
    content=ft.Row(
        controls=[
            ft.Text(
                'Request for access to full medical history',
                weight= BOLD,
                size= 12,
                expand= True,
            ),
        ]
    ),
    padding= page_padding
),
self._body_controls,
ft.Container(
    content=ft.Text(
        'Unsuccessful responses will be removed automatically after leaving this page.',
        weight= BOLD,
        size= 10,
        expand= True,
        text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
    ),
    padding= page_padding
),
]

def did_mount(self):
    self.overlay = overlay(self.page)
    dt_obj = datetime.datetime.strptime("Sat, Sep 7 2024", r"%a, %b %d %Y")
    items = [{
        'date': dt_obj,
        'id': "AKS-00002"
    }]*10
    # patients = connect_backend(page=self.page, url_code= '/get_patient')['message']
    for i in items:
        self._body_controls.controls.append(
            ft.ElevatedButton(
                content= ft.Row(
                    controls=[
                        ft.Icon(ft.Icons.EMAIL, color= TEXT_COLOR),

```

```

        ft.Column(
            controls=[
                ft.Text(
                    i['date'].strftime(r"%a, %b %d %Y, %I:%M %p"),
                    color= TEXT_COLOR,
                    size= 13
                ),
                ft.Text(
                    f"Patient ID: {i['id']}",
                    color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.8, TEXT_COLOR)
                    # size= 10,
                ),
            ],
            spacing= 0,
        ),
    ]
),
data= i,
on_click= self.onclick,
style= ft.ButtonStyle(
    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(10),
    padding= 10,
    bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
    overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, BACKGROUND_COLOR)
)
)
)
self.messages = self._body_controls.controls.copy()
self.update()
return super().did_mount()

```

```

def onclick(self, e):
    # print(e.control.data)
    alertcontrol: AlertControl = self.overlay.alertcontrol
    alertcontrol.change_view(
        controls=[
            ft.Text(
                "Request for access to full medical history",
                weight= BOLD,
            ),
            ft.Text(
                "Ajuga Peterben",
                weight= BOLD,
            ),
            ft.Column(
                controls=[
                    ft.Text(
                        "Time",
                        weight= BOLD,
                    ),
                    ft.Text("24 Aug, 3:30 pm"),
                ],
                spacing= 0,
            ),
            ft.Column(
                controls=[

```

```

        ft.Text(
            "Patient Details",
            weight= BOLD,
        ),
        ft.Text("Phone number: 08140147868"),
    ],
    spacing= 0,
),
ft.Column(
    controls=[
        ft.Text(
            "Reason",
            weight= BOLD,
        ),
        ft.Text(
            r"Routine check-ups are essential for maintaining\
overall health and catching potential issues early.\
This visit will allow us to assess your current \
health status, update any vaccinations, review\
medications, and discuss any concerns you may \
have. Regular screenings for blood pressure, \
cholesterol, and glucose levels can help \
prevent chronic conditions like heart disease \
or diabetes. Staying proactive about your health \
is the best way to ensure long-term well-being.".replace(' ', "").replace("\\n", ")
        ),
    ],
    spacing= 0,
),
],
alignment= ft.alignment.top_left,
)

```

```

alertcontrol.open(True)

```

```

def onsearch(self):
    date = self.calendersearch.date
    if date:
        self._body_controls.controls = [
            i for i in self.messages if i.data['date'] == date]
    else:
        self._body_controls.controls = self.messages.copy()
    self.update()

```

```

# CREATEAPPOINTMENT.PY

```

```

import fl as ft
from utility import *

```

```

def validate(data: dict, page: ft.Page):
    # data = {'patient_last_name': 'ebong', 'patient_first_name': 'chukwu', 'patient_dob':
datetime.strptime('09/06/2000', r"%m/%d/%Y").isoformat(), 'patient_email': '2000@gmail.com',
'patient_mobile_no': '08767594456', 'patient_address': 'bitch', 'patient_gender': 'female',
'nok_phone': '08767594456', 'nok_name': 'bitch gooo', 'nok_address': 'bitch'}
    result = connect_backend(data=data, page=page, url_code= 'add_patient')

```

```

if result:
    page.session.set('Current Patient', result['data'])
    page.go('/Pdash')
    errormessage(page, f"Success: {result['message']}")

```

```

class PatientAppointmentsView(ft.View):
    def __init__(self) -> None:
        super().__init__(
            route= "/Pappoint",
            padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 25, vertical= 40),
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
        )
        color = TEXT_COLOR#CONTAINER_COLOR
        self.form = FormField([
            ft.Text("new appointment",size= 12, weight= BOLD),
            customTextField(
                "HCwName".title(),
                data= f'HCwName',
            ),
            customTextField(
                "Pid".title(),
                data= f'Pid',
            ),
            customTextField(
                "type".title(),
                data= f'type',
            ),
            customTextField( # change to date controls
                "Choose date".title(),
                data= f'Choose date',
            ),
            customTextField(
                "Reason".title(),
                type= "multiline",
                data= f'Reason',
            ),
            ft.ElevatedButton(
                "Register",
                expand= True,
                bgcolor= ACCENT2_COLOR,
                color= "white",
                style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
                    padding= 20
                ),
                on_click= lambda _: self.form.validate(
                    lambda e: validate(e, self.page)
                ),
            ),
        ],
        expand= True,
        spacing= 10,
        padding= ft.padding.symmetric(horizontal= 15)
    )

```

```

self.controls = [
    ft.Column([
        ft.Row(
            controls=[
                ft.IconButton(
                    ft.Icons.CLOSE,
                    on_click= lambda _: self.page.go('/Pdash'),
                    icon_color= color,
                    style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                        overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, color)
                    )
                ),
                ft.Text(
                    'Create Appointment',
                    expand= True,
                    weight= BOLD,
                    size= 20,
                ),
            ]
        ),
        self.form,
        ft.Text(
            "Create appointments for patients here",
            size= 11,
            text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
        ),
    ],
    expand= True,
    horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
    spacing= 10,
)
]

```

```
# PATIENTDASHBOARD.PY
```

```
import flet as ft
from utility import *
```

```
class PatientDashboardView(ft.View):
```

```
    def __init__(self) -> None:
```

```
        super().__init__(
            route= "/Pdash",
            padding= 40,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor= BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN,
        )
```

```
        accent_color = ACCENT2_COLOR
```

```
        self.NName = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
```

```
        self.Name = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
```

```
        self.Id = ft.Ref[ft.Text]()
```

```
        self.controls = [
```

```
            ft.Text("Patient Dashboard", size= 20, weight= BOLD),
```

```
            ft.Row([ft.Container(
```

```
                ft.Column(
```

```
                    controls=[
```

```
                        ft.Container(
```

```

        ft.Text(
            'AP',
            size= 20,
            color= 'white',
            ref= self.NName,
            text_align= ft.TextAlign.CENTER,
        ),
        bgcolor= accent_color,
        padding= 5,
        border_radius= 50,
        width= 40,
        height= 40,
        alignment= ft.alignment.center
    ),
    ft.Text(
        'Ajuga Peterben',
        weight= BOLD,
        color= accent_color,
        ref= self.Name,
    ),
    ft.Text(
        'Aks-000024',
        ref= self.Id,
        color= TEXT_COLOR,
    ),
],
horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
spacing= 0
),
bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
padding= 10,
border_radius= 10,
expand= True,
)],
ft.Row([
    navbuttons(
        'Vital Signs',
        r'\heart-rate.svg',
        'Pulse Rate, Blood Pressure,...',
        4
    ),
    navbuttons(
        'Provisional Diagnoses',
        r'\stethoscope.svg',
        'Examinations',
        3,
        lambda e: self.page.go('/Dign')
    ),
]),
ft.Row([
    navbuttons(
        'Medical History',
        r'\medical-report.svg',
        'Patient Diagnosis Records',
        3,
        # lambda e:

```

```

    ),
    navbuttons(
        'Patient Appointments',
        r'\twenty-two-calendar.svg',
        'Create appointments',
        4,
        lambda e: self.page.go('/Pappoint')
    ),
    ],
    ft.Row([
        ft.ElevatedButton(
            "Back",
            expand= True,
            bgcolor= accent_color,
            color= "white",
            style= ft.ButtonStyle(
                shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(radius= 5),
                padding= 20
            ),
            on_click= lambda e: self.page.go('/Plist')
        )
    ]),
]

```

```

def did_mount(self):
    data = self.page.session.get('Current Patient')
    self.Name.current.value = f" {data['first_name']} {data['last_name']}.title()
    self.NName.current.value = f" {data['first_name'][0]} {data['last_name'][0]}.upper()
    self.Id.current.value = f"Aks- {int(data['patient_id']):06d}"
    self.update()
    return super().did_mount()

```

PATIENTLIST.PY

```

import fllet as ft
from utility import *

```

```

class SearchBar(ft.Container):

```

```

    def __init__(self, onclick= None, on_back= None, on_clear= None):
        super().__init__(
            # visible= visible,
            margin= ft.margin.only(5, 20, 5, 5),
        )
        search_color = ACCENT2_COLOR
        # h_color = CONTRAST_COLOR
        self.b_onclick= on_back
        self.on_clear = on_clear
        self.back_but = ft.IconButton(
            ft.Icons.ARROW_BACK,
            on_click=self.onback,
            icon_color= search_color,
            visible= False
        )
        self.input = ft.TextField(
            expand= True,
            on_submit= lambda e: onclick(),
            prefix_icon= ft.Icons.SEARCH,

```

```

border_radius= 10,
dense= True,
text_size= 15,
hint_text= 'Search for patients',
hint_style= ft.TextStyle(
    color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.6, TEXT_COLOR),
),
bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
border_width= 0,
suffix= ft.IconButton(
    ft.Icons.CLOSE,
    icon_size= 11,
    height= 25,
    width= 25,
    on_click= self.clear
),
)
self.content = ft.Row(
    controls=[
        self.back_but,
        self.input,
    ],
    alignment= ft.MainAxisAlignment.CENTER,
)

def onback(self, e):
    self.b_onclick()
    self.clear()

def clear(self, e):
    self.input.value = ""
    if self.on_clear != None: self.on_clear()
    self.update()

class PatientTile(ft.ElevatedButton):
    def __init__(self, _data, on_click, padding=7):
        super().__init__(
            content= ft.Row(
                controls=[
                    ft.Column(
                        controls=[
                            ft.Text(
                                f" {_data['first_name']} {_data['last_name']}.title(),
                                size= 17,
                                expand= True,
                                color= TEXT_COLOR,
                            ),
                            ft.Text(
                                f"Medical ID: Aks- {str(_data['patient_id']).zfill(padding)}",
                                size= 12,
                                expand= True,
                                # weight= ft.FontWeight.W_300,
                                color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.8, TEXT_COLOR),
                            ),
                        ],
                    ),
                ],
                expand= True,

```

```

        spacing= 0,
        alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.START,
    ),
]
),
on_click= on_click,
style= ft.ButtonStyle(
    shape= ft.RoundedRectangleBorder(10),
    padding= 10,
    bgcolor= CONTAINER_COLOR,
    overlay_color= ft.Colors.with_opacity(0.3, BACKGROUND_COLOR),
)
)
)

```

```
class PatientListView(ft.View):
```

```
    def __init__(self) -> None:
```

```

        super().__init__(
            route= "/Plist",
            padding= 10,
            horizontal_alignment= ft.CrossAxisAlignment.CENTER,
            bgcolor = BACKGROUND_COLOR,
            scroll= ft.ScrollMode.HIDDEN,
            navigation_bar= customHCWNavbar(1),
            # appbar= ft.AppBar(),
        )

```

```
        self.searchbar = SearchBar()
```

```
        # get all the patientdata
```

```

        self.body = ft.ListView(
            spacing= 10,
            padding= 10,
            expand= True,
        )

```

```

        self.controls = [
            self.searchbar,
            self.body,
        ]

```

```
    def did_mount(self): # add reload function
```

```
        patients = saveload_cahce(self.page, "patientlist", default= [])
```

```
        self.update_list(patients)
```

```
        overlays = overlay(self.page)
```

```
        if not patients:
```

```

            overlays.loadingview.open(True, src="/help.svg", text= 'Checking patient list') # change to
a decorator

```

```
            self.navigation_bar.visible = False
```

```
            self.update()
```

```
            patients = connect_backend(page=self.page, url_code= '/get_patient')['message']
```

```
            self.update_list(patients)
```

```
            overlays.loadingview.open(False) # change to a decorator
```

```
            saveload_cahce(self.page, "patientlist", patients)
```

```
            self.navigation_bar.visible = True
```

```
            self.update()
```

```
            return super().did_mount()
```

```
    def update_list(self, patients):
```

```
        if patients:
```

```
self.body.controls.clear()
for i in patients[:100]:
    self.body.controls.append(
        PatientTile(
            i,
            on_click= lambda _, patient=i: self.login_patient(patient)
        )
    )
self.update()

def login_patient(self, patient_info):
    self.page.session.set('Current Patient', patient_info)
    self.page.go("/Pdash")
```

APPENDIX G: ML MODEL RESULTS

Extreme Gradient Boosting Training Performance

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
MAL	0.98	0.98	0.98	2183
ENFVR	0.98	0.92	0.95	927
HVAD	0.99	0.91	0.95	326
UTI	1.00	0.93	0.96	732
RTI	1.00	0.97	0.99	865
TB	1.00	1.00	1.00	299
micro avg	0.99	0.96	0.97	5332
macro avg	0.99	0.95	0.97	5332
weighted avg	0.99	0.96	0.97	5332
samples avg	0.87	0.85	0.86	5332
AUC-ROC	0.97			

Extreme Gradient Boosting Testing Performance

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
MAL	0.84	0.90	0.87	536
ENFVR	0.64	0.56	0.60	230
HVAD	0.62	0.40	0.48	98
UTI	0.77	0.63	0.70	175
RTI	0.77	0.68	0.72	229
TB	0.72	0.60	0.65	82
micro avg	0.77	0.72	0.74	1350
macro avg	0.73	0.63	0.67	1350
weighted avg	0.76	0.72	0.73	1350
samples avg	0.70	0.67	0.66	1350
AUC-ROC	0.756			

Random Forest Training Performance

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
MAL	0.99	0.99	0.99	2183
ENFVR	1.00	0.98	0.99	927
HVAD	1.00	0.97	0.98	326
UTI	1.00	0.98	0.99	732
RTI	1.00	0.99	1.00	865
TB	1.00	1.00	1.00	299

micro avg	1.00	0.99	0.99	5332
macro avg	1.00	0.99	0.99	5332
weighted avg	1.00	0.99	0.99	5332
samples avg	0.88	0.88	0.88	5332
AUC-ROC	0.99			

Random Forest Testing Performance

	precision	recall	f1-score	Support
MAL	0.85	0.91	0.88	536
ENFVR	0.69	0.53	0.60	230
HVAD	0.75	0.39	0.51	98
UTI	0.80	0.65	0.72	175
RTI	0.77	0.68	0.72	229
TB	0.77	0.49	0.60	82
micro avg	0.80	0.71	0.75	1350
macro avg	0.77	0.61	0.67	1350
weighted avg	0.79	0.71	0.74	1350
samples avg	0.72	0.67	0.67	1350
AUC-ROC	0.752			

MLP Training Performance

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
MAL	0.88	0.91	0.90	2183
ENFVR	0.73	0.54	0.62	927
HVAD	0.84	0.42	0.56	326
UTI	0.85	0.67	0.75	732
RTI	0.79	0.74	0.76	865
TB	0.87	0.59	0.70	299
micro avg	0.84	0.74	0.78	5332
macro avg	0.83	0.64	0.72	5332
weighted avg	0.83	0.74	0.78	5332
samples avg	0.75	0.69	0.69	5332
AUC-ROC	0.78			

MLP Testing Performance

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
MAL	0.84	0.87	0.85	536
ENFVR	0.65	0.42	0.51	230
HVAD	0.75	0.34	0.46	98
UTI	0.77	0.65	0.70	175
RTI	0.75	0.63	0.69	229
TB	0.72	0.59	0.64	82
micro avg	0.78	0.67	0.72	1350
macro avg	0.74	0.58	0.64	1350
weighted avg	0.77	0.67	0.71	1350
samples avg	0.70	0.64	0.64	1350
AUC-ROC	0.734			

APPENDIX H: PATIENT SYMPTOM ASSESSMENT & DISEASE CONFIRMATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Patient Symptom Assessment & Disease Confirmation Questionnaire

This questionnaire is part of a PhD research study aimed at evaluating a software-based Enhanced Diagnostic System for diagnosing febrile diseases, including malaria, typhoid fever, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, respiratory tract infections, and urinary tract infections. The collected data will be used solely for academic research and system validation, ensuring patient confidentiality and ethical compliance.

Section A: Patient Information

Patient ID	
Age	
Gender	

Section B: Symptom Assessment

Instructions: Tick (✓) the presence of symptoms experienced by the patient. Mark the severity using the scale: (1) Absent, (2) Low, (3) Moderate, (4) Severe, (5) Very Severe.

Symptoms		(1) Absent	(2) Low	(3) Moderate	(4) Severe	(5) Very Severe
1	Abdominal pains					
2	Bitter taste in Mouth					
3	Bloody urine					
4	Catarrh					
5	Chest Indraw					
6	Chest pain					
7	Chills and Rigors					
8	Constipation					
9	Cough (initial dry)					
10	Difficulty breathing					
11	Dry cough					
12	Fatigue					
13	Fever					
14	High-grade fever					
15	Stepwise rise fever					
16	Low-grade fever					

17	Foul breath					
18	Generalized body pain					
19	Generalized rashes					
20	Headaches					
21	Lethargy					
22	Lymph node swelling					
23	Muscle and body pain					
24	Mouth ulcer					
25	Nausea					
26	Night sweats					
27	Painful urination					
28	Sore throat					
29	Suprapubic pains					
30	Urinary frequency					
31	Vomiting					
32	Wheezing					

Section C: Laboratory Test Results & Diagnosis

(To be completed after lab confirmation)

Diseases		Confirmed	Severity
1	Malaria		
2	Typhoid fever		
3	HIV and AIDS		
4	Urinary tract infection		
5	Respiratory tract infection		
6	Tuberculosis		

Section D: Additional Observations (Optional)

Doctor's Notes:

APPENDIX I: CONFIRMED AND EDS RESULTS

Patient	Abdc	Head	Bitte	Leth	Bloo	Lymf	Catai	Musc	Ches	Mou	Ches	Naus	Chill	Nigh	Cons	Painf	Coug	Sore	Diffi	Supr	Dry c	Urin:	Fatig	Vom	Feve	Whe	High	Step	Low-	Foul	Gene	Gene	Confirmed Diagnosis	EDS Diagnosis	Correctly	False Posti	False Ne	
P1	2	2	2	3	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	5	4	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	4	1	5	4	3	3	2	1	Typhoid Fever, Mala	Typhoid Fever,	1	0	0	
P2	1	2	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	1	1	2	1	1	1	5	1	5	2	4	4	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	1	0	0	
P3	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	3	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	1	0	0	
P4	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	5	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	1	0	0		
P5	4	2	1	3	1	2	1	5	1	4	1	1	1	5	5	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	4	4	4	2	HIV/AIDS, Typhoid F	HIV/AIDS, Mala	0	1	0		
P6	1	5	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	3	1	4	1	1	3	1	Malaria	Malaria	1	0	0		
P7	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Malaria, Urinar	0	1	0		
P8	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	5	2	1	4	1	1	2	1	Malaria	Malaria	1	0	0		
P9	5	5	1	2	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	4	1	1	1	4	1	4	1	1	2	1	1	5	3	3	2	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	0	1	0	
P10	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	0	1	0		
P11	1	5	4	1	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	3	5	1	1	1	1	2	1	4	1	4	5	3	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	Malaria, Tuberculosi	Malaria, Respir	1	0	0		
P12	1	5	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	4	5	1	1	4	1	1	1	4	1	3	4	3	5	1	4	1	1	1	3	1	Malaria, Urinary Trac	Malaria, Urinar	1	0	0		
P13	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	4	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Tuberculosis	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P14	1	1	1	5	1	4	1	1	1	4	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	4	HIV/AIDS	HIV/AIDS	1	0	0	
P15	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	HIV/AIDS	HIV/AIDS	1	0	0	
P16	1	1	1	2	5	4	1	1	1	3	1	1	5	1	3	1	3	1	4	1	5	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	4	5	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	0	1	0		
P17	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	5	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	0	1	0	
P18	3	3	1	3	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	5	4	3	4	1	Typhoid Fever, Urin	Malaria, Urinar	0	1	0	
P19	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	HIV/AIDS	Malaria, HIV/A	0	1	0	
P20	5	4	1	3	1	1	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	4	1	1	3	4	5	2	1	Respiratory Tract Inf	Respiratory Tra	0	1	0	
P21	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	2	1	4	1	1	3	1	2	1	1	2	5	3	2	4	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	1	0	0	
P22	1	3	4	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	5	2	1	1	1	2	5	4	1	1	1	4	3	3	5	1	1	1	3	1	Malaria, Respiratory	Malaria, Respir	1	0	0		
P23	1	3	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	3	5	3	4	1	1	1	1	3	1	4	1	2	4	4	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	Malaria, Tuberculosi	Malaria	0	1	0		
P24	4	2	1	3	1	5	1	4	1	5	1	1	3	4	5	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	3	4	3	5	4	HIV/AIDS, Typhoid F	HIV/AIDS, Typh	0	1	0		
P25	3	5	5	3	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	5	4	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	2	1	5	5	5	2	2	1	Malaria, Typhoid Fev	Malaria, Typho	1	0	0	
P26	1	4	2	5	1	5	1	1	1	3	1	3	3	5	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	1	5	1	1	2	5	HIV/AIDS, Malaria	HIV/AIDS, Mala	1	0	0		
P27	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	1	4	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	HIV/AIDS	HIV/AIDS	1	0	0		
P28	1	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	4	1	3	1	1	1	5	1	Malaria	Malaria	1	0	0	
P29	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	4	1	1	5	1	1	1	3	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Tuberculosis	Tuberculosis, R	1	0	0	
P30	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	Respiratory Tract Inf	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P31	5	5	1	2	1	2	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	4	5	4	3	5	HIV/AIDS, Typhoid F	HIV/AIDS, Typh	0	1	0	
P32	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	4	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	Respiratory Tract Inf	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P33	1	5	3	1	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	5	5	1	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	2	4	4	1	5	1	1	1	2	1	Malaria, Tuberculosi	Malaria, Respir	1	0	0		
P34	1	1	1	4	1	3	1	1	1	5	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	HIV/AIDS	HIV/AIDS	1	0	0
P35	2	4	1	3	1	3	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	2	4	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	2	2	5	3	Typhoid Fever, HIV//	Typhoid Fever,	0	1	0	
P36	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	4	1	5	1	1	4	1	4	1	1	4	2	4	5	4	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	1	0	0	
P37	1	1	1	5	1	4	1	1	1	4	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	HIV/AIDS	HIV/AIDS	1	0	0	
P38	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	4	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	3	2	3	1	5	1	4	1	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	Tuberculosis, Respir	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P39	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	Respiratory Tract Inf	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P40	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	3	1	3	1	1	4	1	1	5	3	2	1	4	1	3	1	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	Respiratory Tract Inf	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P41	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	4	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	Urinary Tract Infectic	No Disease	0	0	1	
P42	2	3	1	4	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	5	3	4	1	Typhoid Fever	Typhoid Fever	1	0	0	
P43	1	1	1	5	1	5	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	4	3	4	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	5	HIV/AIDS, Respirat	HIV/AIDS, Resp	1	0	0		
P44	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	3	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Tuberculosis	Tuberculosis	1	0	0	
P45	4	2	1	3	1	1	1	2	5	1	2	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	3	1	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	3	5	4	1	Tuberculosis, Typho	Malaria, Typho	0	1	0	
P46	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	Respiratory Tract Inf	Respiratory Tra	1	0	0	
P47	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	1	3	1	1	4	1	2	1	1	4	5	2	5	3	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	Tuberculosis, Urinar	Tuberculosis, U	1	0	0		
P48	1	1	1	5	5	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	3	1	2	1	4	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	Urinary Tract Infectic	Urinary Tract In	0	1	0	

